

Coherent & Cross-compliant Ocean Governance for Delivering the EU Green Deal for European Seas

Deliverable 2.2

Horizontal coherence in EU law and policy: Analysing, explaining and improving the horizontal coherence of EU policy design

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ABSTRACT

The report presents the initial findings of T2.2 of the CrossGov project on improving coherence in marine policies within the framework of the European Green Deal (EGD). It includes a coherence analysis of the EGD's ocean-related policies, and the findings from constitutional analysis and stakeholder interviews for explanatory factors for incoherence. The report emphasises the need for improving policy coherence to bridge the gap between EGD's long-term vision and current policymaking.

KEYWORDS

European Green Deal; policy coherence; explanatory factors; marine environmental law;

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Executive Summary

The European Commission launched the European Green Deal (EGD) for the European Union and its citizens in 2019. It is Union's response to the urgent climate and environmental-related challenges while also ensuring that the solutions are protecting the health and well-being of its citizens, just and inclusive and sets the Union on a path of sustainable and inclusive growth. The EGD focuses on three main environmental challenges - biodiversity, climate change and pollution – creating corresponding policy streams. The three challenges are interconnected and one cannot be solved without substantial progress in the others. However, the contribution of each policy stream to the sustainability transition is expected to differ and comes with a unique set of implementation challenges. While all three policy streams are crucial for sustainability, they relate to and address different aspects of it.

This report aims to evaluate the horizontal coherence between EU policies central for the achievement of the EGD objectives regarding the marine environment. Policy coherence refers to how well policies reinforce each other by promoting synergies or reducing conflicts between their objectives and measures both in design and implementation, while horizontal coherence refers to coherence between policies on the same governance level. The report builds on the work done in earlier deliverables of the CrossGov project which has identified the objectives, mapped the policies and formed coherence and cross-compliance evaluation methodologies.

To define the research object, the analysis was done in five different policy clusters: Biodiversity stream, Zero pollution stream, Agriculture and nutrient pollution, Fisheries and biodiversity, and Renewable energy, offshore wind power and biodiversity. The two first clusters were focused on intra-coherence between policies with marine environmental protection objectives to see to which extent the objectives and the instruments of the policies within the cluster are coherent in forming a uniform ambition on the level of protection and means to achieve it. Further, three clusters analyse the coherence in the relation between key economic activities and their impact on the EGD's environmental objectives. These are cross-cutting with different, and often somewhat contradictory aims, as they regulate pressures including objectives that could entail increased pressures on the marine environment while also set out to protect the same.

The report analyses two different aspects of policy coherence through a multi-disciplinary approach. The first aspect is the analysis of coherence attributes through analysis of the policies and their objectives and instruments. The second aspect is the explanatory factors that aims to reveal reasons for the origin of (in)coherence. This is analysed through the EU constitutional setting of the policies as well as through interviews with stakeholders from the European Commission. For the interviews, the preliminary results of the coherence attributes analysis were summarised into one-pagers (see Annex II).

The results reveal that there are no glaring negative impacts between the policies objectives where they set out to achieve direct contradictory objectives. The ambition for environmental objectives in the sectoral policy instruments has continuously been raised throughout the last decades. However, there is risk for internal contradictions as the objectives are set out to achieve objectives that may hinder the achievement of each other, which in turn may cause incoherence between objectives for

different policies. As the core logic for most sector policies is not to achieve environmental protection, this is often not the priority when having to make prioritisations. Further, the different policies have objectives that differ in inter alia legal bindingness, scope, timeframes and exemptions which creates fragmentation between policies, affecting the efficiency and effectiveness.

The analysis of policy instruments reveals that environmental protection instruments remain at the fringe of economic activities. They generally lack capacity to regulate and push economic activities on their own, such as the sectors analysed in this report while certain instruments have considerably more legal forcefulness than others such as the Water Framework Directive. The sector policies analysed have legal instruments aimed to protect the marine environment that differ in design, where some are designed to effectively support EGD objectives on an EU level (for example policies on fisheries) while others are designed with a higher level of subsidiarity that more heavily relies on effective national implementation to achieve the same (agriculture). Both approaches have historically had difficulties to be as effective as intended for different reasons. For some sector policies, conflicts emerge from competing environmental interests. Overall, the policies have objectives and instruments which are designed to achieve coherence and to achieve the EGD objectives but generally lack the forcefulness, bindingness, effectiveness, and efficiency to properly and timely reach set objectives.

The analysis of explanatory factors revealed several factors that can have and are influencing the design of the policies and the detected coherence challenges therein and in the implementation. Firstly, the EU constitutional and administrative law structures governing the EU's legislative and policy formulation competences and the setup of EU institutions may explain the level of (in)coherence found at the level of EU law and policy. The policies analysed are based on different Treaty bases, including environmental policy (art. 191 TFEU), internal market (art. 26 and 114 TFEU), fisheries policy (art. 38 TFEU), agricultural policy (art. 38 and 39 TFEU) and energy policy (art. 194 TFEU). While environmental policy competences require integration of socio-economic aspects into the policies, the reverse is not the case for all economic policy competences that highlight promoting the economic activities. Furthermore, the different natures of EU competences – shared or exclusive – can affect the possibilities of Member States in striving to mitigate incoherence in national implementation. Secondly, the expert interviews shed some light on other factors explaining incoherence, including governmental organisational structures, science-policy-interfaces, and stakeholder participation. Most notable factors identified included the policy silos established by the structures of the Commission's Directorate Generals, lack of comprehensive scientific knowledge on the marine environment and varying scope of impact assessments for the policies as well as imbalances in stakeholder involvement and lobbying.

Acronyms

AECM	Agri-Environmental-Climate Measure
BD	Birds Directive
CAP	Common Agricultural Policy
CFP	Common Fisheries Policy
CJEU	Court of Justice of the European Union
DG	Directorate-General
DG AGRI	Directorate-General for Agriculture and Rural Development
DG Energy	Directorate-General for Energy
DG ENV	Directorate-General for the Environment
DG MARE	Directorate-General for Maritime Affairs and Fisheries
EAGF	European Agricultural Guarantee Fund
EAFRD	European Agricultural Fund for Rural Development
EEA	European Environment Agency
EGD	European Green Deal
EIA	Environmental Impact Assessment
EMFAF	European Maritime, Fisheries and Aquaculture Fund
EMFF	European Maritime and Fisheries Fund
EQSD	Environmental Quality Standards Directive
EU	European Union
EUCFR	Charter of Fundamental Rights of the European Union
FCS	Favourable Conservation Status
GAEC	Good Agricultural and Environmental Conditions
GD	Green Deal

GES	Good Environmental Status
GHG	Greenhouse Gas
HD	Habitats Directive
ICES	International Council for the Exploration of the Sea
MGES	Good Marine Environmental Status
MPA	Marine Protected Area
MSFD	Marine Strategy Framework Directive
MSP	Maritime Spatial Plan
MSPD	Maritime Spatial Planning Directive
MSY	Maximum Sustainable Yield
ND	Nitrates Directive
NECP	National Energy and Climate Plans
NRL	Nature Restoration Law
NVZ	Nitrates Vulnerable Zone
OECM	Other Effective Area-Based Conservation Measures
PoM	Programmes of Measure
RBMP	River Basin Management Plan
RDP	Rural Development Programme
RED III	2023 EU Renewable Energy Directive
SAC	Special Areas of Conservation
SEA	Strategic Environmental Assessment
SMR	Statutory Management Requirements
SPA	Special Protection Areas for Birds
SWOT	Strengths, Weaknesses, Opportunities and Threats

TAC	Total Annual Catch
TEU	Treaty on European Union
TFEU	Treaty on the Functioning of the European Union
UAA	Utilised Agricultural Area
UN	United Nations
UNCLOS	United Nations Convention on the Law of the Sea
WFD	Water Framework Directive
WP	Work Package

I Introduction to the report

1. Introduction

1.1 The European Green Deal

European seas are among some of the busiest in the world, where multiple maritime sectors are competing for limited space and resources. Human and economic activities are creating severe pressures on the marine ecosystems, leading to environmental degradation through pollution, overexploitation, habitat destruction, and climate changes. Land-based activities add additional pressure on marine ecosystems, for example through run-off from fresh-water basins and agricultural practices. The decline in marine natural capital poses significant threats to Europe's economy, the livelihoods of coastal communities and the health and well-being of the citizens more broadly.

In December 2019, the European Commission launched the European Green Deal (EGD) for the European Union and its citizens (European Commission, 2019). The EGD is the European Union's response to the urgent climate and environmental-related challenges while also ensuring that the solutions are protecting the health and well-being of its citizens, just and inclusive and sets the union on a path of sustainable and inclusive growth. The communication of the EGD presented the key policies and measures needed to achieve its objectives with an ambition to create an interconnected and integrated approach to the challenges. The EGD focuses on three main environmental challenges - biodiversity, climate change and pollution – creating corresponding policy streams.¹ The three challenges are interconnected and one cannot be solved without substantial progress in the others. However, the contribution of each policy stream to the sustainability transition is expected to differ and comes with a unique set of implementation challenges. While all three policy streams are crucial for sustainability, they relate to and address different aspects of it.

The biodiversity stream's primary policy objective is to halt the loss of biodiversity, preserve and restore degraded ecosystems in Europe and worldwide. That is primarily operationalized by the EU Biodiversity Strategy for 2030, which includes initiatives to establish a network of protected areas, promote sustainable agriculture, fisheries and forestry, address the impacts of invasive species and wildlife trade, and promote green infrastructure. At the same time, it purports to mainstream biodiversity considerations across all policy areas and to support international cooperation to address the dramatic biodiversity loss at the global level.

The climate change stream sets to achieve the goal of climate-neutrality by 2050, in line with the commitments under the Paris Agreement. To achieve the goal of climate neutrality, the focus is put on reducing emissions (decarbonization) and enhancing the energy transition through the supply of clean, affordable and secure energy as well as the acceleration of the shift to sustainable and smart mobility. It aims primarily to increase the share of renewable energy, improve energy efficiency, promote sustainable transport, and reduce greenhouse gas emissions from industry, buildings, and agriculture.

¹ For a comprehensive review of the EGD objectives, goals and targets, see CrossGov [deliverable 1.1](#).

The zero-pollution stream establishes an action plan to achieve a toxic-free environment to protect human health and the environment by reducing pollution from all sources. It mainly aims to reduce air, water, and soil pollution, promote sustainable chemicals, and address the impacts of hazardous substances on human health and the environment.

At the same time, marine waters are important for economic activities as the EU is looking to enable blue growth with several economic sectors looking to increase their activities in the marine domain. The interrelated policy streams of biodiversity, climate change and pollution are supported by coordinated and cross-cutting efforts towards a sustainable food system, renewable energy production, circular economy and smart mobility. For instance, there are strong interlinkages and synergies between biodiversity, the promotion of an environmentally friendly food system and the development of the circular economy, which can to a considerable extent reduce the environmental impact of human activities on ecosystems. Similarly, the efforts regarding circular economy and its focus on reducing waste and plastic pollution contribute towards the pollution ambition of the EGD.

1.2 About this report

This report consists of a coherence analysis of EU law and policy within the [CrossGov project](#), a 3-year research endeavour. The project aims to improve the coherence of multi-level and multi-sectoral marine policies and their environmental and social cross-compliance. Policy coherence refers to how well policies reinforce each other by promoting synergies or reducing conflicts between their objectives and measures both in design and implementation (CrossGov Deliverable 1.3). Such coherence exists both within the same governance level, referred to as horizontal coherence, and across different governance levels, referred to as vertical coherence. A high level of coherence contributes to the cross-compliance - the delivery of multiple Green Deal strategies, goals and targets in concert.

Task 2 of Work Package (WP) 2 of the project, aims to analyse, explain, and improve the horizontal coherence of EU policy design. The task aims to build on the work done in previous tasks which includes development of methods and definitions used in the CrossGov project as well as concretisation of policy targets in the EGD and mapping of the EU policy landscape and designs. For detailed insights, readers are referred to several key deliverables: [deliverable 1.1](#) (Scoping: Concretising the policy targets and developing key scenarios), [deliverable 1.2](#) (Policy Brief on Coherent and Cross-compliant Ocean Governance for Delivering the Green Deal for European Seas), [deliverable 1.3](#) (The CrossGov Policy Coherence Evaluation Framework - A methodological framework to assess policy coherence and cross-compliance with the European Green Deal) and [deliverable 2.1](#) (Mapping EU policies and Green Deal objectives: observations for policy coherence in the marine domain).

2. Methodological approach

2.1 CrossGov Policy Coherence Evaluation Framework

The CrossGov Policy Coherence Evaluation Framework applies a comprehensive methodological approach for assessing policy coherence.² The framework is developed to create a better understanding of where in the policy cycle or at which governance level coherence issues emerge and where they can be effectively addressed. To understand the level of coherence, the framework explores coherence between the objectives across policies and between levels of governance. This report, however, focuses on the EU level of governance and the coherence between instruments on the same level of governance. The coherence between levels of governance will be further explored in deliverable 2.3. The evaluation is not restricted the evaluation to analyzing alignment across objectives though. The report also addresses the set of policy instruments set out in the policies (instrumentation) and how these have been designed to meet the policy’s objectives (internal coherence), as well as their contribution towards the EGD objectives (cross-compliance).

To enable this, an evaluation framework has been developed based on coherence attributes and explanatory factors to assess against, guiding questions to support the assessment and a simplified coherence scoring. The evaluation framework first components are the coherence attributes and explanatory factors. These are elements or contextual factors of a policy that allow to better understand what causes low or high coherence. The evaluation framework contains two coherence attributes to assess the degree of coherence (namely policy objectives and policy instruments), and three explanatory variables, which contribute to explain the level of coherence. Each of the attributes and variables are accompanied by guiding questions to support the assessment. Not all coherence attributes and explanatory factors will be relevant in all tasks.

Figure 1 Coherence attributes and explanatory variables

Policy objectives refers to the outcomes the policy sets out to achieve. This includes the outcomes specified in the articles of the policy document as well as broader objectives referred to in the preamble. The integration of key policy and societal goals and considerations from other policies/sectors should also be assessed under this attribute (mainstreaming). For policies to be

² For a full explanation of the CrossGov Policy Coherence Evaluation Framework, see CrossGov [deliverable 1.3](#).

coherent, the policy objectives should be aligned or complementary and not contradict or impede each other.

Policy Instruments refers to the mechanisms and instruments that are put in place by the policy to achieve its objectives. The term 'Instruments' is understood in a broad sense as anything that is put in place to reach the policy objectives. This can be market-based instruments, legal instruments, planning mechanisms, monitoring and reporting frameworks, educational programmes, funding schemes and other resources made available to implement the policy, to give some indications. A high level of alignment of policy instruments is considered beneficial for policy coherence.

Governmental organizational structures refer to the government's organizational structure that sets the framework within which policies are formulated and implemented. These structures include the involved and responsible governmental organizations, their roles, and responsibilities as well as coordination mechanisms. Clear responsibilities and means to work towards EGD objectives are more likely to foster collaboration and prioritize policies and actions that deliver against the EGD objectives. To enable exchange, consistent cross-sectoral approaches and joint decisions, coordination and collaboration within and across organizations should be implemented.

Science-policy-society interfaces are the social processes that describe the role of knowledge production, transfer and use in decision-making processes. The interfaces can be studied in specific science-policy-society systems, referring to the actors involved as well as their roles within the different phases of the policy cycle. Effective science-policy-society interfaces can enable and support policy coherence. Policy coherence depends on clear science and knowledge that provides a shared evidence base for coherent decisions.

Stakeholder involvement processes refer to the manner in which stakeholders influence policy framing, design and implementation through participatory processes and other avenues such as information campaigns and lobbying, and how this affects the policies. While science-policy-society interfaces shed light on how stakeholders affect the production and transfer of knowledge, this variable explicitly focuses on how stakeholders shape policy alternatives both during the formulation and design of policies as well as their implementation. This variable sheds light on power dynamics across actor, actor involvement and other factors relevant for the shaping and implementation of policies.

2.2 Multi-disciplinary approach

To explore the coherence attributes and explanatory values, the report will use a multi-disciplinary approach. The guiding questions posed by the coherence framework are multi-faceted and, thus, need more than a single method to be answered as comprehensively and precisely as possible. The approach will be two-folded with application of both legal and policy analysis.

To delimit the research object, the analysis will be done in five different clusters of laws and policies. The clusters have been selected to reflect the EGD's approach to the environmental-related challenges while also considering its objective of sustainable growth. The five clusters identified for analysis are:

- Biodiversity stream
- Zero pollution stream
- Agriculture and nutrient pollution
- Fisheries and biodiversity
- Renewable energy, offshore wind power and biodiversity

As such, the five clusters include two that considers the intra-coherence between environmental protection objectives – biodiversity and pollution. These clusters will explore how different policies, all with environmental protection as their main objectives, work in synergy to achieve set objectives. Delivering the overall ambitions of the EGD related to marine environment relies on the combined framework of these directives and its implementation in EU Member States. For assessing the coherence of EU policies towards the EGD objectives, it is necessary to assess – in accordance with the CrossGov coherence methodology – to which extent the *objectives* and the *instruments* (coherence attributes) of the policies within the cluster are coherent in forming a uniform ambition on the level of protection and means to achieve it.

Further, three clusters analyse the coherence in the relation between key economic activities and their impact on the EGD’s environmental objectives – agriculture, fisheries, and offshore renewable energy. Unlike the first two clusters, these are cross-cutting in the sense that they are policies with different, and often somewhat contradictory aims. The clusters include policies that have objectives that regulate sectors that represents a pressure to the marine environments, including objectives of expansion of said sectors, and to achieve the EGD objectives must work in synergy with corresponding environmental directives to grow in a sustainable way.

The clusters are not a complete representation of the EGD as it will exclude both environmental objectives and activities that are indirectly affected by the EGD ambitions. However, the clusters are expected to provide a good representation of such objectives and activities, thus providing both robust answers to certain issues and general indications of systematic issues in coherence in delivery mechanisms and reasons behind them.

The analysis applied a pilot approach as it was the first practical application of the CrossGov methodology on horizontal coherence. The method was first tested on the biodiversity cluster by creating a pilot analysis. The pilot was analysed in depth and used to adjust the method before the biodiversity chapter was rewritten based on the findings. The following clusters were subsequently written based on these findings. Further, a one-page summary of preliminary findings was written for each cluster and used in interviews with relevant actors in the form of European Commission members from relevant DGs. The one-pagers (see Annex II) were used to verify the findings in the analysis of coherence attributes and as a basis to untangle the explanatory variables.

All five cluster chapters are written using the same structure, albeit some differences are necessary due to the differences in subject matter. The first part of the analysis concerns the coherence attributes in the form of policy objectives. This includes a comparison between policy objectives within policies included in the cluster to evaluate coherence using the guidance questions from the CrossGov Policy Coherence Evaluation Framework to guide what aspects to compare. This includes the objectives

formulated for the policies, but also aspect of inter alia scope, timeframe, legal implications and exemptions from such legal implications.

The second part concerns the wide array of policy instruments that are used to achieve the set objectives. To achieve the set objectives of the policies, policy instruments are established for the implementation. The instruments differ depending on inter alia the legal act used, the objectives that are set out to be accomplished or governance level where they are implemented.

Coherence attributes, coherence between objectives and instruments, relate to the formulation and content of the law, which legal analysis will be applied as the chosen method to unpack them. This includes traditional doctrinal legal research that will be applied to determine to what extent the EU law and policy landscape is coherent and to identify where the incoherences are, assuming such exist. For policy objectives, this includes finding contradictions, overlaps or gaps in scope, differences in timeframes or legal implications, applicable exemptions and other factors that affect the coherence between policies. For policy instruments, this includes legal implications of the different instruments and whether they are forming a uniform approach in relation to their objectives and the objectives of the EGD.

After the coherence attributes have been analysed, the report will look at the explanatory variables of the policy coherence evaluation framework with the aim of explaining why incoherences arise in the EU law and policy landscape. As incoherence can arise for different reasons, the analysis will apply different methods including legal methods concerning competences and structures and policy analysis methods focusing on the explanatory variables stemming from policy creation procedures. The legal method will explore the constitutional context for the EU policy by analysing the legal bases for the policies and the legal structures governing the implementation and enforcement of EU law.

The policy analysis is based on interviews involving relevant actors in the form of European Commission members from relevant Directorate-Generals. A total of six interviews were conducted with representatives of three different DGs (two interviews each): DG MARE, DG ENERGY and DG ENV. Regrettably, representatives from DG AGRI were not available for an interview. Prior to the interviews, the participants received documents containing summaries of the preliminary results for each of the three policy clusters, a list of semi-structured questions, and a consent form for them to sign. These materials ensured that all interviewees were well-prepared and informed about the scope and purpose of the discussions.

2.3 Structure of the report

The report will be structured as follows. The report is divided into three sections. The first section (Section I) serves as an introduction to the report and contains two chapters. The first chapter introduces the context and the report itself. The second and current chapter introduces the CrossGov methodology and how it is applied in this report.

The second section (Section II) contains the coherence analysis of the EU Green Deal implementation policies. The marine waters of the EU consist of a wide variety of components in need of protection while at the same time they are subject to a diverse set of pressures. To achieve the goals set in the

EGD, the policies are required to regulate individual issues while working towards overall objectives and limit clashes with other policies. Policies are fragmented, often addressing only part of a problem or activity. Governing European seas effectively requires coherent and cross-compliant policy actions that account for interactions across sectors, interests, and governance levels. This section seeks to introduce the foundational elements of the individual policies that will be analysed in clusters in the forthcoming chapter as in what are the key goals, who is it directed to, how does it seek to influence behaviour, etc.³ The policies will be analysed in clusters with one chapter for each cluster. The first two clusters are intra-environmental policy clusters for the policy streams biodiversity (chapter 3) and the zero pollution (chapter 4). The following three clusters are for analysis of the coherence between sectoral and environmental policies: Common Agriculture Policy and pollution (chapter 5), Common Fisheries Policy and biodiversity (chapter 6) and renewable energy and offshore power (chapter 7).

The third and final section (Section III) concerns the explanatory factors of incoherence. To resolve the occurrence of incoherence between policies, there is a need to pinpoint its origin. The section will look at the explanatory factors of the incoherence findings from the previous section from two different perspectives – one legal perspective and one policy perspective. In chapter 8, the constitutional basis for the policies will be analysed to find if and how the legal structure contributes to the incoherence found. In chapter 9, the report will look into other explanatory factors by using interviews with members from relevant DGs. The report concludes with chapter 10 that summarises the general conclusions.

The report also has two annexes. The first annex contains the interview protocol and semi-structured questions that were created to facilitate the interview. The second annex contains the one-pagers with summaries of the preliminary findings for each cluster.

³ For further information on the EU policy landscape and how it connects to the EGD goals, see deliverable 2.1.

II Coherence Analysis of EU Green Deal Implementation Policies

3. The Biodiversity Stream (HD; BD; MSFD; WFD; NRL)

3.1 Introduction

The overall vision for biodiversity in the EGD is to halt the loss of biodiversity, and to preserve and restore ecosystems and biodiversity. In the marine domain, achieving this vision necessitates ensuring that the marine ecosystems are in good health, their functions that sustain biological diversity are preserved, and that the marine habitats and species in need for special protection are conserved to ensure their viability. In this vein, the EGD puts forward specific targets to pave the way for realising the overall biodiversity ambitions, which include both targets related to the state of the ecosystems and their conservation, as well as targets related managing certain key pressures and sectors of economic activity. In terms of the state of ecosystems and conservation efforts, the targets can be elaborated as follows:

By 2030:

- Legally protect a minimum of 30% of the EU's seas area and integrate ecological corridors.
- Strict legal protection of at least a third of the EU's protected areas.
- Significant areas of degraded and carbon rich ecosystems are restored, habitats and species show no deterioration in conservation status and trends, at least 30% reach favourable conservation status or at least show a positive trend.
- Effectively manage all protected areas.
- Negative impacts on sensitive species and habitats, including on the seabed, through fishing and extraction activities, are substantially reduced to reach a good environmental status.

By 2050:

- cover all ecosystems in need of restoration (CrossGov Deliverable 1.1).

The legal operationalisation of the EGD's objectives and targets into specific legal obligations and requirements on the EU Member States and relevant actors takes place within the existing framework of EU law that governs these aspects (CrossGov Deliverable 1.1). In EU law, the system of nature protection areas and the conservation regimes for habitats and species are provided in the Habitats Directive (HD) and the Birds Directive (BD) (hereafter described as the Nature Directives), which makes them key legal instruments for operationalising many of the targets. Yet, some protection requirements for habitats and species substantiating the Nature Directives have been included in the Marine Strategy Framework Directive's (MSFD) good marine environmental status objectives, particularly under the qualitative descriptors on biological diversity (D1) and seafloor integrity (D6). It is these directives that lay down primary obligations and conditions on designating marine protected areas (MPA), and thus, are a legal operationalisation of the GD's objectives related to protection area coverage.

Moreover, in the marine areas focused conservation and management efforts on delimited MPAs alone is not effective in preserving and restoring habitats, as their state is affected by the overall functioning of the aquatic ecosystem and general threats to it, such as contamination, eutrophication,

and fishing, that are not strictly located within any delimited protection areas. Albeit the GD's biodiversity objectives have an underscored focus on protected areas, especially the objective on effective management of the MPA's encompasses such wider marine environmental protection dimension. In order to effectively protect and restore marine biodiversity, ecosystem-based management regimes are needed to address the multiple pressures, utilising a variety of more specific policy instruments.⁴ In this regard, the MSFD explicitly aims towards application of ecosystem-based management⁵; in a nutshell, this means integrated management of the whole ecosystem towards ensuring that the cumulative impacts of all human activities does not affect the ecosystem integrity and functioning.⁶ Furthermore, the WFD puts forward an integrated water management regime of inland and coastal waters, which provides potential to link the status of marine waters with land-based sources of pollution. Accordingly, implementing the MSFD and the WFD towards achieving the MSFD's good marine environmental status objective (MGES) and the Water Framework Directive's (WFD) water status objectives in the coastal waters is crucial for effective management of protected areas, preventing negative impacts and degradation of habitats and species and restoring the habitats.

Furthermore, the legal landscape pertaining to operationalising the GD's objectives on marine biodiversity includes the newly adopted EU Nature Restoration Law (NRL). The NRL that intends to put forward legally binding requirements on restoration measures on coastal and marine ecosystems, which encompasses habitats protected in the HD as well as the biodiversity-related elements in the MSFD' objectives.⁷

The analysis is structured as follows. In accordance with the CrossGov methodology, subsection 3.1.2 will analyse the coherence of objectives related to marine biodiversity in the Nature Directives, the MSFD, the WFD and the NRL. This includes analysing i) the substance of the objectives – both in terms of what elements of marine biodiversity are covered and what is the ambition in the goals –, ii) timelines and deadlines for their achievement, iii) the legal force and implications of the objectives in form of obligations to Member States as well as iv) exemptions from the objectives. The purpose of the analysis is to examine whether the objectives (and exemptions) in the policies within the cluster are aligned/complementary or whether there are inconsistencies/contradictions. Subsection 3.1.3 will then follow up with analysing the coherence of the policy instruments set out in the policies (instrumentation), with a particular attention on whether and how they are designed to meet the objectives, so called internal coherence (CrossGov Deliverable 1.2). It should be noted here that the obligations on Member States deriving from the objectives and the related exemptions are considered to form a part of objectives, which is why they are addressed in there. Yet, the objectives of the policies also entail legal implications on individual activities, projects and plans and include derogations related to them; in the analysis, these aspects of the policies are addressed under the

⁴ Sander 2024.

⁵ MSFD Preamble 8.

⁶ Sander 2024.

⁷ European Parliament legislative resolution of 27 February 2024 on the proposal for a regulation of the European Parliament and of the Council on nature restoration (COM(2022)0304 – C9-0208/2022 – 2022/0195(COD)); Position of the European Parliament adopted at first reading on 27 February 2024 with a view to the adoption of Regulation (EU) 2024/... of the European Parliament and of the Council on nature restoration and amending Regulation (EU) 2022/869.

analysis of instruments. This is because the rules related to permitting of new activities, projects and plans and the conditions for derogating from the objectives in relation to authorising those projects and plans are one of the instruments through which the policies try to steer towards their goals, rather than being part of the objectives as such. Finally, the section will conclude by presenting a summary of the coherence challenges and hypotheses behind coherence problems, linking them to the explanatory variables in accordance with the CrossGov methodology.

Based on the analysis, four key coherence challenges can be identified in the joint framework of the Nature Directives, the MSFD, the WFD and the NRL. First, the objectives of the policies are fragmented with a result that no policy addresses all relevant aspects of marine biodiversity with legally forceful conservation obligations. Second, each instruments contains different deadlines for the objectives, and the timeframes are not aligned. Third, the legal obligations on Member States, legal implications on activities, plans and projects and the various exemptions from them are inconsistent with no clear linkages to one another to improve coherence. Finally, the policy instruments can be interpreted in a rather consistent manner, but the complexity creates a risk of distortion and the instruments' design leaves a lot to be desired for in terms of them being able to steer meeting the objectives. With regards to the EGD's objectives related to marine biodiversity protection, the instruments display variable degree of potential to deliver these objectives. For instance, while the 30 % goals for the protection area coverage can be legally operationalised through the complementary application of different instruments (mainly the Nature Directives and the MSFD), the EU legislation does not provide strict legal protection for the 10 % of habitats mentioned in the EGD's objectives. The hypothesised explanations behind the detected coherence problems relate to data fragmentation and science-policy interphase on the one hand, and, on the other hand, the ineffectiveness of each previous legal instrument in ensuring marine biodiversity protection, which the EU legislator has tried to rectify by adopting new, more effective instruments. These conclusions and hypotheses will be returned to in the end of this section, after the more specific and detailed analysis that is presented next.

3.2 Coherence of objectives

3.2.1 The substantive scope of the objectives

When talking about the protection of biodiversity, the EU *Nature Directives* – the *HD* and the *BD* – form the main body of legislation establishing protection goals, species conservation regimes and a network of protected sites, that is, the EU's Natura 2000 network. The general objective of the Nature Directives is striving to ensure the preservation or restoration of a favourable conservation status of the habitat types and the animal and plant species identified as in need of special protection in the directives.

The HD defines that the conservation level of a species is favourable when it is maintaining itself on a long-term basis as a viable component of its natural habitats, and its natural range is neither being reduced nor is likely to be reduced for the foreseeable future. In addition, there should be a sufficiently large habitat to maintain its populations on a long-term basis (Art 1(1), paragraph (i)).

In turn, the conservation level of habitats is favourable when its natural range and areas it covers within that range are stable or increasing, the specific structure and functions necessary for its long-term maintenance exist and are likely to continue to exist for the foreseeable future, and the conservation status of its typical species is favourable (Art 1(1) paragraph (e)).

With respect to the BD, the directive's most important substantive obligation is laid down in Article 2, according to which "Member States must take all necessary measures to maintain the populations of the bird species (...) at a level that meets especially ecological, scientific and cultural requirements, taking into account economic and recreational requirements, or to adapt these strains to this level." Although the BD does not explicitly use the concept of a favourable conservation status, its objectives are generally associated to mean striving for a favourable conservation status for all wild birds.

With regard to the scope of the objectives, the BD concerns all bird species of naturally occurring in the wild state in the Member States. The Member States are required to take the necessary measures to preserve, maintain or re-establish a sufficient diversity and area of habitats (Arts 1(1), 2(1), 3(1)). Accordingly, all sea bird species are covered by this general conservation objectives. In addition, Annex I of the Directive lists bird species – including some sea bird species – that are subject of special conservation measures (Art 4(1)). It is these species, for which special protection areas are to be designated and included in the Natura 2000 -network. Each protection area is to become a subject to specific conservation objectives (Art 4(1) of the BD, Art 3(1) of the HD). In general, the BD covers sea birds quite comprehensively with its species-level protection regimes as well as within its obligations on establishing protected areas to preserve habitats important to the viability of the sea bird species that are deemed to require special protection.

The situation is slightly different with the HD. The directive's objectives (and conservation regimes) extend to those habitats and species that are listed in the directives of being of Community interest based on the threats posed to their existence and their representativeness of Europe's biogeographical regions (Art 1(1) paragraphs (c), (d), (g) and (h)). The habitats that are of Community interest are listed in Annex I to the HD including some marine habitats. For instance in the Baltic Sea area, these include certain sandy beaches, dunes, inlets and coastal meadows and sandbanks.⁸ The species subject to the HD's protection regime are listed in Annex II (plant and animal species of Community interest), and Annex IV (species of Community interest in need of strict protection) or V (species of Community interest whose taking in the wild and exploitation may be subject to management measures). These include certain marine species, such as marine mammals. In the Baltic Sea area, for instance, these species include the grey seal, Baltic Sea seal and porpoise listed in Annex II of the HD. The HD provides that a Natura 2000-network of protected areas is to be established hosting sites of Annex I habitats and Annex II species to protect and restore them at a favourable conservation status in their natural range. Accordingly, the HD includes an obligation for Member States to establish Natura 2000 protection areas for some marine habitats and some key marine species. Similarly to the bird

⁸ <https://www.ymparisto.fi/sites/default/files/documents/Natura%202000%20-%20luontotyypit%20nimet%20FI%2C%20SVE%2C%20ENG%20ja%20koodit%20-%20p%C3%A4ivitetty%202020.pdf>

protection areas under the BD, each protection area is to become a subject to specific conservation objectives (Art 3(1) of the HD).

Although some marine habitats and species are included in the protection regime of the HD, the directive's conservation regimes do not entail a comprehensive take on marine biodiversity. Annex I contains mostly terrestrial and freshwater habitats, and as was seen in the previous paragraph, the marine habitats included are predominantly coastal and shoreline habitats. Instead, there are no seabed habitats as such included in Annex I. Regarding species, the listings in Annex IV and V that provide the stricter protection regimes also put emphasis on terrestrial species and include only few marine species. The issue has been noted by the European Court of Auditors, which has stated that the HD's Annexes do not include enough marine habitats and species to comprehensively protect the marine environment (European Court of Auditors, 2020 & European Environmental Agency, 2015). One reason for this is that at the time of adoption of the Nature Directives, knowledge was much scarcer on marine nature compared to terrestrial habitats and species (European Court of Auditors, 2020).

The *MSFD* provides an important policy to supplement the Nature Directives' in addressing marine biodiversity. The Directive is not a traditional nature conservation instrument, as it does not specifically identify and focus only on habitats and species of which viability is threatened but introduces holistic objectives and management regime for the marine environment, to which marine biological diversity is a part of. It is precisely for this reason that the Directive has the potential to, firstly, broaden the scope of marine natural values of which management is important for preserving marine biodiversity and, secondly, provide a management regime capable of addressing various threats to marine nature.

In the *MSFD*, the main substantive obligation for the Member States is provided in Article 1(1) that puts forward a general obligation that Member States "take the necessary measures to achieve or maintain good environmental status in the marine environment by the year 2020 at the latest". The general objective of good marine environmental status (MGES) is further specified and defined by Member States in the implementation of the Directive based on 11 qualitative descriptors (D), provided in Annex I of the *MSFD*. These descriptors address main characteristics, impacts and pressures in marine ecosystems. Marine biodiversity is specifically addressed under descriptors D1 *biological diversity* and D6 *sea-floor integrity*. Marine biodiversity aspects are also substantiated under especially D3 *commercially-exploited fish and shellfish* and D4 *marine food-webs*, which relate to commercial fishing and exploitation activities (addressed further in chapter 6). Yet, other descriptors are relevant for the wellbeing of marine biodiversity, as they together portray different elements of healthy and functioning marine ecosystems, which are prerequisites for maintaining biological diversity.⁹

Annex I to the *MSFD* provides general definitions of MGES for each qualitative descriptor, which need to be further specified and quantified by the Member States in implementation. For D1, good

⁹ For instance, achieving MGES for D5 eutrophication, D8 chemical contaminants, D9 marine litter and D11 underwater energy and noise is vital for preserving marine habitats and species.

status is defined as follows: “Biological diversity is maintained. The quality and occurrence of habitats and the distribution and abundance of species are in line with prevailing physiographic, geographic and climatic conditions”. For D6 MGES is defined as: “Sea-floor integrity is at a level that ensures that the structure and functions of the ecosystems are safeguarded and benthic ecosystems, in particular, are not adversely affected”. The Commission has also laid down assessment criteria and methodologies for defining MGES for each element to ensure coherence of definitions between Member States in its decision 2017/848.¹⁰ In addition, for operationalising the general objectives of good status into more specific and quantifiable metrics, the MSFD provides the instrument of environmental targets (Art 10). The function of the targets is to guide the development of the state of the marine environment or the predominant pressures towards levels appropriate for the purposes of achieving MGES, for example by prescribing targets for reduction of certain types of pressures or loads (MSFD Art 1(7)).

Table 1 The MSFD's qualitative elements related to marine biodiversity, their assessment criteria and relationship with the Nature Directives

Elements related to marine biodiversity	Assessment criteria for defining good status	Relationship with the Nature Directives
D1 Biological diversity		
Species of birds, mammals, reptiles and non-commercially-exploited species of fish and cephalopods, which are at risk from incidental by-catch in the region or subregion.	The mortality rate per species from incidental by-catch in relation to the level that threatens their viability.	May be partly overlapping with the HD. The BD covers all bird species naturally occurring in Europe in wild state, and thus, the bird species assessed here are also included in the BD. This factor relates specifically to the impacts of incidental by-catches in relation to commercial fishing policies, see chapter 6.
Species groups (as established in table 1 in Annex I, Part II Decision 2017/848) for birds, mammals, reptiles, fish and cephalopods.	The population abundance of the species is not adversely affected due to anthropogenic pressures, such that its long-term viability is ensured.	Partly overlapping with the HD, may include also other species. The BD covers all bird species naturally occurring in Europe in wild state, and thus, the bird

¹⁰ Commission Decision (EU) 2017/848 laying down criteria and methodological standards on good environmental status of marine waters and specifications and standardised methods for monitoring and assessment and repealing Decision 2010/477/EU.

<p>Member States shall establish a set of species representative of each species group.</p>	<p>The species distributional range and, where relevant, pattern is in line with prevailing physiographic, geographic and climatic conditions.</p> <p>For species listed in Annexes II, IV and V to the HD, the habitat for the species has the necessary extent and condition to support the different stages in the life history of the species.</p>	<p>species selected as indicators under the MSFD are also included in the BD.</p> <p>The species selected by the MS as indicators need to include the mammals and reptiles listed in Annex II to the HD present in the geographical region.</p> <p>The selected species may include species included in Annexes IV and V to the HD.</p> <p>For the species that are included in the BD and HD, the MSFD's GES criteria for population abundance, distribution need to be consistent with the Favourable Reference Range values established by the relevant Member States under the HD and the assessment needs to consider their habitats.</p>
<p>Pelagic (open-sea) broad habitat types</p>	<p>The condition of the habitat type, including its biotic and abiotic structure and its function is not adversely affected by anthropogenic pressures</p>	<p>The HD does not contain pelagic habitats, so the element is supplementary to the HD.</p>
<p>D6 Sea-floor integrity</p>		
<p>Benthic broad habitat types (as listed in Table 2 in Annex I, part II Decision 2017/848), if present in the region or sub-region.</p>	<p>Spatial extent of each habitat type which is adversely affected or lost by physical disturbance.</p> <p>The extent of adverse effects from anthropogenic pressures on the condition of the habitat type, including alteration to its</p>	<p>The broad habitat types are based on EUNIS-classification system, which means that they are wider than the habitats included in the HD. The HD habitats concentrate on the coast and shoreline, while these habitats exist in the sea floor bottom. Assessment of good</p>

	biotic and abiotic structure and its functions.	status is conducted based on the MSFD's criteria.
Other habitat types, including those that are listed in the HD.		For the habitat types listed in the HD, the assessments and definition of good status under MSFD use the favourable conservation status information produced under the HD.

In general, the MSFD thus covers and pays specific attention to the habitats and species subjected to protection requirements in the Nature Directives but widens the scope of habitats and species to supplement the HD's narrow take on marine biodiversity in particular.

In addition, the proposed *NRL* includes obligations related to protecting and restoring marine habitat types and habitats of marine species. The *NRL* puts forward a general obligation for Member States to put in place effective and area-based restoration measures with the aim to jointly cover, as a Union target, at least 20 % of land areas and at least 20 % of sea areas by 2030, and all ecosystems in need of restoration by 2050 (Art 1(2)). In addition to this EU-wide objective, Articles 4-13 include more specific restoration targets and obligations for the Member States individually, wherein Article 4 addresses terrestrial, coastal and freshwater habitats and Article 5 marine ecosystems.

With regard to the scope of the *NRL*, the regulation is highly complementary to the Nature Directives and the MSFD in marine biodiversity protection. Article 4 imposes restoration obligations in relation to habitat types listed in Annex I of the regulation, which includes the habitat types listed in Annex I of the HD – thus, the restoration obligations cover the coastal and shoreline habitats of the HD. In turn, Article 5 provides restoration obligations for marine ecosystems listed in Annex II of the regulation; this listing of ecosystems is based on a so-called EUNIS-classification, which is wider and more comprehensive than the HD's marine habitats and which largely corresponds the habitats' aspects in the MSFD's assessments and objectives. Yet, Annex II of the *NRL* is even more comprehensive than the MSFD, as the MSFD addresses mainly bottom-floor habitats and includes significant flexibility for the Member States regarding what habitats are included in the assessments and MGES definition. Furthermore, the *NRL* puts forward an obligation for Member States to ensure an increasing trend towards the sufficient quality and quantity of the marine habitats of the marine species in the BD, the HD and the fish, shark and ray species listed in Annex III of the regulation, which aims to substantiate the relatively narrow marine species listing particularly in the HD.

The substance of the *NRL*'s objectives is, firstly, improving areas of habitats into good condition. This objective applies to the areas of habitats present in the Member States. The *NRL* requires Member States to put in place the restoration measures needed to improve to good condition areas of the habitats listed in the HD so that these measures cover 30 % total area of all habitat types listed in Annex I that is not in good condition by 2030 (Art 4(1)(a)). Furthermore, by 2040 the restoration

measures should cover 60 % of the area of each group of habitats not in good conditions and 90 % by 2050 (Art 4(1)(b)). Yet, a derogation is provided for ‘very common and widespread groups of habitat types’ (Art 4(2)). For the marine habitats, Member States should put in place the measures needed to improve to good condition habitats belonging to groups 1-6 of the habitats listed in Annex II so that these measures cover 30 % of the *total* area of these habitat groups that is not in good conditions by 2030 (Art 5(1)(a)). Furthermore, by 2040, restoration measures should cover 60 % of habitats, and, by 2050, on at least 90 % of the area of *each* of the groups 1 to 6 of the habitat types listed in Annex II that is not in good condition (Art 5(1)(b)). For marine habitats belonging to group 7 – that is, soft sediments – these objectives entail putting in place restoration measures for two thirds of the area that has been identified as a target for the coverage of restoration measures by 2050 by Member States (5(1)(c)-(d)).

In other words, the restoration targets for 2030 concern total area of groups of habitats, not each habitat, meaning that Member States have flexibility to allocation of restoration efforts within the group. Furthermore, the ambition level for coverage of restoration for soft sediments is almost entirely up to Member States’ discretion. Accordingly, the restoration targets do not fully match the obligations under the HD whose protection objectives and obligations concern each habitat individually. Also for the MSFD, Member States are to consider the status of each of the marine habitat included in the assessments and set threshold values for level of adverse impacts in determining MGES with respect to these habitats.¹¹ Yet, the MSFD has awarded Member States considerable leeway in determining MGES, and thus, national definitions may vary. As the NRL also provides some exemptions and allows some aspects of restoration targets to be determined in national restoration plans, national implementation may affect considerably the degree of coherence of the MSFD’s and NRL’s targets. One effort in the NRL to prevent the leeway provided for restoration obligations from producing incoherence with the MSFD is a condition that the restoration objectives for soft sediments are to be set in a way that it does not prevent MGES from being achieved (Art 5(1)). However, this appears as a very much bare minimum requirement, as the rationale of the NRL is supposed to be supporting the efforts under the Nature Directives and the MSFD.

With regards to the substance of this restoration objective, good condition, defined in Article 3(4), entails that the habitat’s “structure, functions and typical species or typical species composition reflect the high level of ecological integrity, stability and resilience necessary to ensure its long-term maintenance”. Furthermore, good conditions is to be defined as such that it contributes to reaching the Nature Directives’ Favourable Conservation Status (FCS) objectives and the MSFD’s MGES objectives. Accordingly, the function of the NRL is to provide explicit, directly legally binding obligations on Member States on putting in place and implementing restoration measures to improve the quality of these ecosystems and habitats, which supports and enforces the obligations on reaching the FCS and MGES in the Nature Directives and the MSFD. Yet, however, good condition does not directly correspond to the HD’s FCS objective nor the management objectives for individual Natura 2000 sites nor the definitions of MGES under the MSFD; accordingly, the NRL creates yet another

¹¹ COM 2017/848 Annex, Part 1.

objective concerning marine nature that requires scientific definition and that may risk distortion between objectives and between Member States.

With regard to restoration objectives, the NRL aims to explicitly foster synergies with the HD in particular. In relation to the HD habitats, the NRL stipulates that in putting in place the restoration measures priority is to be given to Natura 2000-areas, which generally supports the HD's regime where the conservation regime is mainly provided for the occurrence of habitats that are included in the network. The NRL also puts forward a new obligation to prevent deterioration of the HD habitats, which includes both habitats within Natura 2000-areas – to which also the HD Article 6(3) deterioration ban is applied – as well as the occurrences of the habitats outside Natura 2000 -areas, which are currently not explicitly protected against deterioration in EU law (Art 4(11) and (12)). Furthermore, specific restoration obligations are provided for the habitats of species included in the Nature Directives conservation regimes and the NRL's Annex III (Art 4(7) and 5(5)).

In addition to the objectives related to restoration of habitats towards good condition, the NRL also includes a second type of restoration objective, that is, re-establishment of habitats. These objectives include re-establishment of habitats towards ensuring that they meet favourable reference area (Art 3(8)). This objective entails considering the area of the habitat that has been lost and reintroducing the habitat in those areas until the objective of favourable reference area is met. For the HD habitats, Member States are to put in place restoration measures to re-establish the habitats in areas where they do not occur so that by 2030, the measures represent at least 30 % of the additional surface needed to reach the *total* favourable reference area for each *group of habitat types*. By 2040, measures should represent at least 60 % of that surface and by 2050, 100 % (Art 4(4)). Yet, a derogation enabling lowering the target area by 2050 is provided (Art 4(5)). Here again, it should be noted that the re-establishment objective does not concern each habitat type individually but constitutes a joint objective for the groups of habitats; as such, the objective is not fully in line with the HD and entails leeway for the Member States in the allocation of restoration efforts within the groups.

The re-establishment objectives are similar for marine habitats. Member States are to put in place restoration measures to re-establish group 1-6 habitats types in areas where they do not occur so that by 2030, the measures represent at least 30 % of the additional surface needed to reach the favourable reference area for each *group of habitat types*. By 2040, measures should represent at least 60 % of that surface and by 2050, 100 % (Art 5(2)). Yet, a derogation enabling lowering the target area by 2050 is provided (Art 5(3)). Here, again, re-establishment objective does not concern each habitat type individually but constitutes a joint objective for the groups of habitats; as such, the objective is not fully in line with the MSFD's assessment and MGES and entails leeway for the Member States in the allocation of restoration efforts within the groups. Furthermore, remarkably, the NRL does not provide any re-establishment objectives for soft sediments.

With regards to its subject, Art 3(8) NRL defines favourable reference area as 'the total area of a habitat type in a given biogeographical or marine region at national level that is considered the minimum necessary to ensure the long-term viability of the habitat type and its typical species or typical species composition, and all the significant ecological variations of that habitat type in its natural range, and which is composed of the current area of the habitat type and, if that area is not

sufficient for the long-term viability of the habitat type and its typical species or typical species composition, the additional area necessary for the reestablishment of the habitat type'. Furthermore, similarly to the good condition objective, the NRL specifies that favourable reference area is to be defined as such that reaching it contributes to achieving the HD's FCS and the MSFD's MGES objectives.

In general, the re-establishment objectives create a new, crucially needed type of objectives and obligations under EU law as biodiversity loss cannot be reversed by just protecting and restoring the areas of habitat that have not yet been lost. The objective is particularly important supplement to the MSFD, where the assessments consider how much area has been adversely affected, disturbed and lost, and MGES entails setting thresholds for maximum allowable levels of such effects.¹² However, the substance of the favourable reference area objective does not directly correspond to the HD's FCS objective nor the management objectives for individual Natura 2000 sites nor the definitions of MGES under the MSFD; accordingly, the NRL creates yet another objective concerning marine nature that requires scientific definition and that may risk distortion between objectives and between Member States. Furthermore, the various relaxations within restoration objectives – derogations, exclusion of soft sediments and focus on the groups of habitats – entail a significant risk in terms of coherence and hampering the NRL's contribution in supporting the Nature Directives and the MSFD.

Furthermore, the WFD is also a relevant policy for marine biodiversity. The WFD applies to the coastal waters of marine areas.¹³ Many habitats important for marine biodiversity – especially the coastal and shoreline habitats that the Annex I of the HD includes – are in the area of application of the WFD. The MSFD applies to coastal waters “in so far as particular aspects of the environmental status of the marine environment are not already addressed” in the WFD (Art 3(1) paragraph b of the MSFD). In other words, both the WFD and the MSFD apply to coastal waters, but WFD's definitions, objectives and assessment criteria take primacy for those factors that are addressed in both directives.

The general objectives of the WFD are the achievement of the good status and the prevention of deterioration (Art 4(1)). For surface waters, the good status objective covers good ecological status and good chemical status (Art 4(1), paragraph a). Ecological status aims to describe the structure and functioning of the surface water ecosystem as classified in accordance with Annex V of the directive. The ecological status of surface water bodies is assessed for the surface water category – lakes, rivers, transitional waters and coastal waters – on the basis of typical biological, hydrological-morphological and physico-chemical quality factors. The surface waters of each category are further separated into types based on natural geographical characteristics. The biological factors of coastal waters include phytoplankton, other aquatic vegetation and benthic fauna. Hydrological-morphological factors include the variation in depth, the structure and quality of the bottom on the coast, and the effect of waves. Physico-chemical factors include visibility depth, thermal conditions, oxygen conditions, salinity, nutrient conditions and special concentrations of pollutants. Water bodies are classified based on these factors into high, good, moderate, poor or bad ecological status based on the level of

¹² COM 2017/848, Annex Part 1.

¹³ The Directive's scope of application includes all waters that extend on the high seas side up to one nautical mile from the baseline and waters located on the side of the coast from the baseline. Art 2(7) of the WFD.

deviation from the reference conditions, high status, that display the state of these factors when they are practically unimpacted by human interference.

It should be noted that the WFD's objectives for coastal waters do not in themselves address marine nature conservation holistically. They do not consider the status of marine fish, seabirds and marine mammals, or the habitat types that occur in the coastal water bodies. Instead, the WFD's good ecological status objective describes the general state of the water body, where the structure and functioning of the surface water ecosystem is good. Some of the quality elements used in this assessment are linked to biodiversity factors. Good ecological status entails, for example, good conditions of phytoplankton which is an indicator used to assess the status of pelagic habitats under D1 in the MSFD. The WFD's good status objective also includes a good structure and quality of the bottom in coastal waters, as well as the composition and abundance ratios of aquatic vegetation and benthic fauna, which relate to the good status of bottom habitats according to the MSFD. Furthermore, good status generally supports the species and habitat types present in the water body, especially as it can address pressures that are not dealt with MPA regimes, such as chemical pollution and eutrophication.

Moreover, Article 6(1) of the WFD obliges Member States to maintain a register of all surface waters designated as specially protected in EU nature protection legislation. These areas include especially the Natura 2000 areas. According to Art 4(1) paragraph (c) of the WFD, Member States must achieve the compliance with any conservation objectives for these protected areas by 2015, unless the legislation underlying the protection stipulates otherwise. According to the Commission, this means that Member States must recognize the elements of surface waters that are necessary for achieving and maintaining a favourable conservation status of the relevant habitat and species and pay particular attention to those in water management (European Commission, 2011a). While marine biodiversity is not explicitly included in the WFD's objectives, the Directive's requirements should be interpreted and implemented in view of supporting the conservation aspects deriving from other directives, mainly the MSFD and the Nature Directives. However, potential conflicts may arise between the conservation of the species and the WFD's objectives, particularly if the species is dependent on changed conditions in the water body that do not correspond to good status; such situations may arise for instance in relation to bird habitats (European Commission, 2011a).

Table 2 Synthesis on the objective of the Nature Directives, the MSFD, the WFD and the NRL and their relationship with each other.

Marine nature values	Objective	Relationship with the Nature Directives	Relationship with the MSFD	Relationship with the WFD	Relationship with the NRL
The Nature Directives					
Marine (coastal, shoreline and shallow water) habitats in Annex II HD	Favourable conservation status (FCS)	-	Included in the assessment and GES for D6 sea-floor integrity, GES coherent with FCS	Good ecological and chemical status generally support reaching FCS	Listed in Annex I; subject to restoration objectives and no-deterioration obligation within and outside Natura 2000 -area → the NRL is aligned with the FCS objectives, strengthens the legal requirements and broadens the scope of protection and quality/quantity improvement outside Natura 2000 -areas
Certain species of marine mammals, reptiles and fish	Favourable conservation status (FCS) (incl. habitat protection)	-	Some species included as indicators in the assessment and GES for D1 biodiversity, GES coherent with FCS	Good ecological and chemical status generally support reaching FCS	Restoration of the habitats of these species included in the NRL's regime, supports reaching the FCS
All naturally occurring	Favourable conservation status (FCS)	-	Some species included as indicators in the assessment and GES for D1 biodiversity,	Good ecological and chemical status may support reaching FCS	Restoration of the habitats of these species included in the NRL's regime, supports reaching the FCS

sea birds (BD)	(inc. habitat protection)		GES coherent with FCS	The WFD's objectives may sometimes contra- dict with Nature Direc- tives' conservation.	
The MSFD					
D1 species	MGES	Includes the species in Annex II of the HD for which Natura 2000 -areas are to be designated; may include species in Annex IV or V or the HD and bird species in the BD.	-	Good ecological and good chemical status objectives may support reaching MGES.	The habitats of species included in the HD and BD are subject to specific restoration obligations; NRL Annex III introduces new species of which habitats are to be restored – those species may be included in MGES based on MS discretion
D1 pelagic habitats	MGES	MGES supports FCS of the marine shallow water habitats in the HD	-	MGES coherent with good ecological status of coastal water bodies	Not included in the NRL specifically
D6 broad habitat types (sea-floor)	MGES	Includes the marine shallow water habitats in the HD, for their part MGES coherent with the FCS	-	Good ecological status of coastal water bodies includes certain aspects of sea-floor bottom, partly coherent	Included in Annex II of the NRL; NRL pro- vides explicit restoration obligations related to the quality and re-establishing their quantity, which supports and enforces the obligations of reaching MGES

		Broader range of habitats in the sea-floor bottom, substantiates the HD that does not include deep sea floor habitats.			
The WFD					
Coastal water bodies	Good ecological and chemical status	In water bodies that host protected habitats and species, specific attention needs to be given to the aspects that support the viability of these nature values and water management should aim at facilitating the achievement of their conservation objectives.	MGES objectives partly overlap, in which case the WFD takes priority. The MGES objectives may be applied supplementary, insofar as the aspects are not included in the WFD's objectives (e.g. more specific assessment of sea-floor bottom, biodiversity aspects).	-	No explicit linkage, but measures intended to restore the habitats occurring in the WFD's water bodies may be synergetic in terms of the WFD's objectives

3.2.2 Timeframe for the achievement of the objectives

Another key component of the objectives in policy instruments is the timeframes and deadlines for their achievement. The Nature Directives do not set a deadline for achieving the FCS, but the Commission has taken the view that Member States are expected to make continued progress (European Commission, 2011a). Since the marine habitats and some of the marine species of the HD and some seabird species of the BD are included in the MSFD objectives, the MSFD's timetable for achieving the MGES indicates also a timeframe for achieving FCS in respect of these habitats and species.

The MSFD prescribes that the MGES was to be achieved in all marine regions and subregions by 2020. Nevertheless, Article 14 of the Directive allows for certain exemptions from this objective. Exemptions are possible if the objective cannot be fully achieved for the reasons listed in paragraphs (a) to (d) of the Article, or if it cannot be achieved within the timeframe set because natural conditions do not allow for timely improvement of the status of marine waters (Article 14(1)(e)). MGES was not reached for all descriptors in any of the marine regions in the EU, and it has been detected from the implementation reports that Member States have not always justified such failures with derogations (Puharinen 2023). Currently, the legal situation is unclear on whether there is any sort of legal deadline attached to the obligations on achieving MGES anymore. The MSFD is currently under review by the Commission, where one crucial question is whether the directive's deadline for the achievement of MGES will be renewed.

The WFD's targets for good ecological and good chemical status of surface waters were originally set to be achieved by 2015. Article 4(4) of the WFD, however, allows for an extension of the deadline for achieving good status from 2015 because of the technical or economic feasibility of the measures required to achieve good status or because of the natural conditions of the body of water. This extension is available until 2027 for reasons of technical or economic feasibility, which means that the necessary water management measures for achieving good status needed to be in place at the latest in the river basin management plans adopted in 2021.

The NRL provides several deadlines to structure restoration measures that aim to improve the quality and quantity of the habitats that are in its scope, which include the habitats covered by the HD and its FCS objective and the MSFD and its MGES objective. Since the HD does not provide a deadline for the achievement of its objectives, the NRL's deadlines reinforce this aspect of the FCS objectives. For the MSFD, the NRL's deadlines do not correspond to the deadline of the MSFD – obviously, as the 2020 MGES deadline has passed. Yet, in the absence of a currently applicable deadline and the related legal confusion on the achievement of the MGES, the NRL reinforces the obligations and structures continuous efforts towards reaching the MGES in relation to the marine habitats.

The NRL's restoration objectives do not contain an explicit linkage to the WFD's objectives. Yet, the instruments do have crucial interrelationship. Firstly, many of the habitats in the scope of the NRL – particularly the coastal habitats of the HD and NRL's Annex I and Article 4 – are situated in the WFD's coastal water bodies, and the measures set up to restore them are likely to also contribute to

the WFD's objectives. Since the NRL's deadlines for these measures begin in 2030, the timeframe exceeds the WFD's deadline of 2027 of reaching GES. Secondly, the WFD's measures planned in the river basin districts provide a basis for the restoration measures under the NRL to deal with land-based pollution and stressors on the marine biodiversity (see NRL Art 14(14)(c)). Here, the WFD prescribes that these measures were to be included and implemented in the river basin management plans for 2021-2027. Thus, the WFD's measures may provide a significant contribution to the NRL's obligations of restoration measures being in place for 30 % of habitats by 2030.

3.2.3 Legal impacts of the objectives

To assess the coherence of the objectives in the policies within the biodiversity cluster, it is important to also analyse, whether the legal impacts of the objectives are coherent in regulating the conduct of the Member States and other actors towards achieving them. There are two key questions regarding the legal implications of environmental objectives set in EU legislation: 1) the legal obligations of Member States in relation to achieving the objectives, and 2) the legal implications (binding impacts) of the objectives in environmental decision-making situations, for example when considering the authorisation of projects. It should be remembered that many marine biodiversity aspects – such as habitats – are included in the regimes of several policies and thus, it is necessary to assess whether the Member States obligations in improving their state are similar in the policies. Furthermore, the policies in the end all address marine ecosystems, although framing it in slightly different ways, and it is worth examining whether the legal obligations on its protection make up a coherent whole. This subsection will analyse the nature of Member States' obligations deriving from the objectives of the policies. The legal implications and rules pertaining to individual projects that take place at the marine areas as well as the possible derogations are addressed in the section 3.3 along with other instruments in the policies.

With regard to the legal obligations for the Member States, a distinction between obligations of best effort and obligations of result is well established. The former requires Member States to make best efforts in aspiring to achieve the objectives (obligation of means), while the latter imposes an obligation to actually achieve a certain result (van Kempen, 2012). For obligations of best efforts, Member States are required to put forward diligent action and measures towards the objectives, but the mere fact that the objective was not reached on time does not mean that there has been an infringement of obligations under the EU law. For obligations of result, in turn, the proper fulfilment of the obligations under EU law is solely judged based on the outcome of implementation; if the prescribed result was not met in time, Member States can be found to have breached their obligations, unless the failure is appropriately justified with exemptions that may be provided in the EU policy. While both types of obligations do entail binding legal requirements for the Member States to put in place proper efforts towards meeting the goals, in general obligations of result are slightly stricter in terms of the level of protection they impose (Puharinen, 2023).

The Nature Directives' FCS objective does not entail direct or general legal obligations in itself. In other words, there is no obligation of result nor an obligation of best effort on Member States to achieve the FCS. Instead, the FCS objective derives its legal content from the substantive conservation provisions of the directives (Pappila and Puharinen, 2022). The FCS objective is linked, for example, to the assessment of adequacy of the Natura 2000 network (Article 3 of the HD) and to

the conditions for exemptions from the species protection requirements (Article 16 of the HD). The main substantive protection regulation implementing the objective is found in Article 6 of the HD, which obliges Member States to 1) take active conservation measures in Natura sites (Art. 6(1); Art. 4(1)-(2) of the BD); 2) prevent the deterioration and significant disturbance of habitats and species for which protection the Nature 2000-site has been designated (Art. 6(2)); and 3) to assess and specifically approve plans and projects that may have a significant effect on these conservation values (Art. 6(3)-(4)) (Belinskij and Mehling, 2008). Accordingly, it is these Natura 2000-site specific obligations that form either obligations of result or obligations of best effort for Member States in protecting the quality of the occurrences of habitats for which the site has been established. The third dimension, the assessment of individual projects, will be analysed later together with the legal implications on projects deriving from the objectives in the other policies.

The first dimension of Art 6 of the HD, Article 6(1) provides an obligation for the Member States to “establish the necessary conservation measures involving, if need be, appropriate management plans”. While it is clear that there is an obligation to put in place some measures, the obligation is not linked to the FCS or any other qualitative objective on the site, nor is there a deadline against which the achievement of these obligations could be assessed. There is, at most, an obligation of best effort to strive to improve the condition and quality of the sites through taking measures. Nevertheless, even in this respect, the provision leaves a wide margin of discretion to the Member States as to the content of the measures. The Nature Directives do not contain legally forceful obligations on the Member States to improve the state of the (few) marine habitats included under their regime. Yet, the NRL’s restoration obligations significantly reinforce this obligation both in terms of specificity and legal force (see below).

The second dimension of Article 6 of the HD, the requirement to prevent deterioration of the sites, has in turn been regarded as an obligation of result. The CJEU has interpreted the provision as meaning that the Member State is obliged to take all necessary measures to prevent deterioration and found that the mere fact that the deterioration has occurred already establishes a breach of obligations, see case C-96/98 (para 41-46). However, the degree to which this obligation has actually been complied with and enforced against the Member States with regard to marine habitats is unclear.

Regarding the *MSFD*, the obligations of the Member States on achieving MGES in the marine environment by 2020 can be interpreted to constitute obligations of best effort (Puharinen, 2023). This means that Member States have a legal obligation to take all reasonable measures to achieve MGES, albeit the failure to meet the objective does not itself mean that obligations under the *MSFD* would have been breached. Yet, the *MSFD*’s implementation by the Member States or the oversight and enforcement action by the Commission has largely overlooked substantive legal aspects of the MGES and the substantive obligations related to the Directive and its objectives have remained vague (*ibid.*). This is a major issue in terms of marine biodiversity: as was noted above, the *MSFD* is a crucial instrument for supplementing the insufficient account on marine species and habitats of the HD, but as can be seen here, the legal impacts of the *MSFD*’s objectives appear to be even less forceful than those of the Nature Directives, which means that several elements of marine biodiversity are not included under strict legal protection. Furthermore, the *MSFD* does not contain explicit regulation on preventing deterioration; the objective of preventing deterioration is provided as a

general aim for marine management in Art 1(2) but it is not to be considered as a self-standing legal requirement. Preventing deterioration is not mentioned anywhere else in the Directive and no conditions are defined for assessing when the marine environment has deteriorated (ibid.).

The environmental targets are essential for achieving and maintaining MGES, and their achievement could demonstrate that the Member State has complied with the obligation of best effort. Thus, Member States would be required to pursue setting ambitious environmental targets, implementing them and applying the exemptions of the MSFD appropriately to justify each situation where MGES or environmental objectives are not being achieved (ibid.). While such obligations can be read from the directive, the implementation and enforcement have not taken due account on substantive legal aspects.

The *WFD's* ecological status objectives have been seen as binding on Member States in relation to the result to be achieved (van Kempen, 2012). Member States have a legally binding obligation to take all measures necessary to achieve good status in all bodies of water by 2027 at latest. Any failures in this regard must be justified by the exemptions provided in the WFD. For marine biodiversity protection, this would mean that Member States are legally obliged to ensure good ecological and chemical status of all coastal water bodies by 2027, which would also support progress towards improving the status of the HD habitats and achieving the MSFD's objectives. However, the WFD contains relatively wide possibilities for exempting from the good status objectives (examined below), which – together with the fact that no notable progress has been made in improving water quality in the implementation of the Directive – sheds doubts on whether the Directive will force Member States to *de facto* deliver such progress.

As noted above, the NRL has the potential to become a significant regulation to reinforce the HD's and the MSFD's habitat protection regime with legally binding obligations on Member States to take restoration measures towards achieving the FCS and the MGES. The NRL's obligations are provided focusing on putting in place restoration measures that cover a certain percentage of habitats or are intended to re-establish certain percentages of lost area for the habitat (30 % by 2030, 60 % by 2040 and 90 % by 2050). As such, the NRL's obligations are specific, unequivocal, and focused on the outcome (measures are in place covering the said percentage), which strongly suggests them being obligations of result. The obligations are linked to the measures being in place, not to a state in which the habitats would be required to be by the deadlines. Such formulation may be beneficial for monitoring the Member States performance and when necessary, enforcing the regulation, as there are less uncertainties on how to determine whether Member States performance has been adequate. Measures are either in place or not, while the outcome of the measures in terms of status of the environment is more uncertain. The NRL's obligations stipulate a certain amount of effort that has to be made towards the ecosystem goals, but they do not directly require those goals to be met. This is in contrast to the Nature Directives, the MSFD and the WFD and may create confusion on the question of which obligation the Member States performance is to be judged. Measures that are enough to meet the NRL's obligations in time may not be enough to deliver the objectives of WFD or MSFD.

Moreover, the NRL includes obligations for the Member States to aim to ensure that in areas where good condition has been reached, the area does not significantly deteriorate (Art 4(11), 5(9)). Thus,

there is a no-deterioration requirement that addresses the HD's habitats as well as other marine habitats subject to the MSFD. On the one hand, the NRL's non-deterioration rule supplements and reinforces the no-deterioration requirements in the HD and the MSFD, as the HD's one only applies to the occurrences of habitats within Natura 2000-sites (the NRL's one covers habitats in good condition within and outside Natura 2000-areas) and as the MSFD no-deterioration objective is not legally defined as an obligation for Member States. On the other hand, the NRL's non-deterioration requirement is narrower than those of the other directives; in the HD, (the MSFD,) and the WFD the non-deterioration rules do not only apply to habitats or water bodies in good state. Also, these rules prohibit all deterioration, not just 'significant' deterioration like the NRL. In terms of its legal status, the obligation to prevent deterioration is structured as an obligation to 'aim to ensure', which may hint towards being an obligation of best effort rather than one of result.

To sum up the obligations of result and of best effort:

Obligations of result:

- Prevent deterioration of surface water bodies; exemptions provided for new projects (WFD Art 4(7)) or exceptional natural conditions (WFD Art 4(6))
- Achieve good status of surface water bodies by 2015; deadline extension possible, after 2027 only for natural conditions (WFD 4(4)), lowering the objectives possible (WFD Art 4(5))
- Achieve environmental targets under the MSFD; exemptions provided (MSFD Art 14(1))
- Prevent deterioration of and significant disturbance to the natural values of Natura 2000 sites; exemptions provided for plans and projects (HD Art 6(4))

Obligations of best efforts:

- prevent deterioration of the marine environment; no exemptions provided
- achieve MGES in the marine environment by 2020; exemptions provided (MSFD Art 14(1))
- take active conservation measures in Natura 2000 sites; no exemptions provided
- prevent pollution and deterioration of wild bird habitats outside Natura 2000 sites; no exemptions provided
- prevent significant deterioration of habitats restored to good condition; exemption provided (NRL Art 4(11), (12) and (13), 5(11), (12) and (13)).

3.2.4 Exemptions from the objectives

It should be noted that there are several exemptions provided in the Nature Directives, the MSFD, and the WFD in relation to both obligations of result and obligations of best effort (Pappila and Puharinen, 2022). In this section, the analysis will focus on the exemptions that relate to the Member States obligations in achieving the objectives. In turn, the derogations related to the adoption of new projects or plans are dealt with under the following section addressing the instruments of the policies. This is because it is recognised that the rules pertaining to the authorisation of new projects and the related possibilities for derogation from these rules constitute one of the instruments, through which the policies try to achieve the overall objectives.

The MSFD and the WFD provide the widest range of exemptions from their objectives. There are some key differences in the two directives; the MSFD does not contain any exemptions applicable to deterioration of the status of the marine environment, while the WFD provides such exemptions, although only in limited circumstances. Yet, the MSFD does not have a legally fully fledged obligation to prevent deterioration either. In turn, the MSFD's Art 14(1) contains considerably flexible exemption regime from the obligation to achieve MGES and the environmental targets, the application of which furthermore is somewhat voluntary for the Member States as they may choose to justify failures to reach the objectives with some of the wide-ranging reasons listed in the provision. The WFD contains considerably more limited grounds for deviating from achieving good status, albeit the extension for the deadline for reaching the objectives is rather flexible up until 2027. After this deadline, the ambition level of the objectives can be lowered, if the conditions for it are met. While there are such semantic and other differences in the exemptions under the WFD and the MSFD, it has been assessed that the exemptions can be applied in a rather coherent manner (Puharinen et al. 2021).

However, it should be noted that the Habitats Directive does not provide for derogations from the obligation of Member States to take active conservation measures in Natura 2000-sites. Also, there are no exemptions available from the obligation to prevent deterioration of and significant disturbance to the natural values of Natura 2000 sites apart from the exemption related to new plans and projects. Even if a Member State applies the exemptions under the MSFD from achieving MGES by 2020 for a species or habitat type covered by the Habitats Directive, the Member State is still obliged to take appropriate conservation measures in Natura 2000 sites established to protect these natural values. However, as the Nature Directives only contain a narrow take on marine biodiversity, it is relevant to note that for many aspects of marine nature, impairments, deterioration, and lack of progress in improving their status fall under a considerably flexible exemption regime under the MSFD. Similarly, even if a Member State sets less stringent objectives under the WFD for a water body hosting an important occurrence of a habitat or species, it is still obliged to prevent the deterioration of the natural values and the protected area and to take active conservation measures within the protected area (Pappila and Puharinen 2022).

Moreover, the NRL contains notable flexibilities in the obligations related to restoration measures. Firstly, the obligations on Member States involve putting in place measures for a certain percentage of area of the habitats, which provides a possibility to make prioritisations. In putting in place restoration measures for habitats that are included in the HD, the NRL requires priority to be given to areas that are within Natura 2000-sites. This appears logical also from the perspective that the HD is the instrument that does not allow exemptions from the requirement to put in place conservation measures. In turn, if Member States apply exemptions under the WFD and the MSFD on certain water bodies or parts of the marine area, synergies can be sought in the NRL's implementation of considering such areas a smaller priority in setting the restoration measures. Furthermore, the NRL puts forward a specific exemption for areas used for military purposes from the restoration measures.

3.3 Coherence of instruments

In addition to analysing the alignment across the objectives of the policies, the coherence assessment must also address the set of policy instruments set out in the policies (instrumentation). Policy instruments are analysed with a view of exploring how they are designed to meet the policy's objectives (internal coherence) and assessing their level of their contribution towards the EGD's objectives. Furthermore, the interlinkages and coherence of the instrumentation in the policies within the clusters needs to be examined to assess the coherence of these policies also in this regard.

The Nature Directives, the MSFD, the WFD and the NRL employ a variety of instruments in pursuit of meeting their objectives. All policies include obligations to prevent further deterioration of the habitats, species, water bodies and the marine environment, in which purpose they put forward specific rules related to new projects and plans that are liable of causing deterioration. These rules lay down preconditions for Member States in authorising such projects within environmental permitting regimes, yet the instruments also provide possibilities for derogating from these requirements, if the conditions laid down for such derogations are met. Thus, this section will first explore these permitting rules and derogations from them in the instruments.

It should be recognised that while restricting or imposing requirements on the adoption of new projects and plans are an important instrument in preventing further deterioration of marine biodiversity, it has limited potential in steering the improvement of the current status of biodiversity that has degraded over time due to for instance past and existing projects and diffuse pressures. The policies also put forward instruments that aim to facilitate steering towards addressing various pressures and actively improving the state of the marine environment and biodiversity. Such instruments include the area-based protection regimes in the BD, HD and the MSFD, the strategic planning instruments of the WFD, MSFD and the NRL and the species protection regimes in the HD and the BD. These instruments will also be analysed in this section in the light of their capacity to deliver the EGD's objectives on biodiversity on the one hand and in the light of the coherence of this instrument mix in the biodiversity cluster on the other hand.

3.3.1 Rules on authorising new projects and plans and the related derogations

All policies in this biodiversity cluster – the Nature Directives, the MSFD, the WFD and the NRL – impose specific preconditions on Member States when they are authorising (new) projects that are liable of causing adverse impacts on the objectives of the policies, which at the outset is a positive coherence feature. Yet, these permitting rules have different scopes of application, and they differ in terms of how stringently they protect the marine environment against deterioration and how binding the rules are on Member States authorities. As will be shown below, these aspects invite some coherence challenges within the cluster, and create a complex entity of legal requirements that potentially apply to new plans and projects that are, for instance, adopted based on policies related to other EGD objectives (such as the construction of offshore wind farms, see chapter 7).

Which policies may be relevant for the project's authorisation depend on where in the marine area it is situated. Near coast and the shallow water areas the WFD's objectives apply to each water body. Moreover, the HD's habitats, and thus the Natura 2000 sites, are often situated in the same areas. Yet,

the MSFD is applied in a supplementary capacity to the WFD. In turn, if the project is situated on the outer marine areas, the predominant – and in most cases the only – instrument applying to marine biodiversity aspects there is the MSFD. The NRL covers the coastal and shallow water habitats included in the HD, both within and outside Natura 2000-sites as well as other marine habitats situated in the areas of application of the MSFD. The NRL may cover comprehensive parts of the marine area and become applicable to projects that carry adverse impacts on habitats. Consequently, as there may be different combinations of instruments of which substantive requirements apply to the projects, it is necessary to examine whether the preconditions they provide for authorising projects and the possibilities for applying exemptions from these rules to justify authorising the project are coherent.

Applicable to the Natura 2000-sites, Article 6(3) of the HD requires Member States to carry out an appropriate assessment of any plan or project that may have significant effects, either individually or in combination with other plans or projects, on the site. This assessment considers the project or plan's impacts on the conservation objectives of a particular site. National authorities may agree to the plan or project only after having ascertained that it will not adversely affect the integrity of the site concerned. Accordingly, the appropriate assessment and the precondition for authorising the project only apply in relation to the specific site, and thus, they do not cover all occurrences of the habitats provided in the HD. There is also a possibility for a derogation provided in Article 6(4) of the Habitats Directive, which will be examined below together with the relevant derogations in the WFD, the MSFD and the NRL.

The WFD's objectives have also been confirmed binding in the authorisation of individual projects. In its judgment C-461/13, the CJEU confirmed that a Member State may not, unless a derogation under Article 4(7) of the WFD is applied, grant a permit for a project that would cause deterioration of the status of a water body or jeopardise the achievement of good status (para 51). The no-deterioration rule is strictly interpreted, as it is assessed at the level of individual qualitative elements even when the overall status classification of the water body would remain the same (para 70). Thus, the WFD provides binding preconditions on authorising projects situated in coastal water bodies.

The regulation and systematics of the MSFD's objectives are very similar to those of the WFD that have been found to have binding impacts on the authorisation of projects. The key difference is the spatial scale of the objectives in relation to individual projects. While an individual project may affect the status of a water body significantly, the status of the marine environment is often assessed at the scale of the entire sea basins or a larger sub-region. In such cases, a single project is unlikely to in itself have the potential to degrade the status of the marine environment as a whole or prevent the achievement of MGES. However, it is evident that MGES cannot be achieved without translating the marine management objectives into operational targets that can be applied to individual projects (Puharinen et al. 2021). The environmental targets of the MSFD should be employed to translate the general objectives into more concrete targets against which different projects and activities could be assessed. Yet the legal implications of the targets on for instance permitting of new projects is still unclear in the absence of caselaw from the CJEU.

The NRL contains several provisions requiring Member States to aim to ensure that significant deterioration of habitats that are in good condition is prevented (Art 4(11) and (12), Art 5(9) and (10)).

The regulation also provides possibilities to derogate from this requirement due to new project. This implies that there is a rule that Member States may not authorise a project causing significant deterioration to habitats in good conditions, unless a derogation is applied. For habitats within Natura 2000-areas, the HD Art 6 provides already a non-deterioration rule which is stricter than that of the NRLs (see above).

All instruments include possibilities to derogate from the objectives in relation to new projects, plans or developments (WFD Art 4(7), MSFD Art 14(1) para (d), HD Art 6(4), NRL Art 4(14), (15) and (16), Art 5(11), (12) and (13)), which itself is a positive coherence feature. The derogations differ a bit on what projects are in their scope of application and what preconditions need to be met for the derogation to be granted, which constitutes a coherence challenge.

Article 6(4) of the Habitats Directive allows a Member State to authorise a plan or project that affects the integrity and conservation objectives of a Natura 2000 site. This is subject to the condition that there is no alternative solution to the plan or project, that it must be carried out for imperative reasons of overriding public interest, including social or economic reasons, and that the Member State ensures that all necessary compensatory measures are taken to ensure that the overall integrity of Natura 2000 is maintained.

Article 14(1)(d) of the MSFD provides that Member States may derogate from the achievement of MGES or the environmental targets based on “modifications or alterations to the physical characteristics of marine waters brought about by actions taken for reasons of overriding public interest which outweigh the negative impact on the environment, including any transboundary impact”. Notwithstanding the derogation, the Member State shall continue pursuing the environmental targets, to prevent further deterioration in the status of the marine waters affected and to mitigate the adverse impact at the level of the marine region or subregion concerned or in the marine waters of other Member States.

Article 4(7) of the WFD allows for derogations from the prohibition on the deterioration or achievement of good status as a result of new projects that entail physical modifications to the water body. For projects causing other types of impacts such as pollution, the derogation is limited to situations where the project deteriorates the ecological status from high to good status. Moreover, there are four conditions for the derogation: 1) all practicable measures are taken to mitigate the adverse impacts (harm minimisation); 2) the project is explained and justified in the river basin management plan and the objectives for the water body are reviewed every six years; 3) the reasons for those modifications or alterations are of overriding public interest and/or the benefits to the environment and to society of achieving the good status objectives are outweighed by the benefits of the new modifications or alterations to human health, to the maintenance of human safety or to sustainable development (overriding public interest or balancing of interests); and 4) the benefits of the modifications cannot be achieved by other means that are significantly better for the environment due to technical feasibility or disproportionate costs (no alternative).

In the NRL, possibilities for derogating from the requirement to prevent significant deterioration are provided in relation to habitats that occur outside Natura 2000-areas and for the habitats that are

within Natura 2000-areas. For the coastal habitats that are also subject to the HD's conservation regime, if the habitat occurs within a Natura 2000-area, a derogation from the NRL's non-deterioration rule is available for plans or projects that have been authorised in accordance with Article 6(4) of the HD (Art 4(16)(c)). If the habitat occurs outside the Natura 2000-areas, a derogation from the no-deterioration rule is available for plans or projects that are of overriding public interest, and for which no less damaging alternative solutions are available, to be determined on a case-by-case basis (Art 4(14)(c), 15(c)). The same conditions are provided for derogating from the no-deterioration rule in relation to marine habitats protected under Article 5 of the NRL (Art 5(11), (12) and (13)). Within the Natura 2000-areas, the NRL's derogation relies on the HD derogation, thus ensuring coherence between the instruments in this regard. Outside the Natura 2000-areas the conditions for derogation include a no-alternatives requirement and a requirement of overriding public interest.

Scope of application

The Natura 2000 derogation applies to any project that threatens the integrity of the site, regardless of the types of the impacts. Similarly, the NRL's derogation is applicable to all cases of significant deterioration of habitats that are in good condition. In both cases, the derogations are thus available both for physical modifications and pollution that cause significant deterioration on habitats where good condition has been reached. In turn, the MSFD's derogation is limited to projects that physically alter the marine environment, such as dredging, offshore wind farms or other marine construction, or maritime transport infrastructure projects. Similarly, the WFD's exemption is predominantly applicable to the projects that physically alter the water body. Thus, if the project's impacts entail pollution, the MSFD's exemption is not available, and the WFD's derogation only, if the project causes deterioration from high to good status. As coastal waters all around Europe fall short on high ecological status, in practice projects entailing polluting impacts may not be authorised in the WFD's water bodies, even though a derogation from the Natura 2000-protection or the NRL's non-deterioration rule might apply. In marine areas not covered by the WFD, projects with a pollution impact may be allowed only if project is not assessed as affecting the achievement of MGES of the marine environment or relevant environmental targets, in which case a derogation under the MSFD does not apply.

Overriding public interest

A common condition for exemptions under the HD, the MSFD, the WFD and the NRL is that the project must be of overriding public interest, which is however referred to in the relevant provisions in slightly different terms: Article 14(1)(d) of the MSFD and Articles 4(14)-(15) and 5(11)-(12) of the NRL refer to *overriding public interest*, Article 4(7)(c) of the WFD to *overriding public interest or interest comparison* and Article 6(4) of the Habitats Directive to *imperative reasons of overriding public interest*. Despite these semantic differences, the public interest condition can be interpreted in a similar way in all the Directives.¹⁴ Although Article 6(4) of the Habitats Directive seems to refer to

¹⁴ The implementation strategy for the Marine Strategy Framework Directive states that the interpretation of the Directive's overriding public interest criterion can be based on the interpretation of the Water Framework Directive's overriding public interest criterion (MSFD CIS, 2014).

the imperative reasons of overriding public interest more strictly, the interpretation of the public interest has been quite permissive under the HD too (Belinskij, 2018). Article 4(7) of the WFD and Article 6(4) of the Habitats Directive provide also similar clarifications on the relevant aspects of the public interest assessment, which include, in summary, human health and safety, sustainable development and social and economic reasons. Notably, however, the NRL includes a specification for this requirement, as it stipulates that projects entailing the planning, construction and operation of plants for the production of renewable energy, their connection to the grid and the related grid itself, and storage assets are to be “presumed” to be in overriding public interest (Art 6(1)).

No alternatives

Article 4(7) of the WFD lays down a condition that the benefits of the project cannot, for reasons of technical feasibility or disproportionate cost, be achieved by other means that are significantly better for the environment. The derogations under the HD and the NRL also requires that there is no alternative solution to the project or plan. In the Water Framework Directive explicitly, and in the HD and the NRL implicitly, this condition is linked to the public interest, needs and benefits served by the project which have been identified as overriding the environmental protection interest. If an equivalent public interest benefit could be achieved by other means, the conditions for a derogation are not met. Alternative means may include at least locating the project in an area less sensitive, or away from the immediate vicinity of Natura 2000-sites. The NRL, however, projects related to renewable energy production are exempted from the no-alternatives requirement, provided that they have been subject to strategic environmental impact assessment under Directive 2001/42/EC or environmental impact assessment under Directive 2011/92/EU (Art 6(1)).

The derogation under Article 14(1)(d) of the MSFD does not explicitly recognise any conditions related to alternatives for the project. The conditions for a derogation under the MSFD are in this respect less stringent than those under the WFD (Puharinen et. al., 2021). However, for a project located within the scope of the MSFD, an assessment of the absence of alternatives may be relevant if the project could have a significant effect on the natural values of a Natura 2000-site and would therefore also require a derogation under Article 6(4) of the Habitats Directive.

Harm minimisation

A derogation from the objectives of water management under Article 4(7) of the WPD also requires that all practicable steps are taken to minimise adverse impacts. Similarly, Art 14(1)(d) of the MSFD requires that the adverse effects of activities must be minimised. However, the WFD more directly requires all practicable mitigation measures to be taken at project level (ibid.). Article 6(4) of the Habitats Directive or the derogations under the NRL do not directly require minimisation of the adverse impacts. However, the derogation requires the fulfilment of the no-alternative condition, that the project or plan chosen must be the least harmful, which implicitly includes the idea that relevant mitigation measures have been implemented for the project or plan to meet this requirement.

Article 6(4) of the Habitats Directive also requires that any compensatory measures are taken to ensure the integrity of the Natura 2000 network. In practice, this means compensating for damage to the natural values on which the derogation is based by improving the condition of corresponding

natural values elsewhere. Neither the NRL, the WFD nor the MSFD however require compensation for adverse effects of a project in the context of a derogation.

Table 3 Legal implications on project's or plan's containing adverse impacts on marine biodiversity.

	The HD	The WFD	The MSFD	The NRL
Scope of application of the permitting rules in the policies				
Project is situated in coastal waters within Natura 2000-site or impacting Natura 2000-site	Yes	Usually yes (most HD habitats located in the WFD's coastal waters)	Possibly; marine biodiversity aspects complementary to the WFD → depends on how the MGES and/or the environmental targets have been defined in national implementation	Yes
Project is situated in coastal waters outside the Natura 2000-site nor impacts a site	No	Yes	Possibly; marine biodiversity aspects complementary to the WFD → depends how the MGES and/or the environmental targets have been defined in the national implementation	Yes
Project situated in outer seaward area	No	No	Possibly; depends on how MGES and/or environmental targets have been defined in national implementation	Yes
Legal preconditions for authorising the project				
Are there legally binding rules imposed on Member	Yes; project may not be authorised, if it could	Yes; project may not be authorised, if it causes deterioration of ecological status	Not clear; binding condition that project should not jeopardise the achievement of MGES can be	Yes; requirement to prevent significant deterioration of habitats in good condition

States authorities related to authorising the project?	adversely affect the integrity of the site	or jeopardises the achievement of good status by 2027	inferred but this has not been confirmed by the CJEU	should apply to permitting procedures.
Is there a possibility to grant a derogation from these rules?	Yes, applicable to all sorts of projects and impacts	Yes, but restricted; in practise only applicable to physical modifications, not polluting impacts	Yes, but restricted; only applicable to modifications to the physical characteristics of marine waters	Yes, applicable to all sorts of projects and impacts
Conditions for the derogation				
Project is of overriding public interest	Yes, but there is an additional requirement of being “imperative reasons” of public interest	Yes	Yes	Yes; renewable energy projects presumed to fulfil the condition
There are no environmentally better alternatives	Yes	Yes	Not required explicitly	Yes; renewable energy projects excluded from this requirement if a SEA/EIA has been conducted
The adverse impacts of the pro-	Not explicitly required	Yes	Yes	Not explicitly required

ject are mini- mised				
There lost/impaired natural values are compensated elsewhere	Yes	No; compensation elsewhere not required nor can it be taken into account in assessing the per- mitting rules or granting the de- rogation	Not explicitly; compensation elsewhere not required; yet depending on how the MGES and/or environmental targets have been defined in national implementation, compensating the loss elsewhere may prevent the need for the derogation from being triggered, yet this interpretation has not been confirmed by the CJEU	Not required

3.3.2 Area-based protection

For achievement of its objectives in protecting and restoring biodiversity and habitats, the EU Biodiversity Strategy lists as its main instruments the establishment of a network of protected areas and restoration of the protected areas through management plans. In relation to establishing the protection area network, the strategy sets an aim to protect and effectively manage at least 30% of the EU's seas, where at least 1/3 of protected areas is put under strict protection. In addition, the strategy sets an ambition to improve the management of existing Marine Protected Areas (MPA) and enhance their connectivity to ensure their effectiveness in conserving marine biodiversity.

The main area-based protection instrument in EU law covering marine biodiversity is found in the Nature Directives. The Natura 2000 network consists of Special Protection Areas for Birds (SPAs), established to protect Annex I species of the BD, and Special Areas of Conservation (SACs), established to protect Annex I habitat types and Annex II habitats of species of the HD. SPAs and SACs often overlap in practice. A sufficient and representative sample of each habitat type is selected for the Natura 2000 network. Therefore, the Natura 2000-protection does not cover all occurrences of habitats or habitats of species listed in the Nature Directives, but a compilation of sites that is deemed sufficient for protecting them and reaching FCS. For this reason, and because the Directives cover only a few marine habitats and species, the Natura 2000-network alone cannot provide the aspired 30 % coverage for protection in the sea space (European Environment Agency, 2018 & European Court of Auditors, 2020).

The Nature Directives do not themselves put forward comprehensive and strict protection regimes for the sites. Article 6 of the HD harmonises strict conditions for authorising new projects that affect the site and requires Member States to put in place necessary conservation measures involving, if need be, appropriate management plans. However, it is up for the Member States to decide, whether the areas are e.g. designated nature conservation areas under their national laws, how strict of a conservation status is applied, and what uses – apart from the plans and projects to which Art 6(3) applies – are allowed in the areas. The HD itself states that designation of a Natura 2000-site is not considered to require the site to be established as a nature reserve or strictly conserved area, if the necessary conservation measures are taken and protection is ensured by the necessary legislative, administrative or contractual measures (Art 6(1)). For these reasons, the Natura 2000-network alone, as it now exists, does not per se meet the Biodiversity Strategy's targets on the protected areas neither on the quantity of areas nor the effectiveness of their management, let alone the 10 % target for strictly protected areas. Notably, the NRL introduces requirements that restoration measures are put in place to cover the habitats in need of restoration and those measures should prioritise the Natura 2000-areas. Thus, the NRL has potential to supplement and reinforce the HD in relation to subjecting the Natura 2000-areas to effective area-based management and restoration measures, albeit it does not trigger increases in the coverage of the Natura 2000-network nor constitute strict protection as the restoration measures will only gradually cover the areas and significant deterioration is to be prevented only after good condition has been reached.

However, the MSFD can substantiate the Nature Directives in terms of the area coverage of protected areas. According to Article 13(4) of the MSFD, the programmes of measures compiled as parts of the marine strategies must include "spatial protection measures, contributing to coherent and representative networks of marine protected areas, adequately covering the diversity of the constituent ecosystems." These areas can include the SPAs and the SCIs under the Nature Directives as well as marine protected areas agreed with international or regional agreements covering the marine region. The provision thus requires Member States to review the ecological coverage and coherence of the network of existing marine protected areas set up under the Nature Directives and international law and, on the basis of this assessment, complete the network of protected areas as is required for achieving MGES from the biodiversity protection point of view (MSFD CIS, 2014). Notably, the MSFD's regime puts emphasis on the coherence and representativeness of the network and the effectiveness of conservation measures, taking into account all marine habitats and ecosystem characteristics, not only selected species and habitats (European Commission, 2020f). The establishment of new sites under the MSFD's programmes of measures is thus not linked to the completion of the Natura 2000 network but should also take into account species and habitats of national and regional importance (MSFD CIS, 2014). Setting up marine protection areas under the MSFD should be regarded as a main instrument for increasing the coverage of area-based protection towards the Biodiversity Strategy's "30 % by 2030" objective.

Improving the network of protected areas does not only mean establishing new protected areas, but also ensuring effectiveness of the protection. As established above, the Natura 2000 - protection does not in itself put forward comprehensive set of restrictions on the use of the area or other types of measures (European Commission, 2020a & European Court of Auditors, 2020). It is up to the Member States to decide, whether the sites are established as nature reserves or conservation areas under national law, and it is the national law that prescribes then the scope and scale of restrictions and management measures. Similarly, the MSFD does not explicitly determine what kind of protection level and management measures should pertain to the MPA's established in connection to its programmes of measures. Accordingly, the Biodiversity Strategy's objective that 10% of MPA's are subjected to strict protection does not automatically follow from merely implementing the Natura 2000 or the MSFD's area-based protection but requires national measures to be taken on selected sites.

However, the Member States' efforts in implementation are bound by the legal impacts of the substantive objectives of the relevant directives. Under the Nature Directives, Member States have an obligation of result to prevent deterioration of and significant disturbance to the natural values of Natura 2000-sites (from new plans and projects subject to appropriate assessment under Art 6(3), but also from other types of activities and uses). Under the MSFD, Member States have obligations of best effort in relation to the MGES objective, which means that they are under an obligation to take all reasonable measures towards achieving and maintaining good status of the components of marine ecosystems included in the objectives. Living up to their obligations under these directives can mean establishing nature reserves, compiling management plans or setting up restrictions inside or outside the MPAs, such as (temporary) fishing bans, restrictions on certain types of fishing techniques or hunting, or restrictions of

waterborne traffic or other uses. Further, the NRL introduces obligations to put in place restoration measures and prevent significant deterioration – albeit only after good condition has been reached – of marine habitats covered by the MSFD too. While the NRL’s requirements could potentially improve the status of these habitats, they do not appear to constitute ‘strict protection’ as the restoration measures will only gradually cover the areas and significant deterioration is to be prevented only after good condition has been reached.

3.3.3 Species protection regimes

Another key instrument in the Nature Directives is their species protection regimes. Art 12 of the HD sets out protection requirements for species of Community importance as defined in Annex IV(a), which includes prohibiting all forms of deliberate capture or killing of specimens of these species in the wild and deterioration or destruction of breeding sites or resting places. Moreover, Annex V of the Habitats Directive lists the animal and plant species whose extraction and exploitation may require regulation. According to Art 14(1) of the HD, Member States must take the necessary measures to ensure that the exploitation of specimens of Annex V species does not conflict with the maintenance of FCS for the species. These measures may in particular include temporary or local bans on the exploitation of specimens, time limits and regulation of methods, the application of hunting and fishing rules that take into account the conservation of populations, or a system of permits or quotas for the taking of specimens (Article 14(2)). Art 16 of the HD provides for derogation from these protection requirements and restrictions for the reasons listed therein, if there is no satisfactory alternative and the derogation is not detrimental to the maintenance of the populations of the species concerned at a favourable conservation status in their natural range.

Article 5 of the BD provides a general system of protection for all bird species and their specimens within its scope of application. This includes all sea bird species naturally occurring in the wild state in Europe (Art 1(1)). According to Art 5(1), “Member States shall take the requisite measures to establish a general system of protection for all species of birds referred to in Article 1”, which includes prohibitions on deliberate killing or capture of the specimens, deliberate destruction of, or damage to, their nests and eggs and deliberate disturbance of these birds particularly during the period of breeding and rearing (Art 5(1), paras a), b) and d)).¹⁵ Art 9(1) and (2) provide a possibility to derogate from these restrictions, where there is no other satisfactory solution, for the reasons listed in the provision. Accordingly, European sea bird species are at the outset protected under this strict regime that prohibits the killing and capturing of their every specimen and damaging their nests and eggs. Subject to the conditions laid down therein, Art 7 of the BD stipulates that the bird species listed in Annex II may be hunted under national legislation, provided that the Member States ensure that the hunting of these species does not jeopardise conservation efforts in their distribution area. In practice, this means that

¹⁵ In addition, Art 6(1) provides that Member States must prohibit the sale, transport for sale, keeping for sale and the offering for sale of live or dead birds and of any readily recognisable parts or derivatives of all bird species referred to in Art 1(1), unless a derogation from the prohibition in accordance with Art 6(2) or (3) applies.

national hunting legislation needs have in place the necessary mechanisms and safeguards so that hunting of these bird species is controlled according to what is needed for reaching the FCS (see C-60/05 WWF Italia and Others v Regione Lombardia at para 32). What this means is that the hunting of an individual specimen of these species needs not to be justified with application of Art 9(1) exemption. Yet, Art 9(1) exemption may be applied to the conditions and restrictions following from Art 7 on the species-level hunting practices.

Regarding the relationship between the species protection regimes in the Nature Directives and the MSFD and the WFD, a general remark is that there is no incoherence. The WFD's objectives, assessment and water management policy does not concern any individual species, but the ecological status focuses on the groups of certain species, such as fish, as one of the elements in the functions of the ecological system. Thus, the protection level of individual species, their specimens or their nests or breeding sites is not reflected in the WFD's objectives.

The MSFD's objectives and assessments do include specific species, especially those included in the HD and the BD. Instead, the MSFD's objectives and assessments focus on the level of populations, there are no objectives related to individual specimens or nesting/breeding sites. Thus, there are no legal obligations or regulation in the MSFD on prohibitions and exemptions related to killing, capturing, or damaging individual specimen or nests that would conflict with the HD and the BD. Yet as the MGES includes considerations of the viability of the populations of these species, the species conservation regimes under the HD and the BD provide a policy instrument also in the MSFD's implementation, which can constitute a marine management measure to ensure that MGES is achieved with regard to that species (D1 descriptor). However, it should be recalled that while the BD includes also all sea birds, the HD includes only a few marine animal and plant species. As the MSFD's MGES objectives cover also a wider range of marine species than the HD, achieving MGES on all parts may require putting in place additional national species protection measures or extending the regimes provided in the HD in the implementation to cover also additional marine species.

3.3.4. Strategic planning instruments – the marine strategies, river basin management plans and nature restorations plans

With respect to the marine biodiversity, it is important to recall that the nature of aquatic environment may necessitate different approaches in conservation policies than what works for terrestrial environments. One crucial aspect is the distribution of pollution; inputs of polluting substances, such as nutrients and chemicals, or disturbances such as energy and noise do not only have impacts in the place of their origin, but they are spread in wide areas of the marine environment. Moreover, many uses of the sea space are not located in distinct locations either but take place around the area (e.g. fishing not restricted to fishing sites, waterborne traffic not restricted to roads). Protecting the marine environment and marine nature needs to take a more holistic approach compared to traditional area-based nature conservation, which focuses on identifying individual important sites and restricting their use in order to protect the natural values. For example, the adverse effects of eutrophication cannot be effectively controlled with only traditional nature conservation legislation. In 2020, the EEA reported that loss of marine biodiversity in Europe's seas had not been halted, with a high proportion of marine species and

habitats assessments showing an unfavourable conservation status or a status that was unknown (European Environment Agency, 2020).

For this purpose, the marine management regime under the MSFD and the water management system under the WFD play a crucial role alongside the MPAs. These planning instruments have a key function to coordinate multiple sectors/actors towards common challenges and goals.¹⁶ Under the MSFD, Member States need to assess the current status of the 11 qualitative descriptors and the elements associated with each of them, then analyse and identify the predominant pressures and impacts, including human activity, that affect the status of those elements, then establish environmental targets that address the desired levels of impacts or activity, and then compile programmes of measures, which include the necessary measures for steering the human activities, uses and impacts in accordance of the environmental targets that will allow good status to be reached (MSFD Art 8(1), para (a) and (b), Art 10(1) and 13(1)). With regard to the elements of marine biodiversity assessed under the qualitative descriptors, for instance, the Member States are required to analyse and identify all human activities (at sea or on land) that affect or impact them in any relevant way with respect to meeting GES and put in place management measures to control such activities and impacts. In accordance with Art 13(2) of the MSFD, the programmes of measures under marine strategies should include the measures that are taken under other EU legislation, most notably the WFD, the Urban Wastewater Treatment Directive and the Bathing Water Directive. Apart from this, Member States have the flexibility to utilise different instruments, such as those that are provided in the indicative list of measures in Annex VI. Thus, the choice of the instruments and their design features is not guided specifically by the MSFD, but the idea is that the Member States' substantive legal obligations on achieving MGES should steer the Member States to plan the most effective solution in each context in delivering the MGES objectives. However, this has not been realised as the legal implications of the Directives' objectives have remained unclear, which directly affects the level of ambition and stringency of the marine management plans.

In the WFD, the scope of the water management measures is determined based on the scope of anthropogenic pressures that have been found to cause measurable impacts on the ecological quality elements or increases in the concentration of chemicals included in the chemical status assessment. The WFD provides certain mandatory instruments that are to be utilised as part of the programmes of measures, such as permit-based controls and permit review for certain water use activities and implementing the requirements of other EU environmental legislation, notably the Nitrates Directives, Industrial Emissions Directive or the Urban Wastewater Treatment Directive. Moreover, the Member States are required to implement all other types of measures that they deem necessary for reaching the Directives objectives; such supplementary measures may include legislation (such as generally binding norms), economic instruments, or restoration actions (Art 11(4) of the WFD, Annex VI, part B).

¹⁶ Sander 2024.

River basin management plans are adopted (and implemented) for river basin districts designated by the Member States, covering the inland surface waters, groundwaters and coastal water bodies belonging to these districts. As such, they aim to managing impacts to these waters in the main watersheds in the Member States. In turn, the MSFD requires Member States to adopt one marine strategy document encompassing their entire marine waters, including the coastal waters in a supplementary manner. As such, the planning instruments in the WFD and the MSFD have the potential to capture a variety of perspectives into the management of waters and the marine environment, where the WFD's RBMPs focus on river basin systems flowing into the seas – or at least to coastal waters – and the MSFD's marine strategies bring forward a bigger marine environmental perspective. The policy-cycles of river basin management planning and marine strategies are quite coherent as the Directives require the compilation and adoption of the plans in the same six-year cycle.

The relationship between the MSFD's marine management and the WFD's water management planning and the Nature Directives' conservation regimes is mutually complementary. On the one hand, the more integrated and holistic management planning regimes provide policy instruments that can tackle various pressures and environmental problems in the marine environment, which the area-based protection cannot effectively address (such as eutrophication). On the other hand, the Nature Directives' instruments provide tangible policy instruments that can be utilised as parts of the management plans and the programmes of measures under the MSFD and the WFD. There are, however, potential weaknesses identified that can undermine the effectiveness of these combined regimes. With regard to the MSFD, although the marine strategies include comprehensive different characteristics, elements and pressures in the marine environment, including conservation values, the weakness is the Directive's lack of clear substantive legal obligations, which adversely affects the level of ambition and stringency of the marine management plans. With respect to the WFD, the Directive's water management objectives have been interpreted as obligations of result for the Member States, which would entail that the Member States are obliged to include in the river basin management plans all the necessary measures needed to ensure that the objectives are reached. The weakness of the WFD is that it does not specifically note nature conservation values or biodiversity in its objectives but focuses on the overall ecological functions of the water bodies. This means that the specific needs for conserving, for example a threatened or endangered marine habitat or species, are not reflected in the WFD's objectives and the WFD cannot be used to oblige the Member States to take on protection action, if the habitat or species in question is not included in the HD or the BD.

Furthermore, achieving the objectives related to marine biodiversity requires coordination with a wide range of policies and uses of the sea. Reducing the negative impacts of different maritime uses and activities requires comprehensive and holistic spatial planning that could reconcile different uses and environmental objectives, for example by instructing harmful activities outside the most sensitive areas. Spatial planning can also go some way to managing the combined and cumulative impacts of different activities that for example permitting regimes targeting individual new activities often fall short of (Pappila and Puharinen, 2022). As the Nature Directives only provide assessments of and requirements for different uses of

the sea space within their specifically delimited protection areas, they cannot comprehensively answer to the need of spatial planning. Instead, one crucial instrument for allocating space and reconciling different uses with the needs of biodiversity protection and improvement could be the marine spatial planning (drawing up maritime spatial plans, MSPs) under the EU's Maritime Spatial Planning Directive (2014/89/EU).

However, the capacity of the MSPD to produce an ecosystem-centred and forceful instrument in steering towards biodiversity goals is limited. The MSPD aims simultaneously to promote sustainable economic growth, sustainable development and sustainable use of marine resources in marine areas (Art. 1(1)). In drawing up and implementing the MSPs, Member States must take due account of the various economic, social and environmental considerations related to the marine areas in order to support the sustainable development and growth of the marine sector, in accordance with an ecosystem-based approach, and promote coexistence of relevant activities and uses (Art. 5(1)). According to Article 5(2), MSPs should aim to contribute simultaneously to the sustainable development of the energy, maritime transport, fisheries, and aquaculture sectors and to the preservation, protection and enhancement of the environment, in addition to other objectives that Member States may set. Yet, environmental considerations are generally integrated into the objectives of marine spatial planning, they are not set as central prerequisites for the plans; for example, the MSFD's MGES objective or the FCS objectives for marine habitats and species under the Nature Directives are not mentioned in the Directive. It is up to the Member State to determine whether and how much weight to give to the biodiversity objectives in the plan (Art. 5(3)). Furthermore, the effectiveness of the MSPs as policy instruments is undermined by the fact that the Directive does not require the plans to have binding legal effects. Hence, Member States may opt for MSPs that are more of cooperation and information-guidance instruments (Pappila and Puharinen, 2022).

With the NRL, there will be another strategic and integrated management planning instrument that applies in the marine environment; the nature restoration plans (Art 14). Member States are required to prepare a national restoration plan to meet the restoration targets and fulfil the obligations set out in the regulation, including those for the restoration of the coastal habitats listed in the HD and the wider marine habitats and habitats of the species. The NRL explicitly fosters coherence and synergies with the other strategic planning instruments, as it requires Member States to take into account particularly the conservation measures for Natura 2000 established under the HD, the water management measures under the WFD and the marine strategies under the MSFD in compiling restoration plans (Art 14(14)(a),(c) and (d)). However, the content and form of measures has been left completely to the discretion of the Member States, as only an indicative list of possible measures is provided in Annex VII (Art 14(16)(a)). As has been seen with the MSFD, such flexibility can work in inducing Member States to figure out and utilise the most effective combinations of measures, if the substantive objectives of the instrument provide sufficiently clear and precise obligations for them to achieve improvements in the environment; for the MSFD this is not the case, but the focus in the NRL's substantive obligations is more precisely on the measures, which might suggest that it is easier to find the substantive legal impetus within the NRL's regime. The NRL's indicative list of measures is

also much more specific than that of the MSFD's, and the measures listed in carry the potential of addressing various threats to marine biodiversity in the seas.¹⁷

3.4 Conclusions

As can be seen from the analysis above, the objectives and instruments of the Nature Directives, the MSFD, the WFD and the NRL form a complex policy cluster for marine biodiversity protection. While both the objectives and the instruments are by their general nature quite coherent and aim to direct towards improving the state of marine biodiversity, there are several coherence challenges in relation to all analysed features. However, the issue is rather fragmentation than outright incoherence. Fragmentation exists in the substance of the objectives, the timeframes for their achievement, the legal impacts of the objectives in relation to Member States obligation and the instruments, particularly rules on authorising new projects as well as the exemptions. The key challenges for the coherence of the joint framework of these policies can be summed up and explained as follows:

- 1) The objectives of the policies are fragmented with a result that no policy addresses all relevant aspects of marine biodiversity with legally forceful conservation obligations.

The conservation objectives of the Nature Directives, and the objectives of the MSFD and the WFD are generally rather coherent. Yet, there are certain differences of emphasis. The Nature Directives focus on the achievement of FCS for the habitats and species deemed in need of special protection; thus, they do not aim to cover the different components of marine ecosystems or protect biodiversity as a whole.

The Nature Directives are substantiated by the WFD and MSFD that aim to achieve aquatic and marine ecosystems of good ecological quality, which supports the protection of many species and habitats covered by the Nature Directives. Of the two, the WFD's objectives pertain considerably legal forcefulness in obligating Member States to deliver good status of the coastal waters. However, the WFD's objective of good ecological status focuses on selected ecological aspects of water bodies, which generally supports marine biodiversity but does not specifically address it.

The MSFD's objective of good marine environmental status is the most comprehensive as it covers a broader consideration of the structure, functions and processes, characteristics, and major pressures on marine ecosystems from human activities. There is also some overlap between the objectives of the Nature Directives and those of the MSFD, as the MGES objective in the MSFD includes the FCS for the habitats and species included in the Nature Directives regime. Yet the MSFD's biodiversity objectives also go far beyond the conservation values in the Nature Directives, covering also broader sea floor habitats, species richness and food webs. However, the problem with the MSFD is the vague and uncertain legal status of its objectives.

¹⁷ The measures include, for instance, direct measures to restore areas of sea-grass meadows and other habitats, but also measures to tackle specific threats to marine nature, such as reducing pollution.

The NRL includes also wide array of marine nature in the scope of its restoration objectives, thus substantiating and reinforcing the existing vague legal obligations particularly in the Nature Directives and the MSFD. The coherence challenge pertaining to the NRL is that its obligations focus on putting in place restoration measures that address only parts of the area of habitats by 2030, 2040 and 2050. It is unclear, whether meeting the NRL's objectives will produce synergies in terms of also delivering the objectives of other instruments, which concern directly the status of the marine environment and its components.

- 2) Each instruments contains different deadlines for the objectives, and the timeframes are not aligned.

The Nature Directives, the MSFD and the WFD showcase a spectrum of different deadlines for the objectives; in the Nature Directives, there is no deadline attached to the objectives, the MSFD's 2020 objective for MGES appears to be more of an instructive deadline than a legally binding one, while the WFD's 2027 deadline is potentially a binding one, while rather vast possibilities exist to lower the ambition level of the objectives even beyond this deadline. Furthermore, the NRL introduces its own deadlines of 2030, 2040 and 2050 that significantly exceed those of the MSFD and the WFD; furthermore, as those deadlines structure the gradual increase in measures, they are not deadlines for achieving certain status in the environment unlike the ones in the MSFD and the WFD. Thus, while similar measures may be used to deliver the objectives in the different policies – such as reducing pollution and protecting the most vulnerable occurrences of habitats – the different timeframes risk creating fragmentation and confusion on planning the measures.

- 3) The legal obligations on Member States and the various exemptions from them are inconsistent with no clear linkages to one another to improve coherence.

The legal obligations on Member States related to achieving the objectives in the instruments are rather mixed, as some of the obligations are obligations of result – requiring Member States to de facto deliver the result – and some of them are obligations of best effort, which require merely diligent action with aspiration that the goal would be reached. Similarly to what was said with the deadlines, while similar measures and efforts would be required from Member States to deliver the objectives in the different policies, the different legal impetus risk creating fragmentation and confusion on planning the measures. Especially the WFD and the MSFD include a complex system of exemptions from the objectives where it is not quite clear, what exempting from the objectives of one policy means in terms of the legal requirements related to the objectives in other policies. While it does not rectify these coherence challenges, the NRL at least does not add to incoherence here as its focus on gradual coverage of area by restoration measures entails a possibility for the Member States to prioritise actions to which exemptions under other policies do not apply.

- 4) While the policy instruments can be interpreted in a rather consistent manner, the complexity creates a risk of distortion and the instruments' design leaves a lot to be desired for in terms of them being able to steer meeting the objectives.

The area-based and species conservation regimes in the Nature Directives form the backbone of marine biodiversity protection. Nevertheless, due to the nature of the aquatic environments and the insufficiency of the compilation of marine habitats and species included particularly under the HD's regimes, they alone are not enough to meet the Biodiversity Strategy's objectives or ensure effective protection of marine nature. The MSFD's and the WFD's instruments can however supplement the traditional conservation instruments. First, the integrated marine strategies and river basin management plans and their programmes of measures can respond to pressures, impacts and threats that are not addressed with area-based conservation. Second, the MSFD contains a supplementary system of marine protected areas that can be utilised to extend the area-based protection to cover a wider range of habitats than those of the HD. In response, the area-based protection and species protection regimes of the HD and BD form important, harmonised and specific instruments for especially the MSFD's objectives. However, the implementation of the protection regimes, especially the MPAs, has not been very effective in practise, and the EU minimum requirements need to be supported by national conservation regulation and restrictions on key pressures, such as fishing activities (European Court of Auditors, 2020). The NRL adds another layer of strategic planning to this mix and while it contains some potential in supplementing and reinforcing some aspects of the instrument mix, it also pertains significant flexibility on the Member States; thus, national implementation is a key role in ensuring coherence. In addition, a specific coherence challenge in the instrumentation of these policies is the different sets of rules on authorising new projects and particularly the somewhat different scopes of application of the derogations and their conditions. Depending on where exactly in the marine area a project is located, it may be assessed under 2-4 different sets of permitting rules and derogation regimes.

More specifically in relation to the EGD's objectives for marine biodiversity, the policies display variable degree of potential to deliver these objectives. For instance, while the 30 % goals for the protection area coverage can be legally operationalised through the complementary application of different instruments (mainly the nature Directives and the MSFD), the EU legislation does not provide strict legal protection for the 10 % of habitats mentioned in the EGD's objectives. Similarly, the vagueness in the HD's obligations on the management of Natura 2000-sites and the MSFD's ambiguity in the legal bindingness of its objectives undermine the realisation of the EGD target that protected areas are effectively managed. In relation to the EGD's objectives for restoring habitats and ecosystems, the NRL provides an important contribution to the policy mix; yet the NRL does not fully live up to these objectives, as it only prohibits deterioration of habitats and ecosystems after good condition is reached and restoration objectives only cover maximum of 90 % of ecosystems by 2050.

4 The Zero Pollution Stream (MSFD, WFD, ND)

4.1 Introduction

The overall ambition of the Green Deal's zero-pollution stream is to create a toxic-free environment to protect human health and the environment by reducing all kinds of pollution of all environmental media. The EGD puts forward a vision that by 2050, "air, water and soil pollution is reduced to levels no longer considered harmful to health and natural ecosystems and that respect the boundaries our planet can cope with". To structure the progress towards this vision, the EGD and the related EU zero pollution action plan (COM(2021) 400 final) put forward six specific targets for 2030 addressing required levels of reduction of different types of pollution in different parts of the environment. For the marine environment, the most relevant type of harmful pollution is diffuse pollution of nutrients and chemicals.¹⁸ With respect to the marine environment, the most relevant zero pollution target thus is target 4, which states that by 2030, the EU should reduce by 50% nutrient losses, the use and risk of chemical pesticides, the use of the more hazardous ones, and the sale of antimicrobials for farmed animals and in aquaculture.¹⁹

Nutrient and chemical pollution in the marine environment originates mostly from land-based sources (European Environment Agency, 2020). Agriculture is the main diffuse source for surface water pollution, with high emissions of nutrients, such as nitrogen and phosphorus, and chemicals, such as pesticides (European Environmental Agency, 2021). For this reason, the CrossGov's assessments related to the zero pollution goals will be focused on the policies related to agricultural pollution. The incremental role of agriculture is also noted in the EGD, which included the adoption of the EU Farm to Fork Strategy (COM(2020) 381 final) to establish specific targets for the agricultural activities in relation to the various GD goals. With regards to water pollution, the Farm to Fork strategy puts forward the following targets:

- reduce the overall use and risk of chemical pesticides by 50% and the use of more hazardous pesticides by 50% by 2030;
- reduce nutrient losses by at least 50%, while ensuring that there is no deterioration in soil fertility;
- reduce the use of fertilisers by at least 20% by 2030;

¹⁸ See EEA 2021, p. 22, table 3.1 showing that out of pollution pressures, diffuse pollution of nutrients and chemicals is the biggest type of pressure measures by the percentage of surface waters bodies and groundwater affected by it. On the marine environment's side, see European Environmental Agency, Marine messages II: Navigating the course towards clean, healthy and productive seas through implementation of an ecosystem-based approach. EEA Report 17/2019, p. 30. In the Baltic area and Black Sea, for example, the key reason for the impaired conditions in the marine environment is inputs of polluting substances, i.e. nutrients and contaminants. Inputs of polluting substances are key reasons for impaired conditions also in the Mediterranean and the North-East Atlantic Ocean.

¹⁹ Also **Target nr 5**. by 2030, the EU should reduce by 50% plastic litter at sea and by 30% microplastics released into the environment.

- at least 25% of the EU's agricultural land under organic farming by 2030 and a significant increase in organic aquaculture (European Commission, 2020b).

In this assessment, the focus is on the targets related to and policies regulating nutrient emissions from agriculture. According to the EU zero pollution action plan, better implementation of the EU's existing regulatory framework concerning prevention of pollution is a priority action towards realising the targets and the overall vision (European Commission, 2020c). The WFD and the MSFD contribute to realising the zero-pollution ambition for aquatic ecosystems. Furthermore, for controlling the inputs of pollution from various sources, the WFD and the MSFD are substantiated by sectoral pollution policies. For agricultural nutrient emissions, the key sectoral policy is the Nitrates Directive (91/676/EEC).²⁰

Accordingly, the ND, the WFD and the MSFD form the EU zero pollution policy cluster with respect to nutrient pollution originating from agricultural activities. For assessing the coherence of EU policies towards the EGD biodiversity objectives, it is thus necessary to assess – in accordance with the CrossGov coherence methodology (CrossGov Deliverable 1.2) – to which extent the objectives and the instruments (coherence attributes) of the policies within the cluster are coherent in forming a uniform ambition on the level of protection and means to achieve it. Afterwards, the coherence of policies driving the key pressure sector – the EU CAP presented in chapter 5 – can be assessed against the picture formed in this section on the overall EU zero pollution cluster.

The analysis is structured as follows. In accordance with the CrossGov methodology, subsection 4.2 will analyse the coherence of objectives related to nutrient concentrations in the aquatic environment and emissions from agricultural activities in the WFD, the MSFD and the ND. The analysis will focus particularly on the substance of the objectives, the legal force in terms of Member States obligations and the exemptions from the objectives. Subsection 4.3 will follow up with an analysis of the coherence of the instruments in the policies. Finally, the section will conclude by presenting a summary of the coherence challenges detected.

4.2 Coherence of the objectives

4.2.1 Substance of the objectives in relation to nutrient pollution

Nutrient pollution from agriculture usually enters the aquatic environment through runoffs to inland surface waters (and groundwater), from where it eventually makes its way to the marine environment. Accordingly, the WFD's objectives for and regulation of surface water status in the receiving water bodies apply *a priori* to such pollution. As noted above, the general objectives of the WFD are the achievement of the good status and the prevention of deterioration, which for surface waters address ecological and chemical status (Art 4(1)). Good

²⁰ Other key sectoral pollution policies addressing the sources of inputs of pollutants to aquatic environment are the Urban Wastewater Treatment Directive that covers the nutrient and chemical pollution from urban wastewater treatment facilities and the Industrial Emissions Directive that regulates polluting emissions from industrial activities.

ecological status illustrates a healthy and functioning state of the different surface water categories – lakes, river, transitional waters and coastal waters – which is assessed on the basis of typical biological, hydrological-morphological and physico-chemical quality factors. Eutrophication is typically reflected in biological factors (e.g. phytoplankton in coastal waters) and physico-chemical factors (e.g. oxygen conditions and nutrient conditions in coastal waters); in good ecological status, these factors should show only slight alteration through eutrophication caused by anthropogenic pressures (Annex V, section 1.2). Under the WFD, the eutrophication situation is assessed for each water body individually.

For assessing the eutrophication situation in the entire marine environment, the MSFD and its objectives are the most relevant legal instruments. In the MSFD, the main substantive obligation for the Member States is provided in Article 1(1) that puts forward a general obligation that Member States “take the necessary measures to achieve or maintain good environmental status in the marine environment by the year 2020 at the latest”. The general objective of good marine environmental status (MGES) is further specified and defined by Member States for their marine areas based on 11 qualitative descriptors (D), provided in Annex I of the MSFD. Descriptor D5 concerns eutrophication. According to Annex I of the MSFD, MGES for eutrophication entails that “human-induced eutrophication is minimised, especially adverse effects thereof, such as losses in biodiversity, ecosystem degradation, harmful algae blooms and oxygen deficiency in bottom waters”. Member States must adopt more specific metrics and definitions for MGES in implementing the Directive, guided by the Commission’s Decision 2017/848/EU. In the case of eutrophication, the Decision lays down specific assessment criteria and metrics, including nutrient concentration levels, occurrence of harmful algae blooms and oxygen conditions. Furthermore, the MSFD requires Member States to establish specific environmental targets to guide the progress towards achieving MGES, which can specify either desired conditions in the marine environment or reduction targets for pressures and impacts affecting the state of the descriptors (Arts 3(7), 10). In case of eutrophication, the targets could, for example, put forward thresholds for maximum allowable input of nutrients in different parts of the marine area, or allocate reduction targets between sectors, such as agriculture (European Commission, 2020d).

Accordingly, the WFD’s and the MSFD’s objectives concerning eutrophication are highly coherent. The core difference is their geographical scale, which has an impact on the regulatory outcomes: a local scale has a higher resolution, as it were, and is better equipped to produce detailed rules, whereas national or even international scales, which have a lower resolution, produce general frameworks and guidance (De Sousa Santos, 1987, Westholm, 2019 and Puharinen and Belinskij, 2023). In terms of legal scaling, the MSFD’s marine environmental management framework and MGES objectives address national marine waters²¹ in their entirety, yet Member States have the flexibility to make further subdivisions of their marine waters at appropriate levels in implementing the MSFD. Accordingly, the MSFD establishes a

²¹ Marine waters extend from the baseline to the outer limit of their exclusive economic zones (EEZ) (Art 3(1) paragraph (a)).

national legal scale for marine ecosystem management, which is capable of producing a national bigger picture on the marine eutrophication problem and is thus an appropriate legal threshold for assessing national level policies and laws, for example those regulating agricultural conduct (Puharinen and Belinskij, 2023). The regime can also produce nutrient reduction targets for specific sectors, such as the Member States agricultural sector which should then be operationalized through policies and law. The WFD's management approach, in turn, falls on the level of river basin districts and the objectives concern small units, that is, waters bodies like stretches of coastal waters. This enables more refined analyses and management approaches with regional and local focus, which provides a more concrete basis for legal obligations designed to prevent and minimise different impacts of individual activities (De Sousa Santos, 1987, and Puharinen and Belinskij, 2023). Achieving the WFD's objectives in surface waters reduces nutrient loads eventually ending up in the marine waters, which thus supports reaching MGES there. In this vein, the directives' objectives complement each other in forming a spectrum of objectives applied in multiple ecosystem and management scales in relation to the problem.

In addition to the WFD's and the MSFD's objectives for levels of eutrophication in aquatic environments, the ND provides objectives and management regime focusing on the agricultural sector. The general objective of the ND is to reduce water pollution caused or induced by nitrates from agricultural sources and to prevent further such pollution (Art 1). For this purpose, the Directive provides a general framework through which the Member States should address the spreading or discharge of livestock effluents and the excessive use of fertilizers. Moreover, the Directive contains two more tangible objectives that should structure its implementation.

First, Member States are to take specific measures to protect waters that are affected by pollution, or which could be affected by pollution if action is not taken (Art 3(1) and (3)). These measures include designating the drainage areas to such waters as nitrates vulnerable zones (NVZs) and establishing action programs for them for the purpose of realising the general objective of Art 1, that is, reducing and preventing the pollution (Art 3(2) and 5(1)). Annex I of the Directive provides specific criteria for the identification of waters within the meaning of Art 3(1). Accordingly, Member States should identify waters according to Art 3(1) and apply the specific protection actions to them, if the criteria are triggered, which include a threshold of 50 mg/l nitrate in groundwater and of 50 mg/l nitrate in surface water²², or that freshwaters, coastal waters or marine waters are found to be eutrophic or that they may in the near future become eutrophic if action is not taken.

As these criteria for thresholds triggering action and application of the specific protection regime, they, in other words, constitute environmental quality standards for the concentrations

²² In Annex I of the ND, the threshold of 50 mg/l of nitrates concentration is only explicitly provided for groundwater, yet it extends to also surface waters via reference to the Drinking Water Directive (originally Directive 75/440/EEC, nowadays a recast Directive 2020/2184/EU). Despite this reference, the threshold applies to all surface waters, not only those subject to abstraction of drinking water (See C-293/97 Standley e.a. [1999] ECR I-2603).

and environmental impacts of nitrates in the aquatic ecosystems, which should not be exceeded. If the standards are exceeded or are at risk of being exceeded in the waters, Member States are required to take the protection measures under the Directive to reduce and prevent the pollution with the aim of decreasing the levels of nitrogen concentrations and eutrophication impacts below the thresholds. Such protection measures include drawing up action programs (Art 5) and including in them the measures established in Annex III to the Directive that lays down specific rules on i.a. manure spreading and land application of fertilisers. The ND's thresholds are generally parallel and thus coherent with the objectives of the WFD and the MSFD. However, as the objectives of the WFD and the MSFD describe good functioning and quality of specific parts of the aquatic ecosystems, of which vulnerability to nutrient pollution varies, especially the WFD's good status objective may sometimes necessitate lower concentrations of nitrates than the ND's thresholds (Wiering et. al., 2020).

The second objective in the ND is that the Member States should aim to provide all waters a general level of protection against pollution, for which purpose they should establish codes and programmes of good agricultural practise, implemented by farmer on a voluntary basis (Art 4(1)). This can be considered a pre-emptive objective, whose purpose is that the thresholds triggering specific action would not be exceeded in waters. Moreover, the objective may be particularly coherent with the MSFD, especially if Member States have set environmental targets for reducing the overall load from the agricultural sector.

Accordingly, the objectives of the WFD, the MSFD and the ND are generally coherent in terms of addressing nitrates pollution from agriculture. The objectives form a spectrum of legal thresholds both in terms of scoping different scales of ecosystems and areas. The ND's objective of reducing and preventing agricultural nitrates pollution is general enough so that it can be fitted into the different scales of the WFD and the MSFD that frame the aquatic ecosystems and their management. Reducing and preventing nitrates pollution can be a national scale general policy objective matching the MSFD's objective for national marine waters – this scale is particularly emphasised if the Member States have utilised their discretion to apply action plans in their entire territory (Art 3(5)). The objective can also be matched with the WFD's management scale of river basin districts particularly if the Member States put in the effort to designate the NVZs coherently with the river basin districts. Furthermore, the ND's general objective can also be interpreted for a narrower scale finding support from the WFD's objectives targeting individual water bodies and agricultural loads to them; in this case, the ND's objective of reducing and preventing pollution could find substance from the needs stemming from the WFD's good status objective and no-deterioration objective for individual water bodies.

The only notable gap in the objectives is that the ND and its objectives only address nitrates, not phosphorus, which may in some regions be even a more dominant cause of eutrophication. In turn, the WFD's and the MSFD's objectives related to eutrophication of waters include both eutrophication caused by nitrates and by phosphorus. There are no other EU-level measures in place for phosphorus either, setting more specific thresholds and management targets for

phosphorus is left to the discretion of the Member States in implementing the WFD and the MSFD.

Another notable point is that the timeframes of the Directives differ slightly; the MSFD required MGES to be reached in 2020, the WFD has allowed the deadline of achieving good status to be extended up until 2027 and the ND does not contain any deadlines for the achievement of its objective. Yet, the ND's objectives and regime are instrumental for the MSFD and the WFD in addressing pollution from agriculture in line with and as part of the efforts towards the ecosystem goals provided in the WFD and the MSFD with regard to eutrophication in the aquatic environment. Thus, the deadlines for achieving the ecosystem goals should also be considered to structure the implementation of the ND (see more on this dynamic in section 4.3 on the coherence of instruments). As regards to the differing deadlines of the WFD and the MSFD, the exemption regimes of the two directives in principle enable structuring the measures towards realising the objectives in sync with one another, provided that the Member States pay attention in applying the exemptions in a way that focuses on fostering coherence (see section 3.2.4 above).

4.2.2 Obligations on Member States and exemptions

The WFD

As established above in relation to biodiversity protection, the WFD's non-deterioration and good status objectives appear to constitute obligations of result for Member States (see section 3.2.3). This means that a Member State is in breach of the WFD, if it fails to attain the environmental objectives in all the relevant water bodies within the timeframe provided in the Directive, unless failure to do so is sufficiently and appropriately justified by the application of the Directive's exemptions. This also concerns attainment of good status objective in relation to eutrophication and curbing agricultural pollution accordingly. The Member States are to meet the WFD's objectives through the compilation of river basin management plans and related programs of measures, which are adopted for six-year cycles and should include the necessary measures targeting relevant pressures, activities and impacts to reduce the adverse impacts and allow the water bodies to recover to good status during the next management cycle.

Under Article 4(4), Member States have been able to extend the WFD's initial deadline of 2015, when the necessary improvements in water status could not reasonably be achieved due to technical (in)feasibility or disproportionate costs of the measures or due to natural conditions in the water body. Application of Article 4(4) does not mean foregoing taking all necessary measures to bring water bodies to good status but provides a possibility to employ a more reasonable timeframe for implementing measures considering technical and economic realities. Agricultural nutrient pollution has remained one of the most significant pressures throughout the Directive's implementation. The limited progress made on improving water status has so far invited wide use of the WFD's possibility (Art 4(4)) to extend the deadline for achieving good status. Yet, Article 4(4) limits the possibilities of extending the deadline based on technical feasibility and disproportionate costs to two updates of the RBMPs, that is, to 2027, after which further extension can only be applied based on natural conditions in the water

bodies. As eutrophication has affected several water bodies in Europe for a considerably long time, many water bodies will require more time for their natural processes to recover sufficiently to reach good status (Carvalho et. al., 2019).

However, based on the slow progress in taking measures to reduce nutrient loads, it is probable that in many Member States the failures to reach good status by 2027 due to agricultural nutrient pollution and eutrophication are also due of continuing lack of sufficient effort in implementing the necessary measures. As further time lags in taking measures to reduce agricultural pollution cannot be justified beyond 2027 under Art 4(4), the only available exemption after 2027 is the possibility to set less stringent environmental objectives under Art 4(5). Article 4(5) provides that the Member States may recalibrate the level of environmental ambition to reflect the status that they can achieve with the measures that are technically feasible and not disproportionately expensive (European Commission, 2009a). However, the less stringent objectives have to be set for each water body individually to reflect the ecological status that can be achieved by taking all measures that are not technically or economically impossible (Art 4(5), para (b)). Another precondition for applying the exemption is that the socioeconomic needs served by the human activity based on which less stringent environmental objectives are set cannot be achieved by other means, which are a significantly better environmental option (Art 4(5), para (a)). Accordingly, application of Art 4(5) to justify insufficient measures to reduce agricultural nutrient pollution necessitates that the Member States consider and justify the socioeconomic needs behind current sectoral practice against water quality objectives and furthermore, implement all measures to reduce pollution that are technically feasible and do not entail disproportionate costs. Nevertheless, Art 4(5) provides quite some flexibility in lowering the ambition level of water management objectives due to agricultural pressure.

MSFD

As stated above, the MSFD's obligations on Member States related to achieving and maintaining MGES in the marine environment appear to constitute obligations of best efforts. The Member States are thus not obliged to de facto ensure the achievement of MGES within the Directive's timeframe but are rather required to diligently implement all reasonable measures towards that objective. In relation to eutrophication and agricultural nutrient pollution, this means that Member States are required to implement all reasonable measures to reduce agricultural pollution to prevent further eutrophication and enable the marine environment to bounce back towards good status. For this purpose, Member States are to define sufficiently specific and ambitious environmental targets under Art 10 of the Directive that would steer the amount of nutrient pollution and establish sectoral practices in line with achieving the MGES objective, and compile and implement the necessary measures to this end in the programmes of measures.

Similarly to the WFD, the MSFD also contains an exemption regime that provides possibilities for Member States to justify failures to comply with their obligations in relation to MGES and realise the environmental targets. These exemptions, however, do not provide a readily applicable grounds to deviate from the requirements to address agricultural pollution

established above. According to Art 14(1), Member States may justify the failure to reach MGES or the environmental targets based on actions or inaction by other states, natural causes, force majeure, new physical modifications or natural conditions in the water bodies. None of these exemptions thus apply to situations, where the failure to reach MGES or environmental targets is due to lack of sufficient efforts to reduce agricultural pollution. However, it should be remembered that under the MSFD the sufficiency of efforts is not judged based on the state of the marine environment but based on whether reasonable efforts were implemented (obligation of best efforts). Accordingly, there is no requirement to implement the measures that would be required to achieve MGES or environmental targets in relation to eutrophication or agricultural pollution which are deemed unreasonable – for example due to technical or economic infeasibility or disproportionate inconvenience on farmers – as such measures fall outside the scope of the required best efforts.

Accordingly, the legal requirements stemming from the MGES objectives, and the exemptions provided from them support such strategic interpretation of the WFD's and the MSFD's joint regime that the WFD constitutes the priority instrument for dealing with agricultural nutrient pollution and the MSFD constitutes a supplementary regime bringing forward a wider geographic and legal scales perspective on the overall pressure to the marine environment. The obligations related to the MGES objective would appear to be generally fulfilled, if the Member States fulfil the obligations under the WFD to reduce agricultural pollution in surface waters and ensure the achievement of good ecological status, as diligent implementation of the WFD most probably constitutes best effort towards improving the marine environment towards MGES too. Yet, case-by-case assessment might show that reaching MGES for eutrophication would require additional efforts, of which reasonability determines whether they belong within the sphere of 'best efforts' that the MSFD requires. Furthermore, when the Member States apply the WFD's exemptions in relation to agricultural pollution, they need to demonstrate existence of technical infeasibility or disproportionality of costs. Hence, a measure that fulfils the WFD's conditions for exemption, i.e. is unreasonable under the WFD's regime, can most probably be considered unreasonable also under the MSFD, and hence, there is no requirement to implement it under the MSFD either. On the one hand, this dynamic between the WFD and the MSFD means that legal obligations and exemptions of the two directives are highly coherent in relation to agricultural pollution. On the other hand, however, this also means that in case Member States have utilised the flexibilities of the WFD's exemptions to insufficient efforts to reduce agricultural nutrient pollution, it is unlikely that the MSFD could generate additional legal rules and obligations to require more efforts from the Member States.

ND

The ND is somewhat different to that of the WFD and the MSFD, where the substantive legal obligations on Member States are derived from the directives' objectives, and which, furthermore, have to be fleshed out through interpretation. The regulatory logic in the ND is arguably more straightforward: the Directive sets an overall objective for the policy and then puts forward requirements and measures to be implemented by the Member States – including

restrictions and limitations on manure spreading²³ and promoting good agricultural practices – that are thought to lead to realisation of the policy objective.²⁴ While an environmental quality standard of 50mg/l is the trigger requiring a catchment area to be made an NVZ, there are no specific legally binding outcomes mandated by the Nitrates Directive (Boyle, 2014). While the ND requires Member States to take additional measures if the specific measures provided in it are not enough to achieve the reduction in nitrate pollution and prevention of further pollution that is the objective of the Directive, it has been thought that the objectives of the ND do not entail self-standing legal obligations for the Member States (Howarth, 2011). Instead, the substantive measures are provided specifically in the ND, and the Directive’s objectives provide general direction for interpreting the Member States obligations and implementing the specific rules and instruments (C-322/00 *Commission v Netherlands* ECLI:EU:C:2003:532, para 73; C-543/16 *Commission v Germany* ECLI:EU:C:2018:481, para 88).

Yet, it has been thought that the WFD and its objectives establish legal obligations related to the result to be achieved in the water bodies in relation to agricultural pollution, which also affects the Member States obligations under the ND. The WFD sets the goals and provides the overarching legal mechanism for the control of all forms of water pollution; hence, all elements of agricultural water pollution are brought within the scope of the WFD. For this reason, backed up by the fact that the WFD lists the implementation of the ND as one of the mandatory basic measures for water management (see art. 11(3)(a) and art. 10), the substantive obligations arising from the WFD also shape the implementation efforts of the ND. As the Member States have an obligation of result to achieve good water status, they also have an obligation of result to implement and utilise the ND as a water protection measure so that agricultural pollution is reduced and prevented in line with what is necessary to achieve the WFD’s objectives in that directive’s timeline (C-648/13 *Commission v Poland* (2016), paras 125 and 132). The same goes for the influence of the MSFD on the ND’s regime, albeit, firstly, that the MSFD’s objectives entail slightly more lenient obligations on the Member States and secondly, the MSFD relies mostly on the WFD on addressing land-based pollution such as agricultural nutrient pollution. However, as explained above, the WFD contains notably exemptions from the requirements to take measures to tackle pressures like agricultural pollution; if and when the exemptions are utilised by Member States, their application undermines how much the WFD’s objectives put forward legally forceful obligations to reduce pollution also in the implementation of the ND.

However, the ND’s interpretations may be in the process of taking a different direction due to relatively recent case-law by the CJEU, especially its ruling in 2018 in a so-called *German nitrate -case* (C-543/16 *Commission v Germany*). The case concerned alleged failures by Germany to fulfil its obligations under the ND, particularly Art 5(5) that requires Member

²³ Nitrates Directive limits livestock manure application to 170 kg N/ha per year within NVZs. Annex III(2).

²⁴ In the words of the CJEU, the “Directive seeks to create the instruments needed to ensure that waters in the Community are protected against pollution caused by nitrates from agricultural sources”. Case C-293/97 *Standley and Others* [1999] ECR I-2603, para 39; C-161/00 *Commission v Germany* [2002] ECR I-2753, para 42; C-322/00 *Commission v Netherlands* s [2003] ECR I-11267, para 46.

States to adopt supplementary measures in their NVZ action programs “as they consider necessary if (...) it becomes apparent that the measures referred to in (Art 4) paragraph 4 will not be sufficient for achieving the objectives specified in Article 1”.²⁵ The Commission had constructed its infringement action against Germany based on factual findings that the state of the waters in Germany had not improved during the implementation of the ND, and waters particularly in the marine and coastal areas were degrading due to eutrophication effects (paras 32 and 56). In essence, the Commission claimed that the fact that the ND’s objectives are not met indicates that the Member State has not implemented the directive properly; in a way, this interpretation hints towards treating the ND’s objectives as obligations of result of which fulfilment needs to be ensured by the Member States through the implementation of the directive’s specific provisions and, when needed, taking all necessary additional measures pursuant to Art 5(5). Germany, in turn, argued that the ND’s objectives would not have such legal impacts; the obligation to take additional measures is not triggered solely based on the fact that eutrophication occurs but instead, to prove an infringement, the Commission would need to show beyond reasonable doubt that the measures taken by Germany are insufficient to deal with the problem (paras 43-44 and 62). In other words, Germany appeared to consider that the ND establishes obligations of best effort at most in relation to addressing agricultural nutrient pollution (para 54). Germany also tried to justify its lack of action in putting in place supplementary measures based on the protection of fundamental rights and the principle of proportionality (para 75). In other words, it suggested that in putting in place measures to combat nitrates pollution from agriculture, Member States should balance the environmental considerations of the ND’s objectives with proportionality and feasibility of actions, like the balancing exercise under the WFD’s objectives and exemptions.

Remarkably, the Court sided with the Commission and established that “based on the fact that waters are polluted and that the measures adopted have not brought about improvement, it is sufficient to conclude that the measures in force were not sufficient to achieve the objectives of Art 1 ND, and thus, there is an obligation to take supplementary measures under Art 5(5)” (para 61).²⁶ According to the Court, the obligation to take additional measures exists as soon as the need for them is detected based on the information gained on the effectiveness of initial measures (C-322/00, para 166 and C-543/16, para 63). In this case, the Court considered that other measures were necessary since the measures in force were insufficient to achieve the objectives of the ND; thus, Germany had failed to comply with its obligations under the ND by failing to put in place additional measures that sufficiently and effectively address nutrient pollution in line with the Art 1 objective (C-543/16, paras 71 and 74). Germany’s argument related to fundamental rights and proportionality was also rejected (para 76). The Court also found infringements related to specific measures to be included in the action programs listed in Annex III based on the fact that the measures had not been de facto effective in reducing and preventing agricultural nitrates pollution, and because the measures in the national transposing act had not been related to the actual needs of the various crops, the needs in the various

²⁵ Translated from the original French language version.

²⁶ Translated from the original French language version.

pedoclimatic regions and the consideration of the impact of fertilization on water protection. This indicates that it is not sufficient for the Member States to merely establish general binding rules on fertilisation in line with Annex III in a general attempt to control agricultural nutrient pollution, but instead, the rules need to be adapted to regional conditions based on the need of fertilisation, amount of nutrient pollution and status of waters in different regions of the Member States to ensure the fulfilment of the ND's objectives.

The ruling thus established that the ND entails self-standing legal requirements for Member States to achieve the objectives of reducing and preventing pollution that are not only linked to the WFD or the MSFD. Apparently, what this also means is that in the event that the Member State applies the WFD's exemptions (and the same considerations in limiting the scope of efforts pursuant to the MSFD's best efforts obligation), there may still be substantive legal requirements under the ND to ensure reduction of pollution and impacts of eutrophication in the waters due to agricultural activity. Failure to improve the situation in water bodies and reduce the impacts of pollution indicates a breach of the obligations under the ND.

Moreover, it should be noted that the ND does not contain exemptions from its objectives and the related requirements. There is a possibility for the Member States to exempt from the obligation to designate nitrates vulnerable zones and instead, establish and apply action programs for their entire national territory (Art 3(5)); however, this is not an exemption from the objectives of the Directive, but merely provides Member States a margin of choice on how to structure their efforts towards the objectives. In sum, in light of the *German Nitrates -ruling* it appears that the ND could have the potential to become the primary source of legally forceful obligations to *de facto* effectively address agricultural nitrates pollution and achieve sufficient improvements in the aquatic environment, thus rectifying some of the shortcomings produced by the lenient exemption regime under the WFD (and the MSFD).

4.3 Coherence of the instruments

In addition to analysing the alignment across the objectives of the policies, the coherence assessment must also address the set of policy instruments set out in the policies. As established already in section 3.3, the MSFD and the WFD employ a variety of instruments in pursuit of meeting their objectives. The main instruments addressing agricultural water pollution in the ND, the WFD and the MSFD include strategic planning (programmes of measures under WFD Art 11 and MSFD Art 13, nitrates action programs under ND Art 5) that forms the general framework for putting in place measures on agricultural pollution. The specific instrument – type of a measure – for steering towards reducing nutrient loading is setting general binding rules for agricultural activities causing nutrient pollution (WFD Art 10, ND Annex III and Art 4 + Annex II). In this section, the coherence of the planning instruments will be analysed first, followed by an assessment of the general binding rules.

The strategic planning instruments of the WFD and the MSFD – the river basin management plans, marine strategies and the programmes of measures – are highly coherent. Drawing up management plans and programmes of measures in both directives is based on a comprehensive analysis of the state of the waters and marine areas and the predominant pressures significantly

affecting the status of them, judged against the good status objectives in the directives (WFD Art 5(1), 11(1), MSFD 5(2), 8(1), 10(1) and 13(1)). Accordingly, if agricultural nutrient pollution is detected to constitute a significant pressure through eutrophication impacts, an obligation to address agricultural pollution in the programmes of measures is triggered under both directives. The timeframes for conducting the analyses and adopting programmes of measures are in sync, following the same six-year management cycles for which programmes of measures are adopted; currently, the river basin management plans and marine strategies are in place for the period of 2022–2027.

Furthermore, the MSFD prescribes that water management must be integrated in the assessment of marine waters, that the environmental targets for marine strategies need to be compatible with the WFD's water management objectives and that the programmes of measures under the MSFD must be integrated with the WFD's water management measures, see art. 8(2), 10(1) and 13(2) MSFD (Puharinen and Belinskij, 2023). This means that with regard to the substance of the plans particularly in relation to land-based pollution such as agricultural nutrient pollution, the plans and programmes can be made highly coherent. Yet while the marine strategies and programmes of measures are drafted for the entire marine area, the WFD's river basin management plans and programmes of measures are adopted for river basin districts, specific areas within Member States designated based on hydrological boundaries that form operational units for implementing the Directive's river basin management planning. However, as was already explained in relation to the objectives, this difference of geographical scales of the management regimes does not mean incoherence but rather provides a spectrum of management perspectives capable of addressing different aspects of the challenge.

At the outset, the ND's planning instrument – adopting actions plans for the designated nitrates vulnerable areas (Arts 3(1) and 5(1)) – is not explicitly harmonised with the WFD's and the MSFD's planning instruments with regard to procedural planning aspects. Depending on the choices made by the Member States, action plans may be adopted for delimited nitrates vulnerable zones or parts of such zones (Art 5(1)), the Member State may draw up only one action program to apply in all vulnerable zones in their territory (Art 5(2)), or they may exempt from the requirement to designate vulnerable zones altogether and apply action programs in their entire territory (Art 3(5)). The choices made by the Member States in this regard determine how the action programs fit within the management scales of the WFD and the MSFD. Furthermore, the action programs are drawn up and updated in four-year cycles (Art 4(4) and (5)), which does not match the six-year management cycle under the WFD and the MSFD and thus may complicate planning of measures coherently under all plans.

Regarding substantive aspects, the instrumentation of the directive forms more coherent whole. The ND's threshold for taking action – that is, designating NVZs and drawing up action programs and measures – is triggered if the concentration of nitrates exceeds 50 mg/l or if the receiving water body is at risk of becoming eutrophic, which generally matches the WFD's and the MSFD's thresholds for addressing pressures, such as agricultural pollution, that are liable of causing deterioration in the waters or that hinder the achievement of good status.

Furthermore, as the WFD and the MSFD establish rather general frames for action by the Member States, the ND, which provides specific measures to address agricultural pollution in its Annex III, can be seen to specify and reinforce the actions required from the Member States. The ND includes concrete mandatory measures that the Member States need to include and operationalise in the context of the action programs to reduce agricultural nitrates pollution (Article 5(4)(a)). These measures are listed in Annex III of the Directive and they include putting in place rules that, for instance, prohibit the land application of certain types of fertilizer during certain periods, restrict the maximum amount of livestock manure applied to the land each year to 170 kg N per hectare, and lay down requirements for the capacity of storage vessels for livestock manure (ND Annex III, section 1 paras 1 and 2, section 2). In this vein, the ND's measures are important concrete requirements with regards to the GD's goals on agriculture, particularly those of reducing the use of fertilisers and reducing nutrient losses. Yet, a pertinent problem in the implementation of the ND and its action programs has been that the rules laid down by the Member States pursuant to Annex III have not been strict enough to effectively reduce inputs of nutrients (European Court of Auditors, 2016). Furthermore, as the ND focuses on nitrates, it does not impose limits on applications of phosphorus; when eutrophication and water status degradation is triggered by phosphorus, applying a nitrate action programme will not necessarily solve the problem (*ibid.*).

Furthermore, the ND's requirement to establish codes of good agricultural practices applies generally in the territory of Member States to establish a general level of protection against pollution (Art 4(1)). These codes should include, if deemed relevant, provisions on i.a. periods when the land application of fertilizer is inappropriate, land application of fertilizer to steeply sloping ground, the conditions for land application of fertiliser near water courses, and the capacity and construction of storage vessels for livestock manures (Annex II, section A). Moreover, Member States may choose to include additionally provisions related to for instance provisions on land use management, including the use of crop rotation systems and the proportion of the land area devoted to permanent crops, the maintenance of a minimum quantity of vegetation cover during (rainy) periods and establishment of fertilizer plans on a farm-by-farm basis and the keeping of records on fertilizer use (Annex II, section B). Yet, while the codes may thus provide a versatile and comprehensive mix of measures for reducing agricultural pollution, their major flaw is that the ND only provides that they are to be implemented by farmers on a voluntary basis, which decreases their forcefulness and their steering capacity in effectively controlling pollution.

Regarding coherence of specific measures in the ND and the strategic management planning regimes, the MSFD, firstly, is quite ambivalent in addressing agricultural pollution in the marine waters. According to the MSFD, Member States must set environmental targets with due regard for pressures stemming from nutrients. These targets may set out either general overall reductions in nutrients or more detailed, sector- or region-specific objectives that then form the basis for the programmes of measures (Art 13(1)). The MSFD is extremely flexible in terms of the specific management action towards realizing its goals. Member States also have the freedom to compile programmes of measures for marine strategies from any measures they deem most suitable for reaching the environmental targets; Annex VI of the MSFD lists

the types of measures that can be included in the programmes, including input controls, economic incentives, mitigation and remediation, but does not require Member States to employ specific measures in response to any given pressure. The MSFD however requires that relevant measures required under several pieces of EU law are integrated in the marine strategies (Art 13(2)); yet, the ND is not listed as one of them and thus, the measures under the ND do not need to be integrated in the programmes of measures for marine strategies. The MSFD's setting has the effect that the Member States efforts in managing pressures, including agricultural nutrient pollution, are not structured in a clear and specific way in the Directive, which undermines the steering effect and the forcefulness of the Directive in addressing the pressures in an effective way, as nothing prevents Member States from, for instance, applying only voluntary-based measures or other weak instruments.

The WFD, in turn, contains more specific regulation on measures addressing different pressures and contains even explicit linkages to the ND; maybe as it forms the principal instrument for dealing with land-based sources of water pollution. The Directive's objectives are to be reached through compilation and implementation of programmes of measures for water management, with these to include what are designated as mandatory basic measures as well as supplementary measures for addressing the key environmental pressures (Art 11(1) and (2)). The WFD stipulates that the measures taken under the ND form mandatory minimum requirements for the WFD's programmes of measures (Art 10 and 11(3)(a)); this implies that the ND's action programs form priority action in addressing agricultural nitrates pollution in the areas found particularly vulnerable in that respect, and the WFD's regime may provide supplementary management insights. This logic is specified further in Art 10 of the WFD, which requires Member States to operationalise a combined approach for diffuse pollution. This entails, a priori, establishing controls employing best environmental practices set out in other EU legislation, such as the ND (Art 10(2)). In turn, in cases where achieving the WFD's objectives necessitates stricter conditions than are prescribed in other EU directives, the WFD requires Member States to set more stringent emission controls in implementing those directives (Art 10(3)). This means that if the application of the ND's regime, as it is provided in that Directive, is not enough to curb agricultural pollution in line with reaching the WFD's objectives in surface waters, the WFD's objectives have the legal force to determine and shape the ND's implementation to require more stringent measures. Moreover, supplementary measures are to be included in the WFD's programmes of measures if applying the ND's measures to their fullest potential is not enough (WFD Art 11(4)).

However, in its caselaw, the CJEU appears to be opinion that the system for protecting waters from pollution from livestock effluent at the Community level is purely based on the ND and not on other water directives. For example, in the recent German nitrates -case the WFD's objectives and related obligations to address nutrient pollution were not mentioned; instead, the Member States obligations related to matter falling under the ND were explored solely

based on the objectives and provisions of the ND.²⁷ Moreover, it is notable that the MSFD does not even mention the ND or require including the measures taken under the ND in the programmes of measures for marine strategies, making it further unlikely that the MSFD could influence the ND's regime any better than the WFD. This silo-approach to these instruments by the Court does not actively promote coherence in dealing with a core problem common to all three policies. Nevertheless, because the objectives of all directives are so well aligned, this may not be a major coherence problem in practical implementation's context.

4.4 Conclusions

As can be seen from the analysis above, the WFD, the MSFD and the ND form a multifaceted legal cluster addressing agricultural nutrient pollution and its eutrophication effects in the aquatic environment. The objectives of the policies target different geographical scale and have slightly different focus – the WFD and the MSFD assessing functioning of the ecosystems and the ND on the amount and impact of nitrates inputs – but they are coherent in their substance regarding the main problem. The same goes for the instruments in the policies, as the WFD and the MSFD provide more general management frameworks for agricultural nutrient inputs, focusing on the design on national policy responses, while the ND provides more concrete and specific requirements for measures to be taken by the Member States in addressing and controlling inputs of nitrates in the waters. Furthermore, the assessment shows that the directives provide opportunities for the Member States to actively seek synergetic approach to their implementation, including deliberating and establishing the ND's nitrates vulnerable zones and areas of application of the action programs based on the geographical scopes of the WFD or the MSFD or any needs for regional differentiation detected under the implementation of river basin management planning or marine strategies.

In sum, the conclusion of the coherence assessment thus is that there are no major problems of incoherence or fragmentation within the cluster. There are only minor coherence issues, such as the ND's lack of objectives and regulation on phosphorus and the lack of deadline for achieving its objectives. By taking a synergetic and coherence-seeking approach to interpretation, the objectives and instruments can form a coherent and mutually reinforcing regime providing various instruments for tackling the problem of agriculture induced nutrient pollution and eutrophication.

However, the major challenge for this combined regime in legally operationalising the Green Deal's objectives on agricultural pollution is the continued lack of effectiveness and capacity to steer Member States in taking action to actually reduce nutrient pollution from agriculture (European Court of Auditors, 2016). All instruments in the cluster have continuously suffered from insufficient rigor in implementation by the Member States, with the effect that their

²⁷ C-543/16. This appears to be a continuation of an interpretative tradition by the Court. See case C-121/03 *Commission v Spain* ECLI:EU:C:2005:512 in relation to old groundwater directive (80/68/EEC); Antoinette Hilderling, Andrea M. Keessen & Helena F.M.W. van Rijswijk, 'Tackling pollution of the Mediterranean Sea from land-based sources by an integrated ecosystem approach and the use of the combined international and European legal regimes'. *Utrecht Law Review* Vol 5(1) (2009), p. 80–100, at 93.

objectives are far from being realised and agricultural pollution has not been reduced significantly at the European scale (ibid.). With regards to the WFD and the MSFD, while their objectives entail legal obligations for Member States to deliver improvements in the environmental conditions, the flexibilities in the form of obligations (the MSFD's best effort obligations) and exemptions (the WFD's flexible exemptions allowing exclusion of measures on economic and technical grounds) have provided wide margin of discretion to not address agricultural pollution effectively. With regard to the ND, the Directive has set clear requirements on the designation of vulnerable zones, drawing up action plans and adopting measures (Annex III) to reduce nitrates runoff, but has suffered from failures of Member States to set strict enough requirements to tackle the problem and over-reliance on voluntary-based measures. However, new interpretations of the ND's objectives and obligations championed particularly in the German nitrates -case by the CJEU may reinforce the directive on these aspects, or even force the Member States to act on agricultural nitrates pollution in the event that the failures to reach the objectives of the WFD and the MSFD are under exemption.

5 Common Agriculture Policy and zero pollution

5.1 Introduction

The Common Agriculture Policy (CAP) is the agricultural policy as well as one of the oldest and the most expensive policy in the EU. The policy was launched already in 1962 with the current policy in force for the period 2023-2027. The overall policy is formulated in Regulation (EU) 2021/2115 establishing rules on support for strategic plans to be drawn up by Member States under the common agricultural policy (CAP) and the policy is financed through the European Agricultural Guarantee Fund (EAGF) and by the European Agricultural Fund for Rural Development (EAFRD).

The policy has three general objectives as prescribed in article 5:

- a) to foster a smart, competitive, resilient and diversified agricultural sector ensuring long-term food security;
- b) to support and strengthen environmental protection, including biodiversity, and climate action and to contribute to achieving the environmental and climate-related objectives of the Union, including its commitments under the Paris Agreement;
- c) to strengthen the socio-economic fabric of rural areas.

As the policy is not mainly environmentally focused, the policy includes objectives concerning other subjects than the environment and objectives that the achievement of will or might result in degradation of the environment. The objectives of CAP are further defined in ten specific objectives, as formulated in article 6d-f of the regulation, of which three directly concern the environment and climate.

- to contribute to climate change mitigation and adaptation, including by reducing greenhouse gas emissions and enhancing carbon sequestration, as well as to promote sustainable energy;
- to foster sustainable development and efficient management of natural resources such as water, soil and air, including by reducing chemical dependency;
- to contribute to halting and reversing biodiversity loss, enhance ecosystem services and preserve habitats and landscapes;

The three specific objectives each concern one of the EGD policy streams. These aspects are worked into the policy instruments of the policy. In practice, however, CAP is based on incentives that drive for more land being used for agriculture, which in itself is in direct conflict with biodiversity, climate change and environmental quality goals. This makes the policy cross-cutting and the achievement of certain objectives might lead to negative synergy in the achievement of others.

The first specific objective concerns climate change, the second pollution and the third biodiversity. The climate policy stream will exclusively be analysed in the cluster “Renewable energy – offshore wind power” and will not be part of the analysis of CAP. Further, the

biodiversity objective is focused on biodiversity on land where the impact indicators for the objective focuses on inter alia farmland birds, wild pollinators, and crop diversity. As such, the following analysis will focus on the coherence between CAP and the zero-pollution policy stream. Further, the analysis will focus on nutrient pollution. The specific objective of CAP concerning effective management of natural resources includes indicators for several recipients (air, ground, water) and pressures (nitrates, nutrients, ammonia and pesticides). Some of these are naturally not relevant for the marine environment and the remaining will be narrowed down further to focus on one specific coherence issue – the pollution of nutrients.

The EU has for a long time had extensive regulation to protect its waters. However, it was first when the WFD was introduced in 2000 that the union established a comprehensive and cohesive approach to water protection in the EU. The WFD is one of the EU environmental acts that has had and will have the most far-reaching implications for environmental protection and natural resource management in the MS (Langlet and Mahmoudi, 2016). WFD also serves the EU and its member states to fulfil the obligations under several international agreements, among them the Helsinki Convention, the OSPAR Convention and the Barcelona Convention.

The WFD obliges MS to protect inland surface, transitional, coastal, and groundwater bodies, emphasising the ecological quality of waters and prioritising it alongside sustainable water use to reach the overall objective of, at least, good status for all water bodies by 2015, or 2027 at latest. For non-modified surface waters, good status means the achievement of both good chemical status and good ecological status. Good chemical status is achieved when concentrations of pollutants do not exceed the environmental quality standards set in the Environmental Quality Standards Directive (EQSD), while ecological status is determined by the biological quality elements, set out in annex V of the WFD, using the one out – all out principle where the status is determined by the worst element status.

The WFD mandates that MS prevent further water deterioration, promote sustainable use, reduce pollutants, and mitigate the effects of floods and droughts. This is achieved using management plans and programmes of measures as well as legal requirements to be applied for individual projects. The River Basin Management Programmes (RBMPs) and Programmes of Measures (PoMs) are six-year plans set out to protect and, where necessary, restore water bodies to reach good status, and to prevent deterioration. This includes establishing the environmental status and defining the environmental objectives as well as determining measures to be taken and how to monitor the status during the period. The first RBMPs were to be established by 2009 and the first PoMs operational by 2012. Furthermore, as explained in chapter 3, the objectives in the WFD are binding in nature and beyond the establishment and implementation of RBMPs and PoMs.

5.2 Coherence of objectives

The CAP has a long history as a central legislation in the EU. Historically, the agricultural policy in the EU has been oriented towards the objectives of food security and securing the farmers' income, creating incentives to increase production through price and market intervention. This contributed to a strong intensification and regional concentration of

agricultural activities and partly even to overproduction (Vogeler, 2021). Environmental objectives have historically not been of significance for the policy.

In 1992, through the so-called MacSharry reform, the first major shift in this orientation was implemented. The emphasis on price and market intervention was shifted towards direct income payments. As the policy also introduced environmental objectives, the payments were partly conditional on environmental requirements. To be eligible for the direct income payments, larger farms had to take land out of production. The reform also included agri-environment measures as an accompanying measure (Alons, 2017). Although the policy change introduced new, market-liberalizing policy instruments, the underlying goals of the CAP remained the same (Skogstad, 1998). Further reforms have since been introduced that have either environmental objectives or could have positive environmental effects (Alons, 2017).

Today the CAP includes a general objective to support and strengthen environmental protection and three specific objectives of direct environmental concern: climate change mitigation, sustainable development and efficient management of natural resources and halting and reversing biodiversity loss. As noted above, the main objective that concerns the marine environment is the efficient management of natural resources as it includes water. In accordance with the preamble, the current policy emphasis enhanced subsidiarity where the EU should set the basic policy parameters, while Member States are set to bear greater responsibility as to how they meet objectives and achieve targets.

In accordance with article 7, the achievement of the objectives is assessed on the basis of common indicators related to output, result, impact and context which are set out in Annex I. The specific objective *to foster sustainable development and efficient management of natural resources such as water, soil and air, including by reducing chemical dependency* has six impact indicators, with impact indicator I.15 - *Improving water quality: Gross nutrient balance on agricultural land* focusing on nutrient emissions from farms to water. These are complemented by result indicators where mainly R.21^{PR} *Protecting water quality: Share of utilised agricultural area (UAA) under supported commitments for the quality of water bodies*, R.22^{PR} *Sustainable nutrient management: Share of utilised agricultural area (UAA) under supported commitments related to improved nutrient management* and R.26 *Investments related to natural resources: Share of farms benefitting from CAP productive and non-productive investment support related to care for the natural resources*.

The CAP objectives do not refer to the WFD or any other environmental directives directly nor are there any specific provisions in the policy referring to the WFD. However, the preamble reiterates the potential of CAP to deliver added value on the environment and to reinforce its synergies with the financing of investments in nature and biodiversity, with the WFD being one of the environmental directives named (preamble 75). As for the WFD, the policy does not refer to the CAP or the agricultural sector specifically in its objectives. However, the preamble points out agriculture as a policy sector that needs further for integration of protection and sustainable management of water.

5.2.1 The scope of the objectives

As a sector policy, the definition of the scope in CAP differs quite substantially from the environmental directives. It is applicable for agricultural activities and the geographical scope is set in accordance with the territorial scope of the treaties as defined in Article 52 of the Treaty on European Union in conjunction with Articles 349 and 355 of the Treaty on the Functioning of the European Union (TFEU). Agricultural activities are to be performed in agricultural areas which includes arable land, permanent crops and permanent grassland as defined in article 4(3). Agricultural areas are to be defined by the Member States in their CAP Strategic Plans. The geographical scope of activities open for funding are thus limited to land-based activities, but effects in regard to economic, environmental and social spheres have no defined limits.

The agricultural pollution directly concerns the Zero Pollution Action Plan (see also chapter 4). The overall aim is to reduce pollution to levels that are no longer considered harmful to human health and ecosystems. The plan also has a specific objective that immediately concerns agriculture that aims to reduce nutrient losses by 50 per cent. For this to be achieved, the sector policies must achieve an effective legislation for this pressure.

The CAP does have a specific objective that does mention water as a natural resource that should be efficiently managed, but it does not have a specific objective, indicator or target that concerns marine waters specifically. In fact, the marine environment is not specifically mentioned in the overall policy at all. This does not entail that marine waters are outside the scope of the objectives but may affect the policy's and the national implementation's focus. This can be seen in the omission of marine biodiversity or the lack of any references to the MSFD in the policy despite it being a large pressure on the marine environment. The WFD, the HD and the BD are not referred to in the CAP objectives but are referred to throughout the policy and included in the indicators.

The scope overlaps with that of the WFD, BD and HD insofar as the same type of activities and even the same aspects of them can be subject to regulation in both. For marine waters, this concerns the obligations of the WFD and in many cases the obligation of the CAP is defined through references to the WFD.

5.2.2 Timeframe for the achievement of the objectives

The CAP does not have a specific timeframe for the achievement of the objectives. However, the general objectives do reference the policy's contribution to the implementation of the 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development. The support financed by the EAGF and the EAFRD is set for a certain period of time, the so-called CAP Strategic Plan period. The current CAP Strategic Plan period covers the period from 1 January 2023 to 31 December 2027. During 2021 and 2022 transitional regulation was applied and the current CAP also includes a two-year transition period requiring the financial resources to be used by 31 December 2029. Despite the different length and timing of the cycles for WFD and CAP, the end date of the current CAP Strategic Plan period and the third cycle of RBMPs both end on 31 December

2027, allowing for certain synergies in planning. As the cycles differ in length, this will not be the case for the coming cycles.

5.2.3 Legal impacts of the objectives

As the CAP uses regulation as chosen legal act, the legal impacts of the objectives differ quite substantially from those of the directives such as the WFD. Directives create a legal obligation for the Member States regarding the results to be achieved, while regulations instead are directly applicable (art. 288 TFEU). For Member States, it means that they are not allowed to introduce national legislation that alter, breach, or obscure the direct effect of the regulation. A Member State may adopt legislation to implement the regulation and at times it is required for a Member State to do so, either through an explicit requirement of national implementation in the regulation or if necessitated for the regulation to guarantee the application and effectiveness. In such cases, the objectives are of importance to determine that national implementing measures does not compromise the objectives of the policy.

As the policy's objectives do not prescribe an obligation for the Member States, the legal obligation for the Member States is instead specified in the policy instruments. This is mainly achieved through the formulation of strategic plans, which gives the Member State access to the CAP funding, and the implementation of it. As such, for a Member State to be in compliance with the CAP, in principle it does not need to meet an obligation of result or even an obligation of best effort. Instead, it needs to be in compliance with the legal instruments of the policy.

5.3 Coherence of legal instruments

The CAP establishes general and specific objectives for the agricultural sector in the EU. To pursue these objectives, the EU has set up financial arrangements through two funds: European Agricultural Guarantee Fund (EAGF) and the European Agricultural Fund for Rural Development (EAFRD), both lead by DG AGRI. To access the funding, the Member States are required to set up CAP Strategic Plans which set targets, specify conditions for interventions and allocate financial resources, according to the specific objectives and identified needs. When drafting their CAP Strategic Plans, Member States also had to explain how different elements in their plans will be consistent with and contribute towards achieving the EU-level targets set in the EGD, indicating also optional non-binding targets, preferably by setting non-binding national targets (Ecorys, Metis, and Agrosynergy, 2023).

The EAGF has a budget for the current CAP Strategic Planning period of € 291.09 billion (current prices). According to article 85 of the CAP, the EAGF finances interventions related to direct payments and interventions in certain sectors. The EAFRD on the other hand has a budget of € 95.51 billion and shall finance the intervention for rural development, and technical assistance at the initiative of the Member States. Eco-schemes are financed through direct payments. Accessing the funds is dependent on conditionality criteria that are minimal requirements every agricultural producer must meet. Further, each fund has a specific instrument to help integrate EU water policy objectives into CAP – EAGF through eco-scheme direct payments and EAFRD.

Agricultural activities may also be addressed in the national implementation of the WFD through the RBMPs. As a diffuse source of pollution, it is to be addressed in the RBMP and measures must be introduced. These may affect farmers and the effects differ between farmers depending on location.

5.3.1 Legal instruments that address water quality in the CAP

The current CAP has three different legal instruments that can directly affect the nutrient emissions from agriculture to coastal or marine waters – conditionality criteria, eco-schemes and agri-environment-climate measures (AECM). These will be introduced in detail below and followed by a coherence analysis.

Conditionality

Conditionality criteria are the minimal requirements that every agricultural producer must meet to be eligible for funding. These criteria include statutory management requirements (SMRs), which apply to all farmers whether or not they receive support, and good agricultural and environmental conditions (GAECs). Farmers that are found violating the conditions will have their support from CAP reduced and possibly face other penalties. Rules on SMRs and GAECs are specified in Annex III of the CAP.

The SMRs include a set of legally binding rules on public, animal and plant health, animal welfare, and the environment that the farmers need to adhere to. For the environment, this includes the Nature Directives, the ND and the WFD. For the WFD, the requirements refer to basic measures to be included by the Member States in the programme of measures. This entails the controls over the abstraction of fresh surface water and groundwater, and impoundment of fresh surface water and measures to prevent or control the input for diffuse sources liable to cause pollution as regards mandatory requirements to control diffuse sources of pollution by phosphates (see article 11(e) and (h) of the WFD). The GAEC for water consists of establishment of buffer strips along water courses with the main objective of protection of river courses against pollution and run-off (GAEC 4).

Eco-schemes

Eco-schemes is a legal instrument that was introduced in the current CAP. Article 16 of the CAP identifies the types of intervention in the form of direct payments and these types of interventions are financed through the EAGF. Article 16.2(d) includes schemes for the climate, the environment and animal welfare as one of the decoupled direct payments. Direct payments are granted to active farmers, either individuals or companies, who are engaged in at least a minimum level of agricultural activity as defined by the CAP Strategic Plan. Farmers who want to claim direct payments need to apply every year and comply with a number of rules. The EU contribution for eco-schemes is € 44,71 billion, which is 15 % of the total public expenditure and 23.64 % of the total direct payments (European Commission, 2023a and European Parliament, 2023).

Article 31 lays down the rules for eco-schemes. It states that Member States shall establish, and provide support for, voluntary schemes for the climate, the environment and animal welfare

and these schemes are to support active farmers or groups of active farmers who make commitments to observe agricultural practices beneficial for the climate, the environment and animal welfare and combatting antimicrobial resistance. Each eco-scheme shall in principle cover at least two areas of actions. To be provided payment, commitments shall go beyond the conditionality for payments as established by the Member State in the CAP Strategic Plan. As such, eco-schemes should not pay for basic agronomic practices and should not be a top-up of basic income support for all farmers but exist to reward farmers doing more for the environment than the minimum requirements.

Member States must demonstrate how the agricultural practices committed under eco-schemes respond to the needs and be evaluated through a SWOT analysis based on the current situation of the area covered by the CAP Strategic Plan and shall comprise, for each specific objective. For the analysis of the environmental specific objectives, the SWOT analysis shall take into account the national environmental and climate plans emanating from the legislative acts listed in Annex XIII which includes the WFD. The intervention strategy shall demonstrate the consistency of the strategy and the complementarity of interventions across the specific objectives and use a rating or scoring system or any other appropriate methodology to ensure the effectiveness and efficiency of the eco-schemes to deliver on the targets set. Member States must also ensure that the eco-scheme interventions are consistent with the agri-environmental and climate schemes for rural development under article 70.

The European Commission has issued broad guidelines for agricultural practices that can be supported under eco-schemes. In principle, to be supported by eco-schemes agricultural activities should:

- cover activities related to climate, environment, animal welfare and antimicrobial resistance
- be defined on the basis of the needs and priorities identified at national/regional levels in their CAP strategic plans
- their level of ambition has to go beyond the requirements and obligations set by conditionality
- contribute to reaching the EU Green Deal targets

The Commission has also published a list of potential agricultural practices that can be supported by eco-schemes. The design of the eco-schemes is to be decided by the Member States as long as the eco-schemes reward farmers for implementing climate and environmentally friendly agricultural practices. However, eco-schemes will mainly rely on prohibited and/or required farming practices rather than on results and a fortiori impacts (Guyomard et. al., 2023).

Interventions for rural development

The EAFRD provides support to rural areas, and for that it contains funding for so-called agri-environment-climate measures (AECMs). AECMs are voluntary measures in the form of commitments on which there are incentives attached, compensating farmers for income losses

deriving from the adoption of environment-friendly practices. The funding is distributed through rural development programmes (RDP) that are part of the CAP Strategic Plans. The programmes are prepared on a national or regional basis and must work towards specific targets relating to the EU's rural development objectives. At least 30% of funding for each RDP must be dedicated to measures relevant for the environment and climate change and the funding is co-financed by national budgets. The funding is mainly channelled through grants and annual payments to farmers who switch towards more environmentally friendly practices.

The conditions of the AECMs are further specified in article 70. Member States are only allowed to provide payments for commitments that go beyond the conditionality criteria for SMRs and GAECs and mandatory requirements established by national and Union law. The commitments must also be different from those which are granted eco-scheme payments. Commitments are to be undertaken for a period of five to seven years. AECMs can support measures similar to eco-schemes but potentially more ambitious farm practices (Ecorys, Metis, and Agrosynergy, 2023). Within this framework, the Member States are given considerable leeway in determining their needs, selecting measures and allocating funds.

In accordance with article 72, CAP also may grant compensation-based payments for all or part of the additional costs and income foregone related to the requirements from the WFD and the nature directives. Payments may be granted only to area-specific disadvantages resulting from certain mandatory requirements. When determining areas with disadvantages related to the WFD, Member States may include agricultural areas included in RBMPs. Such payments are limited to compensate beneficiaries for all or part of the additional costs and income foregone related to the area-specific disadvantages and in respect to the WFD disadvantages resulting from requirements that go beyond the relevant statutory management requirements.

The coherence of CAP legal instruments and WFD

The policy instruments in CAP introduces economic incentives for farmers to adhere to minimum environmental standards and even go beyond those by supporting innovative and ambitious management. For water pollution, CAP is potentially a very effective legal instrument to target the diffuse nutrient pollution into marine waters where the WFD in itself is unable to provide sufficient protection. The increased allocation of funding to environmental and climate commitments further increases the CAP's potential to support the pollution objectives rather than work against them. The application of the funding also bears several connections to the WFD, and funding can be allocated both to introduce commitments to help comply to the WFD requirements and to aid farmers in the transition.

There are, however, several factors that will undermine or risk the policy's coherence with the WFD. The first and foremost is that funds are not only allocated for activities that are aimed at protection, nor is its objective to do so. A significant portion of the funds are aimed at maintaining or expanding activities. Run-off and leaching of nutrients from fertilisation practices in agriculture is one of the main pressures on water quality and with large production comes increased pressure. The legal instruments of CAP are not ecosystem based insofar as

funding for agricultural activities does not take into account the status of the recipient water body.

The effectiveness of CAP as a legal instrument to aid the achievement of good status for all water bodies is dependent on efficient and effective national implementation. There is considerable leeway for Member States in programming the interventions, i.e. determining their needs, selecting measures and allocating funds. A notable difference is seen in the national Strategic Plans and there is a risk that the results will greatly vary between Member States as a result. Further, the eco-schemes and AECMs are mandatory for the Member States, but optional for farmers. As a legal instrument, it lacks legal bindingness for the farmers and the effectiveness will also be dependent on its ability to affect key activities. The tactic of paying polluters extra for compliance with environmental standards has in earlier audits been noted as a step away from the polluter pays principle. This issue persists in the current CAP. A significant number of payments under rural development are not tied to cross-compliance and as a result, a farmer who pollutes will continue to receive these payments without any reduction (European Court of Auditors, 2014).

In summary, the legal instruments of CAP include economic incentives towards reducing nutrient pollution that goes further than the bare minimum measures of the WFD and other environmental directives while also including legal instruments that will maintain or increase the pressure from the sector. The coherence of CAP with the WFD and other environmental directives will be highly dependent on the national strategic plans and follow-through.

5.3.2 Agricultural activities in the RBMPs

Agricultural activities are also regulated in the WFD. The pollution from agriculture is the most significant of the so-called diffuse pollutions, one of the main significant pressures on surface water bodies and more so than point-source pollutions (European Environment Agency, 2018). At the same time, the evaluations of the first and second round of RBMPs has pointed out that sources of nutrients from agricultural sources is a problem that consists, especially in regions with intensive agricultural activities (Wiering et. al. 2020).

The WFD requires the identification of significant pressures, including diffuse sources of pollution. Significant in this context means that the pressure contributes to an impact that may result in failing to meet the requirements of the environmental objectives. If a water body is not in good status, the development of a targeted programme of measures to handle the pressures is to be developed. There is a wide range of measures that are taken and for agriculture encouraging best practice measures in agriculture to reduce nutrient pollution is the most significant one (European Environment Agency, 2018). As noted above, CAP enables Member States to compensate farmers in full or partly area-specific disadvantages resulting from certain mandatory requirements.

5.4 Conclusion

The Common Agriculture Policy (CAP) is one of the oldest and most expensive policies of the EU. At its core, it has existed to support agricultural production, ensure food security, and promote rural development. At the same time, agricultural production has been one of the main pressures on both our water quality and quantity. While the CAP includes an objective to foster sustainable development and efficient management of natural resources such as water, the main policy for water quality is the Water Framework Directive (WFD). To legally operationalise the European Green Deal objectives of zero pollution from the agricultural production to the marine environment, a high level of coherence between the CAP and the WFD is essential. Tackling diffuse pollution from agriculture remains a key challenge for governments seeking to implement the WFD.

Implementation of the WFD has been significantly delayed due to insufficient integration of environmental objectives in sectoral policies. This is no different for the agricultural sector. While there are environmental objectives in the new CAP, these are added as an outer logic of the already existing policy. This has led to the introduction of legal instruments to address nutrient pollution within the CAP framework. However, the objectives are to a large extent contradictory as objectives on agricultural productivity and environmental production do not relate to each other. There are also no clear linkages between the two policy's objectives. The CAP and the WFD risk ending up working against each other rather than working in a harmonized way.

Agricultural pollution has not been reduced significantly at the European scale. Legally operationalising the Green Deal's objectives on agricultural pollution continues to be a challenge due to the continued lack of effectiveness and capacity to steer Member States in acting to actually reduce nutrient pollution from agriculture. Properly addressing nutrient pollution in the RBMPs has proven to be difficult in the previous cycles of the WFD and such issues can be expected to persist. The success of nutrient mitigation instead becomes heavily reliable of efficient national implementation rather than a guarantee stemming from EU policies. The CAP includes eco-schemes and AECMs to promote sustainable agriculture but the allocation of these will vary greatly across the different Member States and both the prioritisation and effectiveness of implementation in regards to nutrient pollution from agriculture to waters will differ substantially.

The achievement of high level of coherence between CAP and WFD is thus heavily dependent on the national implementation of these policies. Without an effective national implementation, the targets for zero pollution are not going to be met. This creates an uncertainty of the achievement of the zero pollution objectives on an EU level and in certain regards relies on the Member States for the achievement of the concerned EGD objectives.

6 Fisheries and biodiversity

6.1 Introduction

The Common Fisheries Policy (CFP) provides rules for the sustainable management of fishing fleets, conservation of fish stocks, and aquaculture. The regulation of fisheries in EU was originally part of the Common Agricultural Policy (CAP) but featured mainly rules on market organization. It wasn't until the CFP was formally established in 1983. The conservation of marine biological resources has since become an exclusive competence of the Union in accordance with article 3 of the Treaty of the Functioning of the European Union (TFEU) and agriculture and fisheries, excluding the conservation of marine biological resources, are shared competences in accordance with article 4 of the same treaty. In article 38 of the same treaty, it is established that the Union shall define and implement a common agriculture and fisheries policy, where the same objectives and rules on functioning as for the agricultural products are extended to the products of fisheries.

The regulation of fisheries is grounded in international law. The United Nations Convention on the Law of the Sea (UNCLOS) codifies the legal framework for ocean space. This includes the jurisdictional zones in the waters that determines the limits of EU waters (for example, the MSFD is applicable to internal waters, territorial sea, exclusive economic zone, and the continental shelf, including the areas beyond 200 nautical miles). The extension of the legislation also goes beyond the EU waters as it has applicability also for EU flagged vessels. Around 10 % of the catches are made under fisheries agreements with countries outside the EU and another 10 % are made on the high seas (European Commission, n.d.).

The CFP covers two defined areas: (1) the conservation of marine biological resources and the management of fisheries and fleets exploiting such resources and (2) in relation to measures on markets and financial measures in support of the implementation of the CFP: fresh water biological resources, aquaculture, and the processing and marketing of fisheries and aquaculture products. The policy is established in the basic regulation of CFP (1380/2013/EU) which lays down inter alia core principles and objectives of the policy. The CFP is further regulated through a complex set of regulations, focusing on inter alia quotas, the European Maritime, Fisheries and Aquaculture Fund (EMFAF) and specific rules on fishing practices. The legislation is almost exclusively in the form of regulations which creates a heavily harmonised legislation without national legal acts. As fisheries are a shared competence, unregulated areas in the legislation, such as certain species, are still up to the member states to regulate.

Fishing activities are one of the major threats for marine biodiversity due to, for example, the overexploitation of stocks, by-catch and damage caused by the fishing practices. While there are environmentally protective elements of the CFP, the inner logic of the policy concerns production and market measures. The policy covers resource management and market measures, mainly to support the industry and boost the market. While resource management has clear overlaps with environmental protection, there are also differences in protection mainly for further exploitation and the protection of a natural environment. Further, the policy

has historically focused on creating a stable industry and market, while the more restrictive measures have been added more recently. The regulation focusing on the protection of the marine species and their habitats can instead mainly be found in the HD, the WFD and the MSFD.

The three directives set objectives for a minimum standard of environmental protection to be achieved by the Member States. From the outset, the three directives and CFP are managing the same marine spaces with conflicting objectives which creates initial coherence challenges. Further, they are regulating the marine resources with different forms of legislations, through different forms of legal instruments and legal obligations and in different timelines. In an effort to achieve a more consistent implementation of the EU's environmental policy and the common fisheries policy, the Commission adopted the EU Action Plan: Protecting and restoring marine ecosystems for sustainable and resilient fisheries. The Action Plan contains calls to the Member States for action and promises of actions from the Commission for protection and restoration of marine areas.

When the fisheries policy was to be updated, concern for the species and ecosystems were a recurrent and prioritised aspect in the decision-making process (Ribeiro, 2017). The policy contains several objectives with direct or indirect goals of protecting biodiversity, but also a specific coherence objective that states that the CFP “be coherent with the Union environmental legislation, in particular with the objective of achieving a good environmental status by 2020 as set out in Article 1(1) of Directive 2008/56/EC, as well as with other Union policies”.

In the following, coherence between the CFP and the EGD policy stream of biodiversity in the marine environment and its relevant policies will be analysed. The analysis is based on the CrossGov coherence method. The purpose of the analysis is to examine whether the objectives (and exemptions) in the policies within the cluster are aligned/complementary or whether there are inconsistencies/contradictions.

6.2 Coherence of objectives

The regulation of fisheries in the EU has a history that dates back to the early days of the union, but it was not until the United Kingdom, Ireland and Denmark were about to join the European Economic Community in the early 1970s that it began to play a significant role and the Member States agreed to leave the management of their fisheries resources in the hands of the European Community (European Parliament, 2024). It was not until 1983 though that a first common fisheries policy was adopted through regulation 170/83/EEC establishing a Community system for the conservation and management of fishery resources. The regulation does not contain explicit environmental objectives, but instead aims to *ensure the protection of fishing grounds, the conservation of the biological resources of the sea and their balanced exploitation on a lasting basis and in appropriate economic and social conditions* (art. 1). When the regulation was repealed and replaced with regulation 3760/92/EC establishing a Community system for fisheries and aquaculture, the phrase *taking account of its implications for the marine ecosystem* was added along with *needs of both producers and consumers* which was to be taken into account *in particular*.

As the EU's interest in environmental issues has increased over the years, so has the integration of environmental issues in sectoral legislation. The CFP is no different. To the core logic of balanced exploitation of a natural resource to achieve economic and social objectives within the sector, an outer logic of a wider environmental protection not directly connected to the long-term success of the sector has been added. While measures to limit the harm of the fishing sector is necessary to achieve environmental objectives, the main responsibility and holistic perspective of environmental sustainability in the marine environment are still placed in the water and nature directives. To ensure that environmental objectives affected by the main pressures are achieved, the regulation of both must be coherent including the objectives.

The overall objective of the CFP is to ensure that fishing and aquaculture activities are environmentally sustainable in the long-term and are managed in a way that is consistent with the objectives of achieving economic, social and employment benefits, and of contributing to the availability of food supplies. The policy is aimed at exploitation of living marine biological resources that restores and maintains fish resources at levels which can produce the maximum sustainable yield through a precautionary and eco-system approaches to fisheries management. The use of MSY in the EU is thus not intended nor constructed to protect or restore biodiversity, but instead refers to social and economic sustainability for its origins. This is manifested in the combined objective for stocks above levels which could provide MSY with an obligation to pursue an MSY exploitation rate. If achieved, the objective will most likely have a positive net outcome for marine biodiversity, but the objective does not entail optimising the outcome for biodiversity. However, it was noted in the proposal that the MSY approach would allow for the CFP to aid in the achievement of Good Environmental Status (European Commission, 2011b).

The objectives then progress to list ten specific objectives that the CFP shall achieve, including taking aspects of socio-economic aspects, producer and consumer interests and avoiding, reducing or make best use of unwanted catches. The last of these particular objectives is for the CFP to be coherent with the Union environmental legislation, in particular with the objective of achieving a good environmental status by 2020 as set out in MSFD, as well as with other Union policies. The objective was introduced in the latest rendition of the CFP to increase the coherence between the sector policy and the environmental policies. The integration of the reformed 2014 Common Fisheries Policy in the broader maritime policy context was a focus at its conception due to the Integrated Maritime Policy for the European Union, which was based on the clear recognition that all matters relating to Europe's oceans and seas are interlinked (European Commission, 2007). The MSFD was identified as the general basis for the implementation of an ecosystem approach to the marine environment (European Commission, 2008, p. 2). As such, the new CFP had to be set up to provide the right instruments to support this approach (European Commission, 2009b, p. 19). The result was that the MSFD was mentioned as a specific policy that the CFP was to be coherent with and the introduction of legal instruments with the specific purpose of creating coherence between CFP and environmental legislation, most notably art. 11 of the CFP.

There are also important interconnections between the CFP and the Habitats Directive, particularly through policy instruments connected to the establishment and management of protected areas which contributes to the achievement of both policies' objectives.

6.2.1 The scope of the objectives

Unlike the environmental policies, as a sector policy the scope is limited to certain prescribed activities, in this case fisheries and aquaculture which the CFP has a wide scope. Article 1 of the regulation states that the policy covers the conservation of marine biological resources and the management of fisheries and fleets exploiting such resources, as well as measures on markets and financial measures in support of the CFP.

An important aspect of all marine policy is the geographical scope. While similar issues can arise for policy on land, the decision-making and possible influence on activities are generally more divided in the marine space. The possibilities to directly regulate in marine spaces are usually divided into three different competences: coastal state, flag state and port state. The different competences can be used on their own or in combination depending on the type of measure. While it is possible to regulate activities from vessels outside of the geographical territory of the state, the same opportunity does not exist for area protection. As noted above, the EU competence also differs between the conservation of marine biological resources, an exclusive competence of the EU, and fisheries, a shared competence of the EU.

The CFP uses a wide geographical scope, applicable beyond the territorial jurisdiction of EU's member states. According to art. 1.2, the policy covers activities carried out (a) on the territory of Member States to which the Treaty applies, (b) in Union waters, including by fishing vessels flying the flag of, and registered in, third countries, (c) by Union fishing vessels outside Union waters; or (d) by nationals of Member States, without prejudice to the primary responsibility of the flag State. This entails that the policy is not only applicable in EU waters, but also outside of EU territory for EU flagged vessels and, in certain cases, EU nationals. As approx. 20 % of catches landed in EU are from outside of EU waters, the policy has potential for significant impact beyond EU territory.

As such, the geographical scope has a high coherence with the MSFD, WFD and Nature Directives. The CFP covers the geographical scope of these directives in regards to marine waters and thus is not hindered of taking necessary actions by the scope. Furthermore, the CFP's scope covers an even wider geographical scope as it can regulate activities outside EU waters.

6.2.2 Timeframe for the achievement of the objectives

As noted above, the Habitat Directive does not set a timeframe or deadline for the achievement of FCS but instead expects continued improvement, while the MSFD prescribed a set timeframe of achieving MGES by 2020, with certain exemptions, and thereafter continuous six-year cycle for implementation updates with the current 3rd cycle of implementation starting 2024 and ending 2029, see section 3.2.2 above for further information on timeframes for Nature Directives and MSFD. The achievement of the objectives of the CFP are in general not subject

to a specific timeframe but are instead continuous and effective as soon as the regulation enters into force unless otherwise stated. However, the objective of progressively restoring and maintaining populations of fish stocks above biomass levels capable of producing maximum sustainable yield, it was to be achieved 2015 where possible and, on a progressive, incremental basis at the latest by 2020 for all stocks. The objective of achieving exploitation of fish stocks at the level of maximum sustainable yield established in the UN Convention on the Law of the Sea and was adopted at the 2002 World Summit on Sustainable Development as a target to reach by 2015, where possible. Of note is also the timeframe for the EMFAF. With an overall budget exceeding € 6 billion over a seven-year period, the current funding period runs between 1 January 2021 and 31 December 2027. The differences in timeframes may be a disturbance in the coordination between the MSFD implementation and the available funds in the EMFAF.

6.2.3 Legal impacts of the objectives

As the CFP is in the form of a regulation, the legal impacts of the objectives differ quite substantially from those of the directives such as MSFD and the nature directives. Directives create a legal obligation for the Member States regarding the results to be achieved, while regulations instead are directly applicable (art. 288). For Member States, it means that they are not allowed to introduce national legislation that alter, breach, or obscure the direct effect of the regulation.

A Member State may adopt legislation to implement the regulation and at times it is required for a Member State to do so, either through an explicit requirement of national implementation in the regulation or if necessitated for the regulation to guarantee the application and effectiveness. In such cases, the objectives are of importance to determine that national implementing measures does not compromise the objectives of the policy.

Overall, the objectives of the policies have a high level of coherence. The sector policy has clearly stated objectives in line with the environmental policies and there are even references made to them, especially the MSFD. In terms of scope, timeframes and impacts there are noticeable differences that may be of concern. Certain aspects may cause fragmentations, such as the differences in timeframes and scope, while the legal impact may cause incoherence if not properly addressed in the policy instruments as decisions made on an EU level can hinder an effective national implementation of directives.

6.3 Coherence of instruments

6.3.1 MPAs and tools in the CFP for Member States to enact conservation measures

Marine protected areas (MPAs) are geographically outlined zones with certain protection objectives. For further information on MPAs in EU legislation, see section 3.3.2 above. The MPAs are an important measure for the protection and restoration of marine biodiversity and the Biodiversity Strategy has set up an objective of legally protecting min. 30% of the EU's Sea area and integrate ecological corridors by 2030. In the EU, these protected areas are mainly designated under the HD and the BD with the remaining sites designated under national legislation (European Environment Agency, 2020). As noted above, this is substantiated in

MSFD where article 13(4) states that “spatial protection measures, contributing to coherent and representative networks of marine protected areas, adequately covering the diversity of the constituent ecosystems”.

Besides increasing the coverage of MPAs in EU waters, a substantive challenge in providing effective protection is to remove the key pressures from these areas to allow for recovery of the species and habitats. As a key pressure, appropriate measures on fishing are crucial to allow for sufficient protection. To address this, article 11 of the CFP was introduced and it is intended to provide a tool for the Member States to enact conservation measures. Conservation measures are defined in the regulation’s article 7 and contain a large range of measures including multiannual plans, measures to adapt the fishing capacity, measures on the fixing, allocation of fishing opportunities and technical measures such as restrictions on fishing gear. The article empowers the Member States to adopt conservation measures under certain circumstances, a pure environmental protection measure that falls under the shared competence of the EU. As such, it is subject to principles of subsidiarity and proportionality (Ribeiro 2017). The substantive scope is limited to only conservation measures that are deemed necessary for the effectiveness of MPAs. The process of implementing can be complex and is subject to several requirements depending on the subject it is intended to target.

For vessels flying its own flag, art. 11(1) states that Member States are empowered to adopt conservation measures necessary to comply with the MPA regimes established in the HD, BD and MSFD. For the adoption of such measures, the measure must meet three criteria. Firstly, the measure must be compatible with the objectives of the CFP. Second, the measure must meet the objectives of the HD, BD and/or MSFD. Thirdly, it must be at least as stringent as measures under Union law. This entails that the measure introduced by the Member State must meet the minimum standard of environmental protection as set by the EU and can include more stringent protection if compatible with the treaties and notified to the Commission (ibid.). Failure to adopt such conservation methods might result in Member State being in breach of the legal obligation of the nature directives or the MSFD and could result in action from the Commission.

To extend such measures to all EU vessels, i.e. for vessels not flying the Member State’s flag, the process is completely different as other Member States will be involved and the resulting legal measure will be a delegated act according to article 46. The coastal state, or the “initiating Member State”, will have to initiate a procedure that involves both the Commission and other Member States have a direct management interest in the fishery to be affected by such measures by providing relevant information on the measures required, including their rationale, scientific evidence in support and details on their practical implementation and enforcement. The involved Member States may submit suggested measures as a joint recommendation in accordance with art. 18 that the Commission may adopt as a delegated act.

The possibility to submit joint recommendations was introduced in the 2013 version of CFP to increase the regional influence over the management of fishing in the EU. To be noted is that

there is no obligation for the Member States to issue a joint recommendation to the Commission nor is there an obligation for the Commission to follow it (Eggert and Langlet, 2020). Further, it is unclear whether the Commission can influence the shape of such measures with the aim of avoiding rejection (Ribeiro, 2017).

The application of such measures has been uneven at best. Member States have not sought to use the tool as it is complicated, lengthy, and often deemed to lead to weak restrictions. Final restrictions may be weaker than the initially proposed and during the lengthy discussion the area remain open for vessels of other Member States which leads to continued damage to sensitive habitats (European Court of Auditors, 2020). This restricts both the number of conservation measures and the timing of them needed to reach the objectives of the EGD. As such, the EU Action Plan for protecting and restoring marine ecosystems for sustainable and resilient fisheries includes several actions for both the Member States and the Commission, but as the actions are not legally binding it is difficult to predict what impact they will have (European Commission, 2023b).

6.3.2 Maximum sustainable yield to protect biodiversity

In 2006, the Commission sent a communication to the Parliament and the Council on the use of Maximum Sustainable Yield (MSY) as a measure to implement sustainability in EU fisheries (European Commission, 2006). At the simplest of terms, MSY is the maximum yield that may be taken year after year that will be on a level of fishing mortality that will, on average, result in a stock size that produces the highest possible yield long term. Fishing above MSY in the short term will lead to lower catch opportunities in the longer term as the fish stock is fished down. The implementation of this approach was believed to reverse the tendency of decline in many fish stocks, improve the economic situation of the fishery, improve the balance of trade and reduce discards and impact on non-target species.

After intense negotiations, MSY approach was written in to the 2013 edition of the CFP. As noted before, the use of MSY in the EU is not intended nor constructed to protect or restore biodiversity, but instead refers to social and economic sustainability for its origins. This is manifested in the combined objective for stocks above levels which could provide MSY with an obligation to pursue an MSY exploitation rate. This was the result of drawn-out negotiations between the Parliament and the Council, and the ambiguity of it would cause problems in the deliberations of future management plans (Earle, 2021).

In practice, MSY is to be achieved through multiannual plans. The plans shall be adopted based on scientific, technical and economic advice and contain conservation measures to restore and maintain fish stocks above levels capable of producing maximum sustainable yield (art. 9). As with conservation measures for MPAs, Member States are also able to submit joint recommendations in accordance with art. 18. For stocks for which no multi-annual plan has been established, exploitation rates delivering maximum sustainable yield should be ensured by setting catch and/or fishing effort limits (European Commission, 2011b). The multiannual

plans are adopted through regulation from the Council and the Parliament.²⁸ Currently there are four plans established; Cod, herring and sprat stocks in the Baltic Sea, Demersal stocks in the North Sea, Demersal stocks in western Mediterranean Sea and Stocks fished in western waters. The multiannual plans are supplemented by regulations with specific measures, both with regional scope and for the entire Union.

The multiannual plans aim not only to achieve MSY but also to ensure compliance with the MSFD. Out of the eleven descriptors defining GES, descriptor 3 is the most relevant for fisheries management. It considers anthropogenic pressure of commercially exploited fish and shellfish. As it falls under exclusive EU competence, the CFP is essential to achieve set criteria. The Member States are to establish threshold values through regional or subregional cooperation for each population of species in accordance with scientific advice obtained pursuant to art 26 of the CFP. The outcomes of these population assessments shall also contribute to the assessments under Descriptors 1 and 6. The actions of the Member States and the Commission regarding the relationship between MSFD and the fisheries management are further addressed in the EU Action Plan.

Based on the multiannual plans, multilateral or bilateral consultations with non-EU countries, and the scientific advice of International Council for the Exploration of the Sea (ICES), the Council regulates fishing opportunities annually or for several years in the form of set total annual catches (TACs). The use of TAC has been recognised as a potential tool for reaching the objectives of the CFP, but in practice has proven to be unreliable in delivering results. The multiannual plans have been criticised for being both too rigid as they do not allow for sufficient TAC increases in certain situations, while some have criticised them for being too flexible and as such not ensuring they were set at MSY by 2020 at latest (European Commission, 2020e). Furthermore, the scientific advice of ICES is not legally binding and TACs have regularly been set contrary to such advice. At times, reliable data has also been lacking. As a result, the catch limits have not been able to prevent overfishing in a satisfying way.

6.3.3 The fund and biodiversity

The European Maritime, Fisheries and Aquaculture Fund (EMFAF) is one of the main legal instruments within the CFP policy. The fund supports fishing and aquaculture activities and is established for a certain period. The current fund has an overall budget of € 6,108 billion over a seven-year period, with the current funding period running between 1 January 2021 and 31 December 2027. The fund prioritises fostering sustainable fisheries and aquaculture activities, enabling sustainable blue economy and strengthening international ocean governance. It should also contribute to the achievement of the environmental and climate change mitigation and adaptation objectives of the Union (as stated in preamble (16) and again in art. 3).

²⁸ This was a matter of uncertainty for a long period of time. The right of the Parliament to co-decide was confirmed by the ECJ in 2015, see joined cases C-124/13 and C-125/13, *Parliament and Commission v Council*.

While a proper analysis of the fund allocations is outside the scope of this report, it can be noted that other reports have concluded that the funding has been used to a limited extent to limit impact of fishing on the marine environment. Instead, funded activities have historically more often been allocated to activities that risk creating additional pressures on fish stocks and vulnerable marine habitats (European Court of Auditors, 2020).

6.4 Conclusions

Fishing activities are responsible for some of the main pressures on ecosystems in Europe's seas. To protect marine biodiversity in accordance with the objectives of the European Green Deal, a high level of coherence between legal instruments that regulate the pressures and protect the marine environment is necessary. The CFP covers resource management and market measures, mainly to support the industry and boost the market. While resource management has clear overlaps with environmental protection, there are also differences in protection mainly for further exploitation and the protection of a natural environment.

The policy has historically focused on creating a stable industry and market, creating the policy's core logic over a long period of time. Recent years environmental objectives have been added, creating an outer logic. As the logics often clash, the policy has encountered issues with combining the two in practice. This has been furthered by the differences in competences and the different forms of legal acts used for the sector legislation and the environmental protection legislation. Member States have only limited competence in adopting national measures regarding the fishing sector, even when they are acting upon obligations deriving from other EU statutes such as the HD or MSFD. As fishing is one of the largest pressures on marine biodiversity, this limits the Member States ability to enact proper measures in accordance with these directives and creates issues with the coordination of these legal instruments.

The solution has been to add specific legal instruments to ensure proper environmental protection, mainly in relation to the MSFD. Article 11 of the CFP is intended to provide a tool for the Member States to enact conservation measures. The substantive scope is limited though as it only applies conservation measures that are deemed necessary for the effectiveness of MPAs – which is crucial in the biodiversity objectives of the EGD. Further, Member States have not sought to use the tool as it is complicated, lengthy, and often deemed to lead to weak restrictions. This has further led to the ineffectiveness of MPAs in practice. Other key measures in the CFP have also not been able to protect biodiversity. For example, the catch limits have not been able to prevent overfishing in a satisfying way, both due to the lack of reliable data and legal bindingness of MSY. Further, the funding from the policy has only in a limited extent been used to limit impact of fishing on the marine environment and more often funded activities that risk creating additional pressures on fish stocks and vulnerable marine habitats.

While coherence measures have been implemented into the policy's objectives and legal instruments, CFP and the EU fishing management are yet to align with the EU environmental policies, mainly MSFD, in practice. The legal instruments are still complicated and ineffective in the practical use and lack the legal bindingness necessary to ensure the achievement of the objectives in environmental protection policies and the EGD.

7 Renewable energy – offshore wind power

7.1 Introduction

In this chapter, the EU biodiversity cluster (see chapter 3) objectives and instruments are evaluated against the climate change mitigation and renewable energy targets and instruments pertaining to increased offshore wind power generation. The climate policy stream of the EGD aims at reaching climate neutrality by 2050 (economy with net-zero GHG emissions) in line with the EU's commitment to global climate action under the Paris Agreement. By 2030, the EC aims to produce 60GW wind energy and at least 1GW ocean energy, with the aim to increase this to a production of 300GW offshore wind and 40GW ocean energy by 2050. Through the Offshore Renewable Energy Strategy, the EC emphasizes that marine renewables can be a useful tool in achieving the 2030 and 2050 climate goals of the EU, especially if combined with the decarbonisation of maritime transport and fisheries. The strategy focuses on the development of different forms of marine renewable energy, including wind, and aims at the same time to promote a sustainable use of the marine environment and its resources. The strategy highlights the relevance of conducting environmental impact assessments (EIAs) to assess the potential impacts of offshore renewable energy projects on marine biodiversity. It also stresses the need to establish spatial plans to ensure that such projects are located in areas that are appropriate from an environmental, economic and social perspective. The strategy focuses on the importance of stakeholder engagement and consultation in the development of marine renewable energy projects, such as local communities, environmental organisations, and other stakeholders in the planning and decision-making processes. The aspiration to increase renewable energy production – offshore wind power including – is visible both in the overall goals of EU Climate Law (2021/1119) as well as the specific targets of the EU Renewable Energy Directive (RED III, 2023/2413). Maritime Spatial Planning Directive (2014/89/EU) further supports these objectives.

Evaluating the coherence of EU objectives and instruments for renewable energy and marine biodiversity comes with several caveats. First, as the renewable energy objectives cut across renewables technologies both on land and at sea, the renewable energy objectives are not necessarily incoherent with the biodiversity objectives if renewable energy development will not result in increases in offshore wind power generation and related infrastructure, such as transmission cables. Second, even if the objectives will result in offshore wind power development, a transition to floating installations, or locating the bottom-fixed operations in areas with low biodiversity may allow decreased level of conflict between power generation and biodiversity and may render the EU renewables and biodiversity objectives rather coherent. This being said, the current level of technological development does not support this as floating installations are still at a developmental stage and bottom-fixed operations are widely used in commercial facilities. At this moment, it is not foreseen that floating operations would gain considerable market share in the near future (e.g., before 2030) which would mean that many currently planned operations will opt for bottom-fixed foundation. There are also strong signs that offshore wind power installations are often located on shallow banks where biodiversity is higher compared to deeper areas of the sea. There is also concern that the magnetism of

transmission cables will disrupt the lifecycles of fish and other marine species (e.g., migratory fish circumventing areas where there are transmission cables). Moreover, the wingspan of the wind turbines can be several hundred meters with wind power parks encompassing typically dozens or even hundreds of installations. This translates to considerable spatial needs in the European regional seas.

Notwithstanding these caveats, increased offshore wind energy production may entail negative consequences on marine biodiversity. Offshore wind installations can disrupt the lifecycles and fish and other marine species, thereby impacting on marine biodiversity. Moreover, wind turbine parks need considerable space, and the most optimal places are typically in shallow banks that also are biodiversity hotspots. An additional concern is the lack of full knowledge on the possible effects and impact on marine biodiversity through offshore wind energy installations and infrastructures. These concerns, in combination with the observation that there is unclarity about the legal status of the MSFD goals and objectives, bring forth uncertainty on how biodiversity considerations are taken into account during decision-making processes on wind energy projects.

This chapter sheds more light on the specific coherence challenges and opportunities between the EU Climate Law and Renewable Energy Directive and the biodiversity-related directives, including the WFD, MSFD and Nature Directives.

7.2 Coherence of objectives

7.2.1 The scope of the objectives

The primary objective of the European Climate Law is to set a framework for the irreversible and gradual reduction of anthropogenic GHG emissions by sources and enhancement of removals by sinks as regulated in Union law, as stated in Article 1. While the Regulation does not have a specific objective related to the ocean, its overarching goal encompasses a broad range of environmental concerns, including marine environments. These are, however, mostly considered from the perspective that climate change mitigation will help protect marine biodiversity as well.

The general climate change mitigation objectives established in European Climate Law are operationalized by the revised 2023 EU Renewable energy directive (RED III). The primary aim of this Directive is to support the EU's ambition to achieve climate neutrality, primarily through an increased reliance on renewable energy sources. According to the directive, renewable energy means energy from renewable, non-fossil sources, including wind power on land and in marine areas (RED III, art. 2). RED III is designed to bolster the European economy, particularly in the renewable energy sector, including offshore energy production. The Directive also seeks to contribute to climate and environmental objectives, including biodiversity protection, thereby addressing concerns associated with global warming and biodiversity loss. From the outset, the line of reasoning is that by promoting the use of renewable energy sources, RED III indirectly contributes to biodiversity protection by reducing reliance on fossil fuels, which are associated with habitat destruction and pollution. In addition

to this, the directive also contains some specific provisions to ensure that renewable energy is not sourced from areas that are designated as high biodiversity value or from raw material that negatively impact such areas. This includes areas designated for nature protection purposes and recognized areas for the protection of rare, threatened, or endangered ecosystems or species. This refers mainly to agricultural lands, heathlands, and forests, and other types of ecosystems, and not specifically to marine biodiversity.

On the long term, the objectives of the directive can support the environmental objectives of the MSFD and Nature Directives, depending on the effects of certain instruments applied through the directive as well as the magnitude of offshore renewable energy installations, grids and other infrastructure necessary to realize the targets of the Offshore Renewable Energy Strategy. However, such infrastructure may impact marine biodiversity and seafloor integrity, both important indicators for the achieving the MSFD goal of GES for marine ecosystems. It may also impact species and habitats protected under the Nature Directives, thereby possibly affecting achieving their Favourable Conservation Status. Such tensions may be either mitigated or aggravated through the specific policy instruments in place.

To further support renewable energy development – and to reconcile conflicting interests between different uses of the sea – the Maritime Spatial Planning Directive requires member states to establish maritime spatial plans, the purpose of which is to facilitate co-location of several marine activities, including offshore wind power generation, shipping, fishing, aquaculture, and nature conservation (art. 4 and 5). One of the explicit aims of the directive is to promote economic growth in the maritime sector, such as offshore wind (art. 5).

7.2.2 Timeframe for the achievement of the objectives

EU Climate Law sets specific targets that include achieving climate neutrality within the EU by 2050, as outlined in Article 2. This ambitious goal requires balancing Union-wide GHG emissions and removals as regulated in Union law by this date, with the aim of reaching net zero emissions and then moving towards negative emissions. Additionally, there is an intermediate target of reducing net GHG emissions by at least 55 per cent compared to 1990 levels by 2030, as specified in Article 4. The Regulation also emphasizes continuous progress in enhancing adaptive capacity, strengthening resilience, and reducing vulnerability to climate change, in line with Article 7 of the Paris Agreement, as stated in Article 5 of the Regulation.

The European Climate law sets significant milestones for 2030 (e.g., 55 per cent reduction in net GHG emissions) and 2050 (climate neutrality). The ambitious nature of these objectives, coupled with the relatively short timeframe and the need to balance fairness, solidarity, and cost-effectiveness, underscores the Regulation's comprehensive and challenging nature. The European Climate Law aligns with and supports global environmental commitments, notably the Paris agreement and the UN 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development, as referenced in the preamble paragraphs 8 and 9. This alignment demonstrates the EU's commitment to global climate action and sustainable development goals.

RED III requires member states to collectively ensure that at least 42,5 % of all gross energy consumed in the EU comes from renewable sources by 2030, with aspiration to hit 45 %. To ensure that offshore renewable energy can help reach the EU's ambitious energy and climate targets for 2030 and 2050, the Commission published a dedicated EU strategy on offshore renewable energy (COM(2020)741) on 19 November 2020 which proposes concrete ways forward to support the long-term sustainable development of this sector. It sets targets for an installed capacity of at least 60 GW of offshore wind and 1 GW of ocean energy by 2030, and 300 GW and 40 GW, respectively, by 2050.

Regarding MSP, the EU member states were required to introduce transposing legislation implementing the directive by 2016 (art. 15(1)) and to produce the first maritime spatial plans for 2021 (art. 15(3)).

As described in chapter 3, the Nature Directives do not set a specific deadline for achieving the FCS, although the Commission has clarified that Member States are expected to make continued progress (European Commission, 2011a). The MSFD prescribes that the MGES was to be achieved in all marine regions and subregions by 2020 (certain exemptions allowed), however, as explained, the current legal situation is unclear on whether there is any sort of legal deadline attached to the obligations on achieving MGES anymore. The lack of clear and legally binding deadlines for the achievement of the MSFD and Nature Directives objectives does not impose a direct incoherence with the deadlines of RED III. Yet the existence of some collective quantitative targets to be achieved by the set deadlines in RED III versus the more qualitative targets with unclear deadlines in the Nature Directives and MSFD may contribute to differentiated prioritizations within MS, with a risk that the objectives are not accomplished equally well. It thus complicates cross-compliance with both the EGD biodiversity and climate targets.

7.2.3 Legal impacts of the objectives

The European Climate Law is cross-cutting in nature, impacting various sectors across the Union and it applies to all sources and sinks of GHG regulated under EU law. This inclusive approach is evident in paragraphs 7 and 10 of the preambles, emphasizing the role of diverse sectors – from energy and industry to agriculture and waste management – in contributing to the Union's climate neutrality.

Many EU member states, Finland included, are expecting considerable increase in offshore wind power development in the coming decade to reach the climate change mitigation targets. EU member states are, however, free to choose which technologies to deploy under the EU climate law and RED III (either on land or at sea) to reach the objectives which results in uncertainty regarding where the largest push for renewables will be channeled in the different EU countries (Giljam, 2018). The directive does not have offshore wind power-specific objectives or rules. The Renewable Energy Directive pays some attention to biodiversity loss associated with renewable energy but mostly regarding bioenergy and not wind (Romppanen, 2020 and Huhta et. al., 2024).

The collective objective of ensuring that at least 42,5 % of all gross energy consumed in the EU comes from renewable sources by 2030, is a legally binding target with some flexibility. Being a collective target, the impact of this objective plays out differently for the various EU member states. Moreover, covering energy from all energy sources, the division and percentage to be produced through offshore renewables is up to the MS to decide upon. The EGD Offshore Renewable Energy Strategy, though not legally binding, helps specifying the amount of offshore wind energy to be desirably produced.

Moreover, while RED III does not explicitly state the percentage of renewable energy to be produced offshore, Article 9 requires MS bordering sea basins to collaborate in setting collective targets for offshore renewable energy production for 2050, with interim goals for 2030 and 2040. These targets are to be reported in their National Energy and Climate Plans under the EU Energy Governance Regulation. These reporting requirements entail that the overall collective EU target is to be broken down into country specific targets, and that compliance with these is measured regularly. Through this reporting as required under the Governance Regulation, MS also report on the environmental impacts of their energy policies. This includes tracking biodiversity outcomes and ensuring that energy projects comply with environmental standards. There is some potential here to report on matters of particular relevance for the implementation of the MSFD and ND (see more below).

Additionally, the Directive aims to expedite the permitting processes for new renewable energy installations and sets a goal to reach a 13 per cent reduction in GHG emissions intensity in the transport sector by 2030. This reduction is to be achieved through the promotion of advanced biofuels, biogas, and renewable fuels of non-biological origin.

Finally, while member states have an obligation to produce maritime spatial plans for promoting the objectives of the directive, the MSPD comprises of procedural obligations on which marine interests need to be considered in the planning, but not substantive obligations on how the interests are prioritised (Soininen, 2015). This leaves the legal impact of the MSPD into the hands of the member states at the transposition and implementation phases of the directive. This is a challenge from a biodiversity perspective as in many countries MSPs are used to drive economic uses of the sea rather than the protection of the seas (Sander, 2024).

7.3 Coherence between instruments

The European Climate Law requires EU Institutions and MS to implement necessary measures for reaching the 2050 climate neutrality objective, with a focus on fairness, solidarity, and cost-effectiveness (art. 2, Paragraph 2). Additionally, the EC is responsible for reviewing EU legislation to facilitate meeting the intermediate and final targets (art. 4, para 2). The law also mandates continuous progress in adapting to climate change (art. 5), ensuring a comprehensive approach to climate action across the EU.

To reach the objectives of EU Climate Law, RED III establishes several measures for promoting increases in renewable energy, including offshore wind power generation. These include the establishment of renewables acceleration areas, permitting, and impact

assessments. These measures allow the consideration of biodiversity tradeoffs with varying degree. As a primary rule, biodiversity should be considered but in case of conflict, renewable energy development gains priority.

7.3.1 Renewable acceleration areas

RED III requires member states to establish ‘*renewables acceleration areas*’ (also known as ‘go-to’ areas) for streamlined planning and permitting (art. 15c). These areas are homogenous inland, water, or sea areas where the deployment of a specific type of renewable energy sources is not expected to have a significant environmental impact (art. 15c(1)(a)). Acceleration areas should, where possible, be located on areas that are artificial or built (with the intent that there biodiversity has already been lost and this reduces tradeoffs) and to avoid Natura 2000 sites and areas designated under national protection schemes for nature and biodiversity conservation, major bird and marine mammal migratory routes as well as other areas identified on the basis of sensitivity maps and the tools referred to in the point (art. 15c(1)(a)(ii)). Moreover, national authorities should, where possible, use all appropriate and proportionate tools and datasets to identify the areas where the renewable energy plants would not have a significant environmental impact (art. 15c(1)(a)(iii)). Finally, the member states are to establish rules for significantly reducing the environmental impact of renewable energy projects with specific reference to Habitats and Birds Directive biodiversity objectives and instruments (art. 15c(1)(b)).

While RED III makes various references to the protected areas established under the Nature Directives and aims to avoid overlap between the Natura 2000 areas and the renewable acceleration areas, no references are made to the MSFD and the effects of offshore energy projects on marine biodiversity as addressed through the MSFD GES within and outside of renewable acceleration areas.

7.3.2 Permits and impact assessments

Article 16 RED III regulates the *permitting procedures* for building, repowering and operating renewable energy plants. The directive introduces a simplification and shortening of the administrative permit-granting procedures for renewable energy plants (including their connection to the grid) as deemed necessary to ensure that the Union reaches its ambition climate change energy targets by 2030 (Preamble para 22) and accelerate the deployment of renewable energy projects (para 23). Within renewable acceleration areas, member states shall ensure that permit duration of offshore wind power projects does not exceed 24 months – with a possibility for 6 month extension if justified (art. 16a(1)). For smaller plants, the procedure shall not exceed 12 months. Outside renewable acceleration areas, the timeline for permits is 36 months (art. 16b(1)).

Screening process

As part of the permitting procedure, competent authorities are to conduct a *screening process* of the applications aiming to identify if any of the renewable energy projects is highly likely to give rise to significant unforeseen adverse effects in view of the environmental sensitivity of

the geographical areas where they are located (art. 16a(4)). The project developer provides relevant information on the characteristics of the project, including measures taken to comply with the ND and WFD, and how these measures address environmental impact. For new applications however (as those specified in article 16a(3)), the burden of proof lies upon the competent authority to demonstrate that there are due reasons to assume, based on clear evidence, that a specific project is highly likely to give rise to significant unforeseen adverse effects in view of the environmental sensitivity of the geographical area where the project is located, that cannot be mitigated by the measures identified in the plans designating acceleration areas or proposed by the project developer. In such circumstances, the projects shall be subject to an impact assessment pursuant to the Nature Directives (art. 16a(5)).

RED III provides considerable leeway. It specifies that in the event of justified circumstances, for example being the need to accelerate the deployment of renewable energy to achieve the climate and renewable energy targets of the EGD, Member States may nevertheless exempt wind projects from such assessments. If needed, the operators can be required to pay monetary compensation for species protection programmes for the duration of the operation of the plant to ensure or improve the conservation status of the species affected (art. 16a(5)).

Normally, the threshold for carrying out such assessments pursuant to the Nature Directives is relatively low. The HD and BD require that the condition or quality of designated areas should not deteriorate. Plans and projects in these areas likely to have significant effect thereupon shall be subject to an appropriate assessment of their implications for the site in view of the site's conservation objectives. Impact assessments have to be carried out for *any* project that *may have* a significant effect on the site, and it should not be assumed too easily that significant effects will not arise.

If the appropriate assessment concludes that adverse effects cannot be ruled out, then there are very limited options. If the appropriate assessment shows that the activity may adversely affect the integrity of the site, the permit should in principle not be granted. The permit can only be granted if there are no other alternatives for the project, and only for reasons of 'overriding public interest', and if compensatory measures are in place (art. 6.4 HD).

Despite RED III establishing a general obligation not to locate renewable energy projects in Natura 2000 areas or areas otherwise protected by the Habitats and Birds Directives, the directive states explicitly that renewable energy projects automatically fulfil the 'overriding public interest' requirement under article 6.4 HD (art. 16f RED III) in the period between February 2024 until the overall objective of the Climate Law of climate neutrality has been achieved. Being one of the key criteria for granting exemptions from biodiversity protection, this will make it much easier to ensure 'compliance' with the Nature Directives goals and instruments while also speeding up offshore wind energy projects.

Likewise, a similar reasoning applies to the exemptions available under the WFD. Article 16(f) RED III clarifies that the planning, construction and operation of renewable energy plants, and their connection to the grid, should be considered to be of overriding public interest when

balancing legal interests in legal cases for the purposes of not only the Nature Directives, but also the WFD. Article 4.7 WFD provides the legal grounds for failure to achieve good ecological status or to prevent deterioration in the status of a water bodies (exemptions). Exemptions are allowed in case of new modifications or new sustainable human development activities, and if certain conditions are met. One of these conditions is that the reasons for modifications are necessary for reasons of overriding public interest. RED art 16(f) stipulates that offshore renewable energy projects are automatically considered to be of overriding public interest, providing grounds to justify non-achievement of the WFD goals.

Impact assessments

Environmental assessments may be required as part of the permit-granting assessments. Within acceleration areas, the idea is that environmental impact assessment is conducted as a whole and subsequently the projects are exempt from conducting project specific EIAs and Natura 2000 impact assessments (art. 16a(3)). The overall plans designating renewables acceleration areas shall be subject to an environmental assessment pursuant to Directive 2001/42/EC, and if they are likely to have a significant impact on Natura 2000-sites, to the appropriate assessment pursuant to the HD.

By way of derogation from Article 6(3) of Habitats Directive, individual renewable energy plants do thus not need to be subject to an assessment of their implications for Natura 2000-sites provided that those renewable energy projects comply with the rules and measures established in accordance with Article 15c(1), point (b), of RED III, which lay down a requirement to have in place appropriate mitigation measures to ensure compliance with the HD, BD and WFD.

Compliance with the Nature Directives and the WFD is presumed when appropriate mitigation measures are implemented by the individual projects. If novel mitigation measures are applied and these have not been proven effective yet with regard to preventing the killing of disturbance of species protected under the Nature Directives, Member States may nevertheless apply such mitigating measures for one or several pilot projects for a limited time period, provided that the effectiveness of such mitigation measures is closely monitored and appropriate steps are taken immediately if they prove not to be effective (Article 15(1) RED III).

Outside of the acceleration areas, when an environmental assessment is required pursuant to the Nature Directives, it shall be carried out as a single procedure that combines all relevant assessments for a given renewable energy project (art. 16(b)2). Also, when a renewable energy project has adopted necessary mitigation measures, any killing or disturbance of species protected under the HD and BD shall not be considered deliberate. As such, a permit cannot not be rejected on those grounds.

To further facilitate the decision-making process for individual projects, under art. 16a(6), Member States shall ensure that the lack of reply by the relevant competent authorities within the established deadline results in the specific intermediary administrative steps to be considered as approved, except where the specific renewable energy project is subject to an

environmental impact assessment pursuant to paragraph 5 or where the principle of administrative tacit approval does not exist in the national legal system of the Member State concerned.

7.4 To sum up

The above assessment on the level of coherence between the objectives and instruments in environmental policies and RED III demonstrates that the latter establishes several easements to comply with the procedural and substantive legal requirements of renewable energy projects. To sum up the main easements:

- Within renewables acceleration areas, effects on Natura 2000 sites should be avoided, while effects on GES required through the MSFD are not really addressed. The *overall plans* designating such renewable acceleration areas shall be subject to an impact assessment.
- Within renewables acceleration areas, permitting procedures should be simple and effective.
 - i. For the screening phase, the competent authority can require an impact assessment in case it is *highly likely* that the renewable energy project give rise to *significant unforeseen adverse* effects. Only then, project-based impact assessments are necessary.
 - ii. MS can nevertheless exempt wind projects from such assessments in case of justified circumstances (which is the need to accelerate renewable energy deployment).
 - iii. If the competent authorities did not handle (the various components of) the application by the deadline, they should be considered as approved (some exemptions).
 - iv. If an impact assessment is carried out and demonstrates adverse effects, a permit can still be granted on grounds of ‘overriding public interest’. Renewable energy projects fulfil the requirement of being of overriding public interest in both the Nature Directives and the WFD.
- Outside of renewables acceleration areas, the permitting process should be carried out as a single procedure. Further, if all necessary mitigating measures are adopted, disturbance of species protected under the Nature Directive is not considered deliberate, and thus will not stand in the way of a permit for the renewable energy permit.

While these easements are an effective mechanism to avoid incoherence between the RED III and the environmental directives, they will most likely not ensure proper cross-compliance with the EGD ambitions for both climate change and biodiversity protection. The environmental directives, as a package, are intended to ensure biodiversity protection in the EU and to avoid the deterioration of FCS and GES of marine waters. Creating exemptions and weakening the legal impacts of their instruments helps accelerating the production of offshore renewable energy and the achievement of the quantitative targets set by the Climate Law, RED III and the Offshore Renewable Energy Strategy. It is questionable whether this is a sustainable

approach and whether it undermines, at the same time, progress towards the biodiversity targets of the EGD.

Another observation at this stage is the lack of references to the MSFD in RED III. While various references are made to the Nature Directives and the WFD, references to the MSFD are scarce. In fact, there is only one reference to the MSFD in the Preamble to underscore that the transition to more renewable energy production in the EU will also help a better protection of marine biodiversity through reduced reliance on fossil fuels (Preamble para 83). In the following, some coherence challenges with the MSFD will be highlighted, that require more research and attention.

7.5 Need for increased focus on the MSFD

The Marine Strategy Framework Directive establishes a framework requiring member states to achieve Good Environmental Status (GES) of their marine waters by 2020 (art. 1.1). The ultimate goal of the directive is to maintain biodiversity of the seas that are clean, healthy and productive, and to secure sustainable use of the European seas (preamble 3 and 4). The Good Environmental Status is defined by the following factors: 1) biological diversity; 2) the level of non-indigenous species; 3) populations of commercial fish and shellfish; 4) elements of marine food webs; 5) eutrophication; 6) sea floor integrity; 7) alteration of hydrographical conditions; 8) contaminants; 9) contaminants in fish and seafood for human consumption; 10) marine litter; 11) introduction of energy, including underwater noise (MSFD annex I). Out of these criteria, offshore wind power negatively affects sea floor integrity and introduction of energy (underwater noise from the blades and magnetism from the transmission cables) directly, which in turn may negatively affect several other criteria, such as biological diversity and elements of marine food webs. The extent of these negative biodiversity impacts is relative to the size of the installations and the biodiversity values present at the site of wind power generation and transmission.

The substantive goal of GES is implemented via several procedural requirements. Procedurally, the directive requires member states to establish national contact points (art. 7) and to produce marine strategies, which in turn contain the following: 1) assessment of the ecological condition of the marine areas and drivers affecting it (art. 8); 2) establishment of criteria for measuring the GES (art. 9); 3) programmes of measures to maintain and reach the GES (art. 11); and 4) a monitoring programme tasked to keep track of the condition of the marine environment (art. 13). The preamble of the MSFD emphasizes the role of the programmes of measures describing them as the ‘culmination point’ for achieving the GES.

First coherence challenge between the MSFD good environmental status requirement and RED III backed offshore wind power development is *lack of scientific knowledge* concerning the status of sea-floor integrity and the negative biodiversity impact of underwater noise and magnetism caused by the rotating blades and transmission cables respectively. Despite the MSFD monitoring programmes, authorities in member states such as Finland have not established with sufficient spatial resolution the condition of the sea floor or specific biodiversity values that would be applicable at the (wind power) project scale (Pappila and

Puharinen, 2021). This challenge can, in principle, be overcome to some extent by careful Environmental Impact Assessment when permitting the wind power projects. RED III, however, introduces the idea that EIAs can be exempted in ‘renewable energy acceleration areas’, and there is a real possibility that this will result in overlooking specific biodiversity related values at the site of the operations. This is so particularly considering that the current MSFD assessments should result in an accurate picture of these biodiversity values, and it has so far failed to do so. It is hard to see how RED III ‘renewable acceleration areas’ impact assessments would result in a better biophysical knowledge of the seas than the marine strategies themselves. Yet, neither within or outside of such acceleration areas are the authorities required to use and incorporate the MSFD marine strategies.

Second challenge is managing the *cumulative impact* of wind power projects. While MSFD seeks to put forward a holistic environmental goal for the status of the seas and establishes marine strategies with monitoring programmes and programmes of measures to manage human activities to this end, it currently lacks coercive power to influence planning and permitting decisions made under other EU legislation and national legislation related to energy (Soininen and Platjouw, 2019). This is the result of the legal bindingness of the MSFD targets being unclear as well as there not being sufficient linkages from MSFD to RED III instruments. Biodiversity is something to be considered in renewables projects but it can, according to RED III, be cast aside as soon as conflict between the two arises. This results in a situation where MSFD sets ambitious targets in line with the EGD – and to manage cumulative impact – but does not establish legally binding and integrated pathways for their implementation (Soininen and Platjouw, 2019, and Puharinen and Belinskij, 2022). This is likely to result in a situation where the EU Climate Law and RED III targets are implemented without careful consideration of marine biodiversity. In practice, this means that marine wind power projects are being located based on business and energy security interests, rather than the environment.

Third challenge is that under RED III, offshore wind power projects automatically fulfil the ‘overriding public interest’ requirement as established by art. 14(1)(d) of MSFD. This means that offshore wind power projects have – even if the MSFD were considered legally binding – a clear substantive legal pathway to cast aside (m)any biodiversity considerations. This results in a situation where the (marine) biodiversity branch of the EGD is severely crippled from the legal perspective.

The three challenges above *could* be alleviated somewhat with careful maritime spatial planning. This would require that as part of MSPs, the member state authorities would establish ‘go to’ or ‘no go’ areas to wind power, in line with RED III, and would conduct biophysical impact assessments to match these designations. The full functionality of such a system would require MSPs to be legally binding with capacity to integrate sectoral (energy, biodiversity) interests, and with legal force to steer energy development away from biodiversity hot spots. These criteria are, however, tricky to fulfil and for instance in Finland both the capacity of MSP authorities to produce additional biophysical knowledge and the capacity of MSPs to direct the location of energy projects are very limited (Soininen et. al., 2024). This is so because MSPs in Finland are not legally binding, the planning relies heavily on existing knowledge of marine

biophysical characteristics without producing new knowledge in the process to aid spatial allocation, and the MSPs do really coordinate or help in integrating (solving potential conflicts) between sectors and actors. As a consequence, in the Finnish example, MSPs add to the fragmentation of the governance landscape rather than promote coherence.

7.6 Conclusion on coherence

At the moment, the climate and energy policies pushing for increased offshore wind power generation do not sufficiently consider biodiversity and establish various procedural and substantive easements from biodiversity protections. This results in potential incoherence particularly with Natura 2000 and species protection objectives established under the Habitats and Birds Directives as well as the marine environmental quality elements of the Marine Strategy Framework Directive, such as the integrity of the sea-floor bottom and underwater noise. A particular cross-cutting challenge is lack of knowledge on the marine biodiversity and the impact of offshore wind power development on it.

As discussed in chapter 3, the MSFD protects marine biodiversity much more comprehensively than the Nature Directives. The installations of wind turbines can cause hydromorphological alterations and damage to habitats. But, in addition, such installations can also cause adverse impacts on sea-floor integrity which are, so far, not appropriately considered in the permitting processes related to individual renewable energy projects, nor in the processes leading up to the designation of renewables acceleration areas. The Maritime Spatial Planning Directive could, in principle, contribute to identify the most optimal areas for offshore wind projects from a MSFD perspective (for example areas with less vulnerable bottom floor habitats). However, so far, marine spatial planning under the MSPD has not been used systematically to ensure such a balance, but rather to ensure economic growth in the marine environment and to maximize sea space for new developments.

The use of exemptions in RED III to ensure that the Nature Directives and WFD do not slow down or complicate the permitting processes is also noteworthy. The rules in the environmental directives ensure that such projects do the least harm as possible on habitats and species, or the good quality status of the waters. The easements and exemptions provided through RED III, including the presumed overriding public interests of renewable energy projects, actually makes it more difficult to ensure decoupling. It has been argued that the transition towards more renewable energy sources will also be beneficial for the protection biodiversity, yet an increase in renewable energy installations and infrastructures will have some impact on marine biodiversity during and after the lifetime of these projects.

III Possible explanations for incoherence

8. Constitutional context for EU policies

The CrossGov methodological framework (CrossGov Deliverable 1.2) contains three overarching categories of explanatory variables that may explain the level of policy coherence and contribution to EGD: governmental organizational structures, science-policy interfaces and stakeholder involvement. Governmental organization structures refer to governmental structures that set the framework within which policies are formulated and implemented, including structures establishing the involvement and responsibilities of governmental organizations and coordination mechanisms (CrossGov Deliverable 1.2). EU policies – such as those studied above – are adopted, interpreted and enforced within the institutional framework of EU constitutional law, or general EU law. Accordingly, the EU constitutional and administrative law structures governing the EU’s legislative and policy formulation competences, institutional law setup of EU institutions, the general principles of EU law as well as the general structures shaping the implementation and enforcement of EU law constitute factors that may explain the level of (in)coherence found at the level of EU law and policy. The following sections will examine these structures in the light of how they might affect the coherence challenges identified above.

8.1 The legal bases of the policies

The European Union’s political and legislative powers are based on the principle of conferral, meaning that the EU may only act within the limits of the competences that EU Member States have conferred upon it in the Treaties to attain the objectives set out therein Art 5 of the Treaty on European Union (TEU)). The EU’s power to act thus comes with some preconditions for the material scope within which the Union is entitled to act (competence) as well as on the manner in which it must act (procedure) (Art 5(2) TEU). In a nutshell, each EU policy must find a specific legal basis in the Treaties and the objectives, principles and limitations attached to that legal basis determine the policy’s scope, the objectives it pursues and its legal design (See case 45/86 *Commission v Council*). The Treaties present various provisions on thematically limited competences in distinct policy areas. Thus, the institutional law setting of EU policy-making is structured to distinct policy areas, each shaped by their own core objectives, principles and limits to EU’s powers in that field; these include e.g. environmental policy (Art 191 TFEU), internal market (Art 26 and 114 TFEU), fisheries policy (Art 38 TFEU), agricultural policy (Art 38 and 39 TFEU) and energy policy (Art 194 TFEU). Secondary legislation – directives and regulations – are adopted under these specific Treaty bases and thus, the legal basis for each policy area as articulated in the Treaties fixes some ground-rules for the format and content of legislative intervention by the Union.

The key EU policies for that should operationalise and deliver the GD objectives in the marine areas that have been analysed above – the MSFD, WFD, Nature Directives, ND – have been adopted pursuant to the EU’s environmental policy competence (Art 191 of the Treaty on the Functioning of the European Union (TFEU)) and the related legal basis (Art 192 TFEU). Article 191(1) TFEU lays down the overarching objectives that EU environment policy should

contribute to, including preservation, protection and improvement of the quality of the environment and prudent and rational utilisation of natural resources. In addition, Article 191(2) provides the principles on which the Union's environment policy should be based; these include aiming to achieve a high level of protection while taking into account the diversity of situations in different regions, the prevention principle and the polluter pays principle.²⁹ Article 191(3) provides specific factors that should be taken into account in preparing EU environmental policy, that is, available scientific and technical data, environmental conditions in the various regions of the Union, the potential benefits and costs of action or lack of action and of the economic and social development of the Union as a whole and the balanced development of its regions. Accordingly, the EU environmental policy is fundamentally geared towards promoting the inclusion of scientific knowledge and aiming towards effective environmental protection, both of which are generally recognised as positive coherence features. Notably, considerations of economic and social development have also been integrated in the core of the policy field, meaning that account should be given to these factors in preparing EU environmental legislation.

In turn, the sectoral economic policies – in this assessment, the CAP, RED III and CFP – are based on different Treaty bases, which set their own policy objectives, principles and procedural frames that shape the secondary legislation enacted based on them. The CAP has been adopted pursuant to the EU's agricultural policy competence (Arts 38(4) and 39 TFEU) and the related legal basis (Art 43(2) TFEU, also Art 42 concerning competition rules). According to Art 39(1) TFEU, the objectives of common agricultural policy are to “increase agricultural productivity by promoting technical progress and by ensuring the rational development of agricultural production and the optimum utilisation of the factors of production, in particular labour” as well as to ensure a fair standard of living for the agricultural community, to stabilise markets, to assure availability of supplies and to ensure that supplies reach consumers at reasonable prices. Moreover, regarding the operationalisation of the CAP account is to be given to the social structure of agriculture and structural and natural disparities between the various agricultural regions and “the fact that in the Member States agriculture constitutes a sector closely linked with the economy as a whole” (Art 39(2) TFEU). Notably, the EU constitutional legal basis for CAP is predominantly economic and about market-optimisation, which does not internalise environmental considerations and is even counterproductive to environmental policy, here referring to the primary objective of increasing agricultural productivity. The same is true for the CFP, which forms a part of the EU's agricultural and fisheries policy competence (Arts 38–44), and the specific legal basis (Art 43(2) and (3) TFEU).³⁰

²⁹ The other principles include the precautionary principle and the source principle (environmental damage should as a priority be rectified at its source).

³⁰ Notably, Art. 43(3) TFEU excludes measures on ‘fixing prices, levies, aid and quantitative limitations and on the fixing and allocation of fishing opportunities’ from co-decision making and instead, gives the authority to adopt such measures to the Council alone.

The RED III, in turn, is based on both the EU environmental policy and energy policy competences (Art 191 and the related legal basis (Art 192(1) and 194(2) TFEU). The environmental legal basis for the Directive relates to the EU environmental policy's objective of promoting measures combating climate change. With regards to the EU energy policy competence, Art 194(1) TFEU outlines that the Union's energy policy is driven by the establishment and functioning of the internal market as well as the need to preserve and improve the environment. Thus, the fundamental objectives for the policy area encompass market-optimisation objectives – promoting the interconnection of energy networks, ensuring the functioning of the energy market and the security of energy supply – but also an environmental objective to 'promote energy efficiency and energy saving and the development of new and renewable forms of energy'. Accordingly, while Arts 194 and 191 TFEU clearly encompass the EU's role in promoting forms of renewable energy, at the same time they provide that the EU is both empowered and obligated to safeguard biodiversity and the quality of (aquatic) environments, which requires that the Union adopt measures to prevent potential adverse ecological impacts of renewables development (Huhta et. al., 2024).

Nevertheless, it should be noted that neither Art 191 nor Art 194 TFEU outline any mechanisms or principles for reconciling different objectives within the environmental policy competence and the environmental aspects of energy policy, here particularly the climate action and biodiversity protection. This setting has the effect to allow adoption of policies with a sing-minded focus on some environmental aspects, like the RED III on climate mitigation. Furthermore, the convergence of EU climate policy and energy policy competence and the development of law in these policy areas has been for a long time quite evident, marking a stark contrast to the situation with EU biodiversity and energy policy (Romppanen and Huhta, 2023). Consequently, while the RED III does recognise the trade-off between climate goals and biodiversity goals in relation to the development of bioenergy, it continues to disregard sustainability concerns related to other forms of renewable energy, such as the biodiversity harms of offshore wind development (Huhta et. al, 2024).

It should also be noted that the Treaties contain some explicit provisions of constitutional nature related to policy coherence, especially for environmental protection. First, Art 7 TFEU provides a general provision that the 'Union shall ensure consistency between its policies and activities, taking all of its objectives into account and in accordance with the principle of conferral of powers'. Second, Art 11 stipulates that '[e]nvironmental protection requirements must be integrated into the definition and implementation of the Union's policies and activities, in particular with a view to promoting sustainable development', which is also known as the principle of environmental integration. Third, environmental integration in connection with the principle of sustainable development is also enshrined in art. 37 of the Charter of Fundamental Rights of the EU (EUCFR) that – contrary to the integration clause enshrined in art. 11 TFEU – makes explicit reference to the policy objective of a "high level of environmental protection" and the objective of "the improvement of the quality of the environment". Together, these provisions could form a clear constitutional mandate and an obligation to ensure the coherence of sectoral policies towards promoting the environmental policy's objectives, recently outlined in the GD (Krämer, 2013 and Sjäfjell, 2014). In reality, however, their legal weight on ensuring

coherence has remained rather small, and the EU organs enjoy a degree of discretion in implementing the enshrined principle and in weighing it against competing principles or interests (de Sadeleer, 2020). In the jurisprudence of the CJEU, environmental integration principles have mainly constitutes legal grounds to justify and enable the inclusion of (some) environmental aspects into sectoral policies.³¹ In contrast, they have not been recognise to have much capacity to direct or force wide integration as a condition of validity for sectoral laws.³² Against this background, the objectives and principles enshrined in the legal basis for sectoral policies – such as the legal basis for CAP – are a much stronger constitutional conditions shaping the design and content of those policies than the general principles of coherence and environmental integration.

Furthermore, the practical administrative and organisational aspects for EU law-making may affect the decree of coherence between environmental law and economic sectoral legislation. In the EU, the legislative power lies with European parliament and the Council, but the Commission is the executive institution in the EU, which also has a constitutional prerogative with regards to the power of making legislative proposals (Art 17(2) TEU). Accordingly, the Commission is the key institution regarding the preparation of EU law, overseeing its implementation and enforcing it. The Commission is formally composed of the “political” level – the president and her/his College – and the administrative infrastructure, consisting of Directorates-Generals (DG) and Services. Similarly to national ministries, the DGs are specialised in specific policy areas and thus operate ‘vertically’ in those policy fields; thus, each DG has the mandate to administer, prepare legislation and oversee implementation for only the policies within their area. Notably, the Commission’s rules of procedure require the DG’s to ‘work in close cooperation and in coordinated fashion’ and there is also a formal requirement imposed on the DGs to consult other departments associated or concerned and to ‘endeavour to frame a proposal that has the agreement of the departments consulted’.³³ Nevertheless, these provisions are rather general and procedural in nature, and thus cannot be regarded as strong guarantees for ensuring policy coherence in the midst of the sectoral structure of the DGs.

8.2 Legal structures governing the implementation and enforcement of EU law

The nature of the EU’s competence has implications also regarding the room that the Member States have in implementation for example for taking measures to increase policy coherence if

³¹ Case C-62/88 Greece v Council ECLI:EU:C:1990:153 paras 19-20; case C-300/89 Commission v Council ECLI:EU:C:1991:244 paras 22-24; case C-336/00 Huber ECLI:EU:C:2002:509 para. 36; case C-440/05 Commission v Council ECLI:EU:C:2007:625 para. 60.

³² Case C-341/95 Gianni Bettati v Safety Hi-Tech Srl ECLI:EU:C:1998:353 paras 34-35 and 53; Austria v Parliament and the Council, opinion of AG Geelhoed, cit. para. 59; E.ON Biofor Sverige AB cit. paras 50, 64-70. See Jans, 2011 and Karageorgou, 2023. The Environmental Integration Principle in EU Law: Normative Content and Functions also in Light of New Developments, such as the European Green Deal. European Papers, Vol. 8, 2023, No 1, pp. 159-189, 171–173.

³³ Art 21 of the Rules of Procedure of the Commission [C(2000) 3614]. OJ L 308, 8.12.2000, s. 26—34.

and when there are caveats, fragmentation or incoherence present at the level of EU policy design. EU environmental, agricultural, internal market and energy policy fall under a shared competence between the EU and the Member States (Art 4(2)(a), (d), (e) and (i) TFEU). In turn, fisheries policy partly falls under shared competence (Art 4(2)(d) TFEU), yet the ‘conservation of marine biological resources’, in other words, fixing the fishing quotas, falls under exclusive competence of the EU (Art 3(1)(d) TFEU).

Shared competence means that both the Union and the Member States may enact legislation in this area, but Member States are to exercise their competence only to the extent that the Union has not exercised, or has decided to cease exercising, its competence. In other words, the Member States may not legislate in a manner that would contravene EU legislation, but they may adopt rules to complement EU legislation, especially such that go beyond the EU’s rules towards promoting the policy objectives in the relevant field. Furthermore, the EU exercising of its competence is governed by the principles of subsidiarity and proportionality. This means that the EU may only take action if it is more effective than action taken at the national, regional or local level, and furthermore, action may only be taken to the extent that is necessary to achieve the pursued result (Art 5 TEU). Often these principles have inherently shaped the legal design of EU acts, providing flexible rules and obligations as well as exemptions which the Member States may utilise in fitting the legal regime better into their national circumstances.

Accordingly, the discretion that remains with the Member States provides potential for promoting policy coherence; if and when there are gaps, fragmentation or outright incoherence at the level of EU policy design, Member States may have the opportunity to adopt complementary legislation to mitigate such coherence challenges at the national level. However, it must be remembered that the competence to legislate is only provided to Member States in so far it does not interfere with or contravene the EU’s legislation in the field. In other words, the Member States have an opportunity to adopt national legislation that go beyond the EU’s minimum harmonisation in certain fields, for example environmental policy.³⁴ Thus, the Member States may in principle adopt more stringent controls on environmental impacts of sectors, such as agricultural nutrient emissions, decide to legally protect more habitats and species than what the EU Nature legislation provides or apply strict conditions for permitting offshore wind power facilities. However, when such actions would concern policy fields or sections for which the EU has provided legislation – such as offshore energy – the Member States are also bound by the supremacy of that EU legislation and may not use their legislative capacity to contravene the EU legislation adopted to promote the objectives of that policy field.

The problem was particularly elevated regarding questions where the environmental considerations clashed with the CFP, because the conservation of marine biological resources under fisheries policy falls within the exclusive competence of the EU (Appleby and Harrison, 2019). The EU’s exclusive competence does not cover all aspects of fisheries, however, and competence over other fisheries matters are shared between the EU and the Member States (Art

³⁴ The competence of Member States maintaining or introducing more stringent protective measures than those adopted by the EU under environmental policy has also been specifically pronounced in Art 193 TFEU.

4(2)(d) TFEU). Nevertheless, the existence of exclusive competence for the EU related to marine conservation in the fisheries sector has implications on legal clarity and practical capacities of the Member States to exercise their part of the shared competence for nature protection purposes. Indeed, the precise division between these different competences is complex in the context of fisheries management, especially regarding conservation due to the potential overlap between fisheries measures and environmental measure (ibid.). This is further complicated by the difference in legislative competences in the different parts of the marine areas due to the division of marine zones as well as the limitations on state jurisdiction on shipping under the UNCLOS.

9. Other explanatory factors for policy (in)coherence

As noted above, the CrossGov methodological framework (CrossGov Deliverable 1.2) contains three overarching categories of explanatory variables that may explain the level of policy coherence and contribution to EGD: governmental organizational structures, science-policy interfaces and stakeholder involvement. The previous subsection included an account of possible legal institutional and governance organization structures enshrined in the EU constitutional law that can explain the coherence issues detected in the EU policies analysed in section II of this report. However, not all factors contributing to the level of coherence in policies are legal in their nature. Such factors can include political will, commitment and leadership, societal and political interests, budgetary imperatives and financial resources, clear roles and responsibilities, development and use of data and knowledge, involvement of knowledge providers, and more (CrossGov Deliverable 1.2). As these explanatory factors are not captured by legal desk analysis of the policies, a series of interviews of experts working in the European Commission on the relevant policy fields was conducted to gain an understanding of their perspectives on possible factors that have influenced or are influencing policy coherence in the different EGD clusters.

A total of six actors from relevant DGs were interviewed, two each from DG MARE, DG ENVI and DG Energy. Three addressed the offshore energy and biodiversity cluster, one the agriculture and pollution cluster and two the fisheries and biodiversity cluster. Interviews were conducted online through the tool Zoom. In preparation of the interview, the experts were provided in advance with a background document (one-pager, Annex II) summarising the core findings of the coherence assessment of the respective cluster and a list of questions (see Annex I).

9.1 Consolidating experts of EU policymaking on explanatory factors behind policy incoherence

The interviewees were selected based on their expertise and affiliation in the relevant units of the European Commission's Directorate General's engaged in the EU policymaking related to the EGD clusters; however, the availability of persons affected significantly on the number of interviews and the coverage of different DGs in the final interviewee pool. Each interview was linked to one of the three clusters, formulated for the coherence analysis, that include a relation between key economic activity and one of the EGD's environmental objectives: the agriculture and pollution cluster, the fisheries and biodiversity cluster and the offshore wind energy and biodiversity cluster. The methodology applied in the study generated valuable outcomes, particularly by verifying the findings of the coherence analysis and providing expert insights on possible explanatory factors behind the detected coherence challenges.

Table 4 Experts interviewed for the assessment.

Name	Affiliation	Interviewed in connection to cluster
Interviewee 4	European Commission, DG Env	Agriculture and pollution
Interviewee 1	European Commission, DG Mare	Fisheries and biodiversity
Interviewee 6	European Commission, DG Mare	Fisheries and biodiversity
Interviewee 2	European Commission, DG Energy	Offshore wind energy and biodiversity
Interviewee 5	European Commission, DG Env	Offshore wind energy and biodiversity
Interviewee 3	European Commission, DG Energy	Offshore wind energy and biodiversity

9.2 Outcomes

On a general note, the majority of the experts recognise the inherent and unavoidable trade-offs in policymaking concerning the environment and economic sectors utilising and affecting natural resources and the trade-offs between different EGD goals. It was highlighted by one of the experts that traditional policies like the CAP and CFP face inherent contradictions between long-term economic support and environmental objectives, which creates a challenge of transitioning these sector-supporting policies to align with environmental objectives. Many of the experts consider that the initial Commission’s Communication on the EGD in general and its “do no harm” principle in particular, represented a huge positive change in terms of bringing together a comprehensive set of objectives and promoting consistency between policies, but subsequent political and policy developments concerning have sometimes led to opposite direction, giving rise to coherence challenges. It was highlighted by one of the experts that there is a growing awareness of the complex interconnections between climate, energy, biodiversity, and carbon sinks, which makes policy-making more complex and challenging but at the same time underscores the need for coherence.

With regard to the research aim of verifying the results of the coherence analysis, the experts largely agreed with the findings of the legal analysis on the coherence challenges in the clusters, albeit that some minor comments were expressed to clarify certain aspects and noting some additional aspects. The interviews also provided valuable insights into potential explanatory

factors. For all three clusters some factors related to governmental organisation, science-policy-society and public participation were identified by the experts. The interviews also provided some input about how coherence could be improved or is at the risk of being further weakened in the next phases of policymaking, particularly implementation at the Member States' level. Moreover, the experts provided their insights on how the detected coherence challenges could be mitigated and policy coherence improved.

9.2.1 Main outcomes related to verifying the coherence analysis

Agriculture and pollution

The interviewees confirmed that coherence assessment for the cluster – as presented in the one-page summary (Annex II) – is agreeable. Minor comments were made about clarifying the role of the ND and the WFD as main policies addressing agricultural pollution, while the MSFD has only a supporting role. In addition, the interviewees called for more clear recognition of the WFD's and the MSFD's nature as flexible instruments, which is intentional and entail positive features allowing local solutions to local problems that should also be reflected in the analysis. One interviewee highlighted that additional policies addressing climate change, air pollution, and water pollution, including the recent revision of the Urban Wastewater Treatment Directive, are expected to bring positive results for the zero-pollution ambition, particularly in reducing nutrient pollution in various water bodies. Yet, the challenges related to addressing agricultural nutrient pollution remain.

It was recognised that inherent contradictions exist between economic support and environmental objectives due to past policy development; traditional policies like the CAP have long supported economic growth and now they face a contradiction of this traditional rationale and achieving environmental objectives. Despite recent developments, the transition towards environmental sustainability is challenging. The interviewee considered that the main challenge is to align these sector-supporting policies with environmental goals, ensuring that they contribute to good environmental status while addressing social complexities and resistance, especially in agriculture. As sectoral policies often prioritize economic growth, they potentially conflict with environmental objectives unless these objectives are integrated into the policies themselves. According to the interviewee, this integration is crucial to avoid typical barriers, such as coordination problems among national authorities and political decisions favouring short-term voter reactions. Furthermore, it was recognised that environmental policies should ensure their objectives are defined clearly enough and that their legal weight is strong enough to influence sectoral policies.

Fisheries and biodiversity

Experts interviewed about the fisheries and biodiversity cluster generally recognise the coherence issues summarised in the one-pager (Annex II). Challenges with art. 11 of the CFP were recognised in the interviews; according to one interviewee, the provision is not functioning well in promoting biodiversity conservation due to its complexity and the ease with which a single Member State's disagreement can prevent action being taken. The introduction of the new concept of 'strict protection' and the related 10 % area-coverage objective with the

EU biodiversity strategy were regarded as strengthening biodiversity protection, but also adding to the complexity of the policies and legislation, especially as ‘strict protection’ has not yet been defined clearly. One of the interviewees underscored that the implementation of the CFP on the one hand and nature legislation on the other is different, since the CFP is a policy that is highly controlled in a centralised manner at the EU level. According to the interviewee, the CFP is based on scientific advice and assessment and the centralisation is working well, even though some destructive methods, like bottom-trawling, have not been eliminated. One interviewee also mentioned that there is an effort to align the policy cycles of different regulatory frameworks like the MSPD and the CFP to facilitate better coherence; while it may not be possible to legally enforce such alignment, the EU is encouraging this practice through guidance documents and showcasing best practices.

The interviewees mentioned the 2023 EU Fisheries Action Plan as an example of a policy that has aimed at rectifying some of the coherence challenges between the CFP and nature protection legislation. Especially the action plan’s aim of eliminating bottom trawling in MPAs by 2030 was mentioned as a positive action. Other actions in the plan were also highlighted, such as improving the selectivity of fishing gear, limiting impacts on sensitive marine species, enhancing scientific data to support measures, ensuring effective governance, and fostering synergies between fisheries and environmental authorities and stakeholders. Yet it was recognised that the plan’s implementation is still in process in the Member States. In addition, the 2021 Commission Communication for Sustainable Blue Economy was raised as a policy document entailing a holistic approach that fosters coherence among different policies and challenges in maritime sectors like fisheries and aquaculture. Moreover, the interviewees raised the ongoing MSFD review up as a possibility to ensure that the Directive contributes effectively to the EGD goals and to address coherence issues in the fisheries policy cluster.

Offshore wind energy and biodiversity

All experts interviewed in connection to the offshore wind energy and biodiversity cluster recognised the inherent trade-offs in policymaking in the cluster, albeit that one of the interviewees suggested that the perceived incoherences might be less significant than they appear. The coherence analysis presented in the one-page summary (Annex II) was generally agreed upon by the experts. The acceleration of permitting procedures for renewable energy was seen to imply that environmental safeguards, such as the Environmental Impact Assessment Directive, have been watered-down. Furthermore, the fact that in acceleration areas renewable projects are presumed to be of overriding public interest were regarded to make it challenging to demonstrate a higher public interest not supporting the projects. These changes were seen to complicate the assessment of specific local impacts and the inclusion of localized public consultations.

Some remarks were however made about the need to clarify certain aspects of the policies in the coherence analysis and reflect them accurately in the one-page summary. Two interviewees highlighted a need to clarify that while renewable acceleration areas should not be designated in Natura 2000 areas, the RED does not entail any general prohibitions to locate renewable energy projects in Natura 2000 areas. Acceleration areas should be designated where significant

environmental impacts are not expected and should exclude Natura 2000 sites. However, the Natura 2000 legislation is flexible in a way that the protection does not entail exclusion of human activities in the area, and renewable energy projects may be deployed in those areas as long as they comply with the applicable rules and regulations. In addition, one interviewee underscored that Art 16(2) of RED addressing the simplified permitting also includes a provision about innovative mitigation measures, which aims to promote the use of new technologies to mitigate environmental impacts like negative impacts on biodiversity, which should be noted in the coherence analysis. The interviewee also highlighted that RED does not automatically declare renewable energy projects as fulfilling the overriding public interest requirement but instead, establishes a rebuttable presumption. As established in the RED recitals, this presumption does not apply when there is clear evidence of significant adverse environmental impacts that cannot be mitigated or compensated.

9.2.2 Explanatory factors behind the detected coherence challenges

For each cluster, experts recognised factors related to all three categories of explanatory factors that may influence the level of coherence across policies. These findings are discussed in relation to each three categories of explanatory factors. Annex II includes a presentation of the factors identified per policy cluster.

Governmental organisational structures

Most of the reflections related to governmental organisational structures by the interviewees were related to organisational behaviour and collaboration or mandates and responsibilities of different organisations and units. In addition to these subcategories, only a few other factors were mentioned. These included the co-decision-making procedure in the legislative process, which was identified as to negatively affect coherence by one of the interviewees. The separation between the political level (commissioners and their cabinets) and the administrative level was considered to lead to gaps in information by one of the interviewees. In turn, some interviewees mentioned different coordination mechanisms within and outside the DGs as positive factors for coherence. These included joint events organised by different DGs, specific units tasked with collaboration and coordination, inter-service groups bringing together all relevant DGs for a certain topic or theme, and expert meetings on different policies involving several DGs as well as national ministries.

Many interviewees brought up factors influencing coherence that can be categorised relating to organisational behaviour and collaboration. These included both factors that were regarded to support and increase policy coherence as well as factors negatively affecting coherence. Some interviewees mentioned governance and policy-development being carried out in silos, which makes it difficult to change longstanding mindsets focused on specific areas. Yet it was remarked that there has been significant improvement in this regard within the current Commission compared to the previous one, leading to more integrated and holistic policy development. Particularly the representatives of sectoral economic policy DGs regarded that there is good communication and sharing of information between the DGs as well as close cooperation and involvement with DGs ENER, MARE and ENV to align objectives and

address challenges. In turn, representatives from DG ENV consider that while collaboration under the EGD between DGs was initially constructive, external pressures related to particularly RePowerEU changed the dynamics towards neglecting environmental protection aspects. One interviewee also brought up that internal discussions within large DGs like DG Energy and DG Agriculture can be influenced by individual positions and diversity of opinions over e.g. green practices for agriculture, which can complicate internal consensus.

The experts also raised a variety of points that can be categorised as relating to mandates and responsibilities of different organisations and units. It was noted by several interviewees that the inherent structural setup that the Commission is organised with, where DGs specialize in certain sectors (energy, environmental, maritime, climate), leads to different views, approaches and priorities between the DGs. This was seen as having negative impacts on policy coherence as the DGs implement the EGD within their competences. Yet, one of the interviewees regarded that the organisational divide could also be beneficial for policy coherence, as it fosters necessary advocacy for specific objectives and at the same time requires communication and finding a balanced middle-ground.

Many of the interviewees, related to all three clusters, mentioned the joint commissioner for DG ENV and DG MARE as a positive factor for fostering coordination and collaboration and improving policy coherence. Some interviewees pondered over ideas of establishing more overarching mandates in the Commission. These included creating an Ocean DG by integrating different units dealing with marine related policies into a broader ocean-focused directorate or appointing a ‘Commissioner for the ecological transition’, in line with the examples of France or Spain, to foster a common direction and achieve better coherence across policies. The post of Executive Vice-President for the Green Deal, which was situated hierarchically above the Commissioners for energy, climate and environment, was mentioned as a positive development compared to the organisations of previous Commissions. Yet, one interviewee raised concerns related to such initiatives, underscoring that maintaining a separate DG environment is important to ensure a strong, independent voice for environmental objectives within sectoral policy development.

Science-policy-society interfaces

With regard to SPS interfaces, the interviewees had partly conflicting views on the extent to which scientific knowledge has informed policy design and improved coherence. In particular, representatives of DG ENV mentioned that there are still many knowledge gaps in understanding the marine environment and offshore impacts, especially cumulated ones. While the MSFD is regarded to have advanced knowledge production, these experts emphasised that scientific data still needs to be improved to determine GES under the MSFD. This includes a need for concrete methodologies, threshold values, aggregation rules, and assessment methods to define GES. It was regarded that defining GES more clearly in a way that sets limits for sectoral policies would make it more enforceable; currently, lack of full scientific determination of GES has made it rather abstract, which was seen to create a challenge for policy coherence.

In turn, representatives of sectoral economic DG's considered that the relevant policies, like the CFP and the MSPD, are already based on and require comprehensive scientific evidence. These experts also brought up that there is a requirement for the Commission to conduct impact assessment and public consultation prior to proposing any policy or law. Relatedly, however, an interviewee from DG ENV highlighted the importance of having solid evidence to support environmental priorities in discussions with sectoral DGs, whose primary focus are rather on e.g. security of supply of energy than environmental concerns. It was also mentioned that while standard policy-making includes conducting impact assessments, formulating different options and collecting background data, the crisis following the Russia's war of aggression towards Ukraine created a sense of urgency, especially for the preparation of RePowerEU, which led to fewer consultations being carried out. This relaxation of impact assessments and consultations extends to implementation, as RED III has introduced provisions on weakening such requirements in the adoption of renewable energy projects. The interviewee mentioned that there are still knowledge gaps regarding both positive biodiversity impacts of offshore energy projects but also unknown negative impacts. According to this expert, the scientific uncertainty highlights the need for new installations to include a comprehensive monitoring system, with data available for researchers to analyse impacts and overall biodiversity, coupled with an open access to this monitoring data to enhance understanding of offshore impacts.

With regard to the fisheries policy cluster, it was recognised by one interviewee that there appears to be different scientific experts contributing to the CFP and to the MSFD with varied expertise and methodologies, which may affect coherence. The interviewee noted that there are ongoing discussions about moving towards multi-species, ecosystem-based scientific assessments under the CFP instead of the current single species assessments, which arguably could foster more coherence in the scientific bases of the CFP and the MSFD.

Several interviewees raised up the role of Horizon-EU framework, specifically the mission to restore our ocean and waters, in supporting policy-development, fostering coherence of objectives and finding solutions to. Yet, one expert regarded that the SPS interface is a weak link in the implementation process; EU-funded projects and their research outcomes are rarely adequately translated into practical tools for implementation, which indicates a gap between knowledge-production and implementation and creates a bottleneck in the implementation process. Another interviewee also acknowledged that there is an issue with timing for the Horizon projects, as the results are often available with delay, which does not necessarily match policy-cycles although it was stressed that the knowledge generated by those projects is still valuable.

Stakeholder involvement

With regard to factors related to stakeholder involvement, the interviewees brought up the more formal public participation procedures as well as more informal factors, such as lobbying. Generally, the interviewees recognised the importance of stakeholder engagement especially in the implementation of EU policies and that maintaining an open dialogue with a diverse range of stakeholders – including Member States, regional authorities, neighbouring countries, local coastal communities, industry and academia – may foster cooperation and coherence.

Many interviewees emphasised that the EU legislative drafting procedure includes several participatory processes. However, one expert noted that public consultations do not always represent a cross-section of the EU population and stakeholders as there has been large campaigns by citizens and NGOs to quickly generate substantial amount of input and influence the outcome of consultations. One interviewee commenting on the offshore wind cluster raised that there are also regular meetings with stakeholders from different groups, including industry, NGOs, and academia, during the preparation of initiatives that complements the engagement with other DGs and Member States. The opportunity of launching citizen initiatives to suggest new European policies was also mentioned.

Apart from these standard formal participatory mechanisms, some specific initiatives and mechanisms ensuring further stakeholder involvement were mentioned. The three sea-based initiatives in the Atlantic, Western Mediterranean, and Black Sea, and two of the four macro-regional strategies in the Baltic and Adriatic-Ionian Seas were regarded as successful initiatives in engaging stakeholders. Also, a blue forum created under the sustainable blue economy strategy, a series of workshops organised by DG MARE and the collaboration between ENTSO-E and the Renewable Grid Initiative were mentioned as positive initiatives. Regarding the fisheries policy cluster, it was brought up that the CFP specifically involves advisory councils that are intended to facilitate dialogue among representatives from the fisheries sector, scientists, and NGOs. Yet, it was noted that there is currently an ongoing boycott of the council by some major NGOs that claim that the representation in the council is unbalanced.

Regarding more informal engagement, the majority of the interviewees recognise lobbying having an impact on policy focus and that there are imbalances in the access of EU policymakers. It was noted by one of the experts that the distinction between lobbying and science-policy inputs is sometimes blurred, as for example NGOs and think tanks publish reports with specific messages to influence policymaking. It was mentioned by several interviewees that organisations with more resources, including both industry and civil society groups, have a more favourable position while smaller stakeholders and local groups are sometimes underrepresented due to a lack of opportunities to enter structured dialogues. Yet, the level of influence of different stakeholders can also change based on timing and political priorities; one interviewee raised that in the beginning of the EGD, influence by industrial and NGO actors was more balanced, but for example during the RePowerEU initiative, energy companies had significantly more power to influence decisions. Moreover, the interviewee noted that while information about meetings and consultations with lobbying organisations is in principle publicly available by request, this is not effectively communicated and many citizens are unaware about the possibility to request information, which undermines transparency in practise.

It was also raised in several interviews that there are imbalances in the representation of operators and civil groups within the larger industrial and NGO actors. The industrial representatives are prone to represent the interests of their larger-scale, economically stronger members, while the interests smaller-scale producers – such as small-scale farmers or artisanal fishers – are often overshadowed. One interviewee assessed that as smaller-scale activities

typically have a lesser environmental impact, policies tailored to large-scale operations may disproportionately burden small-scale operators. Similar remarks were made in relation to civil society actors, where representation tends to favour larger NGOs, sidelining local organizations that work directly with affected sectors. It was noted by one of the interviewees that there are also differences in this regard between countries; in countries with strong, effective coordination of national, regional, and local engagement, stakeholders are better organized and more present in European forums, while in countries with weaker organisational structures the groups may struggle to have their voices heard.

Table 5 Explanatory factors identified in the expert interviews.

	Agriculture and pollution	Fisheries and biodiversity	Offshore wind energy and biodiversity
Governmental organisational structures			
Legal (constitutional) system structures		(-) co-decision procedure in the legislative process	(-) separation between the political level (commissioners and their cabinets) and the administrative level
Organisational behaviour and collaboration	(-) working in silos (-) difficulty in coordinating between authorities at both EU and national levels	(+) good communication between DG ENV and MARE (+) European political goals and policies are collectively developed by several European institutions	(-) working in silos (+) close cooperation and involvement with DGs ENER, MARE and ENV to align objectives and address challenges (-) collaboration under the EGD between DGs initially constructive, but the pressures of RepowerEU changed the dynamics (-) discussions within large DGs (ENER, AGRI) influenced by

			individual positions not reflecting the official stance of the DG, which complicates internal consensus
Clear mandates and responsibilities	<p>(+) proposals to merge units, such as creating an Ocean DG, a broader ocean-focused directorate</p> <p>(+) joint commissioner for DG ENV and DG Mare</p>	<p>(-) specialisation of DGs leads to different approaches and incoherence as DGs implement the EGD within their competences</p> <p>(+) joint commissioner for DG ENV and DG MARE</p>	<p>(-) division into DGs with different priorities</p> <p>(+) specialisation of DGs fosters necessary advocacy for specific objectives and requires communication and finding a balanced middle-ground</p> <p>(+) joint commissioner for DG MARE and DG ENV</p> <p>(+) Commissioner for the ecological transition</p> <p>(+) the post of Executive Vice-President for the Green Deal, hierarchically above the Commissioners for energy, climate and environment</p>
Coordination mechanisms		<p>(+) the role of DG MARE E3 in supporting sea-based and macro-regional strategies, which promote cooperation</p>	<p>(+) an inter-service group bringing together all relevant DGs</p> <p>(+) joint events with DGs can facilitate</p>

		between member states and non-EU neighbouring countries on sustainable economy initiatives	inter-departmental dialogue (+) bilateral interactions of DG ENER and DG MARE (+) expert meetings including national ministries (environmental, marine policies, the MSPD)
Science-policy-society interfaces			
Science and knowledge feeding	(+) MSFD has significantly advanced knowledge production and research in various marine environment areas (-) more data and knowledge are still needed (-) GES under MSFD still not fully defined, concrete methodologies, threshold values, aggregation rules and assessment methods needed (-) SPS interface a weak link in implementation; research outcomes are not adequate translated into practical tools	(+) mandatory for the Commission to conduct impact assessment and public consultation prior to proposing any policy or law (+) integration of and connection to best available science strong in the CFP and MSPD (-) different scientific experts contribute to the CFP and the MSFD with varied expertise and methodologies (+) discussions about moving towards multi-species, ecosystem-based scientific assessments under the CFP instead of	(+) EU legislation relies on impact assessments, that provide reasoned analyses of problems, their drivers, and potential solutions, based on evidence (literature, modelling, etc.), also with the involvement of the Joint Research Centre (+) important to have solid evidence to support environmental priorities in discussions with sectoral economic DGs (DG ENER) (-) still many knowledge gaps in understanding offshore impacts,

	<p>(-) EU-funded re- search projects fail to deliver practical tools, indicates a gap between knowledge production and im- plementation</p>	<p>the current single species assessments</p> <p>(+) Horizon Europe, specifically the mission to restore our ocean and waters, beneficial for integrating objec- tives of different policy streams</p>	<p>notably cumulated ones</p> <p>(-) urgency due to crisis led to fewer public consultations in the preparation of RePower EU initia- tives and relaxation of impact-assesse- ment requirements in implementation</p> <p>(+) Horizon Europe contributes to identifying and triggering solutions to achieve various policy objectives</p> <p>(-) delays in the availability of results under Horizon Europe</p> <p>(-) knowledge gaps of offshore instal- lations pointed out in the EU offshore stra- tegy; includes uncer- tainty over positive impacts as well as unknown negative impacts</p> <p>(+) commitment un- der the offshore stra- tegy to develop re- search to improve the understanding of the- se impacts</p> <p>(-) political leaders and their cabinets</p>
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			often lack deep knowledge of specific issues, which results in a tendency to remain in "silos", show little interest in broader perspectives and adopt simplistic approaches of promoting certain technologies, like carbon capture and storage
Stakeholder involvement			
Participatory processes		<p>(+) several participatory processes in legislative drafting</p> <p>(+) opportunity to launch citizen initiatives to suggest new European policies</p> <p>(+) advisory councils as structured part of the CFP, intended to facilitate dialogue among representatives from the fisheries sector, scientists, and NGOs</p> <p>(-) currently there's a boycott by some major NGOs in the advisory council for they believe the representation is unbalanced</p> <p>(+) blue forum created after the</p>	<p>(+) several participatory processes in legislative drafting that need to be explained in the proposal</p> <p>(+) collaboration between ENTSO-E and the Renewable Grid Initiative involves various environmental NGOs to ensure environmental objectives are considered in off-shore network development</p> <p>(+) regular meetings with stakeholders from different groups, including industry, NGOs, and academia, to gather diverse inputs during the preparation of</p>

		<p>sustainable blue economy communication including various stakeholders</p> <p>(+) three sea-based initiatives in the Atlantic, Western Mediterranean, and Black Sea, and two of the four macro-regional strategies in the Baltic and Adriatic-Ionian Seas have been successful in engaging stakeholders and identifying concrete projects that promote sustainable economic actions</p> <p>(+) a series of workshops organised by DG MARE on five maritime sectors, fisheries, aquaculture, blue biotechnology, coastal maritime tourism, and marine renewables, to engage stakeholders, identify their needs and challenges, and motivate cooperation for coordinated implementation</p>	<p>initiatives that complements the engagement with other DGs and member states</p> <p>(-) public consultations not always represent a cross-section of the EU population and stakeholders as there has been large campaigns by citizens and NGOs to quickly generate substantial amount of input</p>
<p>Information campaigns and lobbying</p>	<p>(-) access to EU policymakers significantly influences the representation of different</p>	<p>(-) local groups underrepresented due to a lack of op-</p>	<p>(-) distinction between lobbying and science-policy inputs can be blurred; NGOs and think</p>

	<p>sectors, often favouring those with more resources, including both industry and civil society groups</p> <p>(-) smaller-scale producers (like farmers or artisanal fishers) overshadowed in industrial representation compared to larger-scale members</p> <p>(-) civil society representation tends to favour larger NGOs, sidelining local organisations that work directly with affected sectors</p> <p>(-) imbalanced representation and polarization can lead disproportionate burdens to smaller-scale operators and skewed policy debates that miss nuanced local collaborations</p>	<p>opportunities to enter structured dialogues</p> <p>(-) stakeholder representation varies by country; in countries with strong, effective coordination of national, regional, and local engagement, stakeholders are better organized and more present in European forums, while in countries with weaker organisational structures the groups may struggle to have their voices heard</p> <p>(+) importance of Fisheries Local Action Groups (FLAGS) for promoting a place-based and bottom-up approach in policy creation</p>	<p>tanks publishing reports with specific messages to influence policy-making</p> <p>(-) industry and significant think tanks have more resources to contribute to policy process, underrepresented groups are less visible</p> <p>(-) information about meetings and consultations publicly available in principle and in intent, but transparency is not effectively communicated and many citizens are unaware about the possibility to request information</p> <p>(-) influence of different stakeholders can change based on timing and political context</p>
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Insights into improving coherence

Many interviewees raised up some reflections on the need to ensure policy coherence in the national implementation. With regard to the fisheries cluster, it was emphasised that the responsibility for both developing and implementing fisheries action plans as well as planning and enforcing MPAs is with the Member States, and that it needs to be sure that implementation of the MPAs in particular is truly effective.

For the offshore energy cluster, it was identified that Member States have discretion which may impact policy coherence. It was mentioned that Member States may make diverse choices

between different technologies (onshore/offshore wind, solar) in scaling up renewable energy production, which are outlined in national energy and climate plans (NECPs). It was noted that these plans are still relative new instruments, but there are sections in the NECPs that could be improved, particularly in terms of comparing policy coherence and conducting impact assessments for different alternatives. The importance of local coordination was identified in fostering coherence in relation to adoption of specific projects and involving stakeholders. Furthermore, a specific consideration for offshore energy, raised up by a couple of experts, was national practices around the measures and technologies intended to mitigate the environmental impacts of offshore wind projects. One of the interviewees considered that some Member States have employed specific regulations that require certain particular mitigation measures, potentially limiting the innovation and adoption of new technologies that could prove beneficial for biodiversity considerations.

The experts also deliberated over potential solutions for improving policy coherence. Many interviewees from both DG ENV and sectoral economic DGs raised the ongoing review of the MSFD as an opportunity to improve policy coherence. The review document is expected to include an evaluation of how EU policies contribute to the MSFD's GES objective, also integrating the zero pollution goals and the EGD principles. Specific ideas included for example integrating more specific aspects in the Directive on key offshore sectors in contrast to its current rather abstract formulation. According to one of the experts from DG ENV, more clear and enforceable definitions of GES under the MSFD is crucial for ensuring that its objectives are integrated into sectoral policies and set limits to economic development. According to the interviewee, defining and integrating environmental limits into sectoral legislation is crucial also with regard to chemical contamination, as outlined in the Water Framework. Moreover, the interviewee considered it necessary to ensure coherence in funding, raising the examples of the CAP and the European Maritime and Fisheries Fund (EMFF) as examples of policies that often claim to support biodiversity and sustainability but that sometimes funds projects that contradict these goals, such as financing larger fishing vessels.

Another solution raised up by several interviewees was the role of maritime spatial planning in improving coherence. With regard to fisheries cluster, the experts noted that the MSPD entails some potential to address coherence issues related to fisheries and biodiversity, which hopefully is understood and utilised by the Member States. Relatedly, one interviewee mentioned the concept of 'Other Effective Area-Based Conservation Measures (OECM)' as another new element that Member States are considering in their planning, which admittedly adds to the complexity of biodiversity protection but is also regarded as an opportunity for better conservation strategies. The role of maritime spatial planning in improving the coherence with regards to offshore energy and biodiversity was also recognised, underscoring the need to integrate the Biodiversity Strategy and Nature Restoration Law in maritime spatial planning.

With regard to fisheries and offshore energy clusters, the role of innovation and technological development in improving coherence was also recognised. For the fisheries cluster, 'smart specialisation strategies' in the regions were seen as an opportunity to engage different stakeholder – including research and academia, public administration and the private sector –

to turn research ideas into marketable innovative products. For the offshore wind cluster, the role of Art 16(2) RED III as allowing Member States to use novel mitigation measures in controlled environments with monitoring was mentioned. The provision aims to encourage the testing and potential adoption of new technologies to mitigate environmental impacts, including nature-inclusive design for offshore developments and approaches that create positive environmental and biodiversity impacts in the sea. However, one interviewee in the energy cluster also questioned, whether the Green Deal goals, including biodiversity, should be prioritized equally or if some goals should be given higher priority and should take precedence over others in policy planning and implementation.

10. Conclusions

The report has now analysed five different clusters of policies and made conclusions for each of them. The clusters were chosen to represent a wide array of policy constellations regulating different sides of the same issue. This section will conclude with overall conclusions that has emerged from the foregoing challenging the delivery of the EGD goals and, where possible, make general conclusions on horizontal coherence in the complex policymaking for marine sustainability.

As concluded in the deliverable for WP 2.1, there are no glaring negative impacts between the policies objectives where they set out to achieve direct contradictory objectives. At times, such as for the CFP, objectives even referred to environmental policies and included them as an objective in the sector policy. As expected, however, there were indirect contradictions between the sector policies and the environmental protection policies where sector policies included one or several objectives that were designed to retain or, more often, expand the most significant pressures on the marine environment. For CAP and CFP, these contain a core logic developed during decades of maintaining or expanding a strong economic activity and social development with an environmental component added at a later stage as an outer logic without the willingness to comprise the established inner logic.

For the relationship between the environmental directives, the objectives are not contradictory and are often indirectly creating synergies where the achievement of one policy's objective enables to achievement of others. However, the environmental protection objectives form a highly fragmented landscape to the extent that it is tricky even for environmental policy and law specialists to form a clear picture of the landscape. At times it can be challenging to identify how and where an issue should be handled, creating scenarios where issues cannot be handled in the most efficient and effective way due to fragmentation. There are differences in legal bindingness, timeframes, scopes and exemptions creating further confusion. Overall, the policies' objectives have a high level of coherence and are generally geared towards achieving the EGD goals even if there is room for improvement.

The legal instruments differ greatly between the different policies. The level of coherence will as such depend on different factors and ways to improve will be highly individual for each specific policy. For such, the individual conclusion sections are to be consulted. However, there are some general trends that can be noted.

The environmental protection instruments remain at the fringe of economic activities. They lack capacity to regulate and push economic activities on their own, such as the sectors analysed in this report. Certain instruments have considerably more legal forcefulness than others. The WFD, for example, has a legal bindingness for the Member States to deliver good status of the coastal waters and mechanisms to see it through for certain kinds of pressures, such as the direct pollution, while less capable of handling diffuse pollution. Other policies lack that kind of legal bindingness, such as the MSFD which has a vague and uncertain legal status. Further, MSFD is largely omitted from RED III and even if the achievement of MSFD's objectives is an objective in itself in CFP, the legal instruments are vulnerable as they in large lack legal

bindingness for the EU and/or the Member States and the scientific input can be and has been overlooked despite its implications on MGES.

As the environmental protection directives are not capable on their own to uphold a protection level enough to achieve the EGD objectives, sector policies need to complement with effective instruments. The sector policies analysed have legal instruments designed to protect the marine environment. There is a large variety on both design and effectiveness. This is partly due to competence, but also due to political compromises made (further analysis on explanatory factors in the following section). For the RED III, it becomes evident that it is not always economic interests against protection interests but also conflicts between environmental values are needed to be handled. The CFP has legal instruments with the possibility to make far-reaching and uniform decisions on an EU level while the CAP allows for a high level of freedom for the Member States in the implementation and success in achieving EGD objectives will more likely depend on successful national implementation and vary more across the EU territory.

The ambition for environmental objectives in the sectoral policy instruments has continuously been raised throughout the last decades. Both the CAP and CFP have legal instruments that directly and indirectly connect to the environmental directives. These have historically proven to increase the coherence between the instruments and eased in the just transition of the sectors, but the application in practice has yet to produce results that indicate the achievement of the environmental objectives within the timeframes established in the directives or the EGD.

For the policy instruments, the coherence issues become more evident than they were for the policy objectives. As the objectives allow for a more generous inclusion of both economic and protection interests, the policy instruments are to put those into practice. Policy instruments for the achievement of the EGD objectives are in place, but economic interests are more often than not still in the forefront as the instruments lack forcefulness, bindingness, effectiveness, and efficiency to properly leave guarantees of the achievement of set objectives.

The analysis of explanatory factors revealed several factors that can have and are influencing the design of the policies and the detected coherence challenges therein and in the implementation. The EU constitutional and administrative law structures governing the EU's legislative and policy formulation competences and the setup of EU institutions may explain the level of (in)coherence found at the level of EU law and policy. The policies analysed are based on different Treaty bases, including environmental policy (Art 191 TFEU), internal market (Art 26 and 114 TFEU), fisheries policy (Art 38 TFEU), agricultural policy (Art 38 and 39 TFEU) and energy policy (Art 194 TFEU). While environmental policy competences require integration of socio-economic aspects into the policies, the reverse is not the case for all economic policy competences that highlight promoting the economic activities. The principle of integration of environmental protection requirements into all Union policies outlined in Art 11 TFEU has not evolved into a legally strong principle in shaping the sectoral policies either. Furthermore, the different natures of EU competences – shared or exclusive –

can affect the possibilities of Member States in striving to mitigate incoherence in national implementation.

Moreover, the expert interviews shed some light on other factors explaining incoherence, including governmental organisational structures, science-policy-interfaces and stakeholder participation. Most notable factors identified included the policy silos established by the structures of the Commission's Directorate Generals, lack of comprehensive scientific knowledge on the marine environment and varying scope of impact assessments for the policies as well as imbalances in stakeholder involvement and lobbying. With regard to governmental organisational factors, certain cooperation mechanisms as well as the joint Commissioner for DG ENV and DG MARE were perceived as having a positive influence on coherence, albeit that the organisational silos have remained. Several factors related to science-policy-interfaces were identified as negatively affecting coherence; these included the lack of full scientific knowledge and determination of good environmental status under the MSFD, the varying practices with impact-assessments and the time-lags in producing final knowledge under Horizon Europe projects. For the last category of factors, stakeholder involvement, the interviews identified imbalances in formal public consultation procedures but particularly in informal involvement and lobbying, which can influence the design of policies. The interviews also deliberated on possibilities to improve coherence at the level of national implementation and possible solutions to be examined at the EU policy development.

References

Alons, Gerry (2017). Environmental policy integration in the EU's common agricultural policy: greening or greenwashing?. *Journal of European Public Policy* 24(11), pp. 1604-1622. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13501763.2017.1334085>

Appleby, Thomas and Harrison, James (2019). Taking the Pulse of Environmental and Fisheries Law: The Common Fisheries Policy, the Habitats Directive, and Brexit. *Journal of Environmental Law* 31(3), pp. 443-464. <https://doi.org/10.1093/jel/eqy027>

Belinskij, Antti (2018). Erittäin tärkeän yleisen edun edellytys EU:n ympäristöoikeudessa: Natura-alueen suojelusta ja vesienhoidon ympäristötavoitteista poikkeaminen uuden hankkeen takia. *Ympäristöjuridiikka* 39(2-3), pp. 42-62.

Belinskij, Antti and Mehling, Michael (2008). Natura 2000-verkoston suojelu Suomessa ja Saksassa EY-oikeuden näkökulmasta. *Ympäristöjuridiikka* 29(2), pp. 8-52.

Boyle, Sam (2014). The Case for Regulation of Agricultural Water Pollution. *Environmental Law Review* 16(1), pp. 4-20. <https://doi.org/10.1350/enlr.2014.16.1.200>

Carvalho, L., Mackay, E., Cardoso, A. C., Baattrup-Pedersen, A., Birk, S., Blackstock, K., Borics, G., Borja, A., Feld, C., Ferreira, M. T., Globevnik, L., Grizzetti, B., Hendry, S., Hering, D., Kelly, M., Langaas, S., Meissner, K., Panagopoulos, Y., Penning, E. Rouillard, J. Solheim, A. L. (2019). Protecting and restoring Europe's waters: An analysis of the future development needs of the Water Framework Directive. *Science of The Total Environment* 658, pp. 1228-1238. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2018.12.255>

CrossGov Deliverable 1.1: Boteler, B., Giannopoulos, N., Passarello, C., Trevisanut, S. Scoping: Concretising the policy targets and developing key scenarios. Available at: https://crossgov.eu/wp-content/uploads/2023/08/CrossGov_D1.1.-Green-Deal-Objectives-and-Scenarios192855226f323a3f738b788cd50d8fb95d4d8f1f801da614a9a7943f653785ed.pdf

CrossGov Deliverable 1.2: Platjouw, F. M., Sander, G., Ramirez-Monsalve, P., Friedrich, L., Trubbach, S., Boteler, B., Passarello, C., Soininen, N., Belinskij, A., Kyrönviita, J., de Oliveira, C. S., and Strosser, P. (2023a) Deliverable 1.2: Coherent and Cross-compliant Ocean Governance for Delivering the Green Deal for European Seas. *CrossGov Policy Brief 1*, May 2023. Available at: <https://crossgov.eu/wp-content/uploads/2023/06/20230602-Policy-Brief-1.pdf>

CrossGov Deliverable 1.3: Platjouw, F. M., Friedrich, L., Trubbach, S., Sander, G., Boteler, B., Passarello, C. C., Soininen, N., de Oliveira, C. S., Kyrönviita, J., Belinskij, A., Puharinen, S. T., Albrecht, E. (2023) The CrossGov Policy Coherence Evaluation Framework - A methodological framework to assess policy coherence and cross-compliance with the European

Green Deal. Available at: <https://crossgov.eu/wp-content/uploads/2024/02/Updated-Del-1.3-Coherence-cross-compliance-methodology-Feb-2024.pdf>

CrossGov Deliverable 2.1: Boteler, B., Passarello, C., Platjouw, F. M., Friedrich, L., Trubbach, S., Soininen, N., Kyrönviita, J., Puharinen, S-T., Trevisanut, S., Giannopoulos, N., Van Rijn-Bogaart, M. EU and international policy landscape. Available at: https://crossgov.eu/wp-content/uploads/2024/02/CrossGov_-D2.1_EU-and-international-policy-landscape.pdf

de Sadeleer, Nicolas (2020). Environmental Principles: From Political Slogans to Legal Rules. Oxford (2nd ed.).

De Sousa Santos, Boaventura (1987). Law: a map of misreading — toward a postmodern conception of law. *Journal of Law and Society* 14(3), pp. 279-302. <https://doi.org/10.2307/1410186>

Earle, Michael (2021). Maximum sustainable yield in the EU's Common Fisheries Policy - a political history. *ICES Journal of Marine Science*, 78(6), pp. 2173–2181. <https://doi.org/10.1093/icesjms/fsab037>

Ecorys, Metis, and Agrosynergy (2023). Mapping and Analysis of CAP Strategic Plans - Assessment of joint efforts for 2023-2027. Final Report (European Commission - Directorate-General for Agriculture and Rural Development).

Eggert, Håkan, and Langlet, David (2020). Svenskt yrkesfiske och EU 1995-2020. *Sieps* 2020:6.

European Commission (n.d.). Fishing outside the EU. Retrieved 13 June 2024. Available at: https://oceans-and-fisheries.ec.europa.eu/fisheries/international-agreements/fishing-outside-eu_en

European Commission (2006). Implementing sustainability in EU fisheries through maximum sustainable yield. COM(2006) 360 final.

European Commission (2007). An Integrated Maritime Policy for the European Union. COM(2007) 575 final.

European Commission (2008). The role of the CFP in implementing an ecosystem approach to marine management. COM(2008) 187 final.

European Commission (2009a). Common Implementation Strategy for the Water Framework Directive (2000/60/EC) - Guidance Document on Exemptions to the Environmental Objectives. Guidance Document no. 20.

European Commission (2009b). Green Paper - Reform of the Common Fisheries Policy. COM(2009)163 final.

European Commission (2011a). Links between the Water Framework Directive and Nature Directives – Frequently asked questions. December 2011. Available at: http://sgil.isprambiente.it/zoneumide/allegati/FAQ-WFD-BHD_20Dec2011_with%20draft%20case%20studies_clean.pdf

European Commission (2011b). Proposal for a Regulation of the European Parliament and of the Council on the Common Fisheries Policy. COM(2011) 425 final.

European Commission (2019). The European Green Deal. COM (2019) 640 final. Available at: <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=COM%3A2019%3A640%3AFIN>.

European Commission (2020a). EU Biodiversity Strategy for 2030 - Bringing nature back into our lives. COM(2020) 380 final. Available at: <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=celex%3A52020DC0380>

European Commission (2020b). Communication from the Commission to the European Parliament, the Council, the European Economic and Social Committee and the Committee of the Regions, A Farm to Fork Strategy for a fair, healthy and environmentally-friendly food system. COM(2020) 381 final.

European Commission (2020c). Communication from the Commission to the European Parliament, the Council, the European Economic and Social Committee and the Committee of the Regions, Pathway to a Healthy Planet for All – EU Action Plan: 'Towards Zero Pollution for Air, Water and Soil'. COM(2021) 400 final.

European Commission (2020d). Commission staff working document, Background document for the Marine Strategy Framework Directive on the determination of good environmental status and its links to assessments and the setting of environmental targets. SWD(2020) 62. final.

European Commission (2020e). First report on the implementation of the Multiannual Plan for the stocks of cod, herring and sprat in the Baltic Sea and the fisheries exploiting those stocks. COM(2020) 494 final.

European Commission (2020f). Report from the Commission to the European Parliament and to the Council on the implementation of the Marine Strategy Framework Directive (Directive 2008/56/EC). COM/2020/259 final.

European Commission (2021). Communication from the Commission to the European Parliament, the Council, the European Economic and Social Committee and the Committee of the Regions, Pathway to a Healthy Planet for All – EU Action Plan: 'Towards Zero Pollution for Air, Water and Soil'. COM(2021) 400 final.

European Commission (2023a). Approved 28 CAP Strategic Plans (2023-2027) – Summary overview for 27 Member States. Facts and figures.

European Commission (2023b). U Action Plan: Protecting and restoring marine ecosystems for sustainable and resilient fisheries. COM(2023) 102 final.

European Court of Auditors (2014). Integration of EU water policy objectives with the CAP: a partial success. Special Report.

European Court of Auditors (2016). Combating eutrophication in the Baltic Sea: further and more effective action needed. Special Report.

European Court of Auditors (2020). Marine environment: EU protection is wide but not deep. Special report 26/2020.

European Environment Agency (2015). Marine protected areas in Europe's seas. EEA report 3/2015.

European Environment Agency (2018). Marine Protected Areas. Briefing No 13/2018.

European Environment Agency (2020). Marine messages II: Navigating the course towards clean, healthy and productive seas through implementation of an ecosystem-based approach. EEA Report No 17/2019.

European Environment Agency (2021). Drivers of and pressures arising from selected key water management challenges – A European overview. EEA Report 9/2021.

European Parliament (2023). Direct Payment – Fact Sheets on the European Union. Retrieved 13 June 2024. Available at: <https://www.europarl.europa.eu/factsheets/en/sheet/109/direct-payments>

European Parliament (2024). The Common Fisheries Policy: Origins and Development. Fact Sheets on the European Union – 2024. Available at: https://www.europarl.europa.eu/erpl-app-public/factsheets/pdf/en/FTU_3.3.1.pdf

Giljam, Renske A. (2018). Implementing Ecological Governance in EU Energy Law: The Role of Technology Neutral Legislative Design in Fostering Innovation. *European Energy and Environmental Law Review* 27(6) pp. 236-250. <https://doi.org/10.54648/eelr2018029>

Guyomard, H., Détang-Dessendre, C., Dupraz, P., Delaby, L., Huyghe, C., Peyraud, J-L., Reboud, X., Sirami, C (2023). How the Green Architecture of the 2023–2027 Common Agricultural Policy could have been greener. Volume 52, pp 1327–1338. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s13280-023-01861-0>

Howarth, William (2011). Diffuse Water Pollution and Diffuse Environmental Laws. *Journal of Environmental Law*, Volume 23, Issue 1, March 2011, pp 129–141, <https://doi.org/10.1093/jel/eqq031>

Huhta, K, Soininen, N, and Vesa, S (2024). The ecological sustainability of the energy transition in EU law: pro et contra hydropower. *Journal of Energy & Natural Resources Law*, pp 1–17. <https://doi.org/10.1080/02646811.2024.2331886>

Jans, Jan H. (2011). Stop the Integration Principle?. *Fordham Int'l L.J.* 33(5) pp. 153315-47.

Karageorgou, Vasiliki (2023). The Environmental Integration Principle in EU Law: Normative Content and Functions also in Light of New Developments, such as the European Green Deal. *European Papers*, Vol. 8, 2023, No 1, pp. 159-189. <https://doi.org/10.15166/2499-8249/645>

Krämer, Ludwig (2013). Giving a Voice to the Environment by Challenging the Practice of Integrating Environmental Requirements into other EU Policies. In *European Perspectives on Environmental Law and Governance* (Kingston, Suzanne ed.) (Taylor and Francis).

Langlet, David, and Mahmoudi, Said (2016). *EU Environmental Law and Policy*. Oxford University Press.

MSFD CIS (2014). *Common Implementation Strategy to the Marine Strategy Framework Directive, Programmes of measures under the Marine Strategy Framework Directive – Recommendations for implementation and reporting*. Jointly developed common strategy by the Marine Directors of the European Union (EU), Acceding Countries, Candidate Countries and EFTA Countries.

Pappila, Minna, and Puharinen, Suvi-Tuuli (2022). *Meriluonnon suojelun sääntely : Merellisen luonnon suojelun, merenhoidon ja vesienhoidon yhteensovittaminen EU- ja Suomen oikeudessa*. Ympäristöministeriö.

Puharinen, Suvi-Tuuli (2023). Achieving good marine environmental status in the EU – Implications of the marine strategy framework directive for member states and blue economic activities. *Marine Policy* 155 (2023). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.marpol.2023.105712>

Puharinen, Suvi-Tuuli, and Belinskij, Antti (2023). Influence of the EU on Regional Environmental Governance: Application of the Marine Directives in the Baltic Sea. In Rosas, Allan and Ringbom Henrik (eds.). *The EU and the Baltic Sea* (pp. 195-219). Bloomsbury Publishing.

Puharinen, S-T, Hakkarainen, M, Belinskij, A. Suomen merenhoitolainsäädännön toimivuustarkastelu: Merenhoidon tavoitteet ja niistä poikkeaminen. Ympäristöministeriön julkaisuja 2021:14. Available at: <http://urn.fi/URN:ISBN:978-952-361-241-9>

Ribeiro, Marta Chantal (2017). The Protection of Biodiversity in the Framework of the Common Fisheries Policy: What Room for the Shared Competence?. In Andreone, Gemma (ed.). *The Future of the Law of the Sea - Bridging Gaps Between National, Individual and Common Interests* (pp. 65-86). Springer Open.

Romppanen, Seita (2020). 'Blind Spots' in EU Climate and Energy Law. *European Energy and Environmental Law Review* 29(4), pp. 150-162.

Romppanen, Seita, and Huhta, Kaisa (2023). The interface between EU climate and energy law. *Maastricht Journal of European and Comparative Law* 2023, Vol. 30(1), pp. 45-62. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1023263X231159976>

Sander, Gunnar (2024). European Approaches Support an Essential Definition of Ecosystem-Based Management and Demonstrate Its Implementation for the Oceans. *Ocean Development & International Law* 54(4), pp. 421–447. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00908320.2023.2301105>

Sjåfjell, Beate (2014). The Environmental Integration Principle: A Necessary Step Towards Policy Coherence for Sustainability. In Ippolito, F., Bartolini, M-E and Condinanzi, M. (eds.). *The EU and the Proliferation of Integration Principles under the Lisbon Treaty*. (Routledge).

Skogstad, Grace (1998). Ideas, Paradigms and Institutions: Agricultural Exceptionalism in the European Union and the United States. *Governance: An International Journal of Policy and Administration* 11(4), pp. 463-490.

Soininen, Niko (2015). Marine spatial planning in the European Union. In Hassan Daud, Kuokkanen, Tuomas and Soininen, Niko (eds.). *Transboundary Marine Spatial Planning and International Law*. Routledge.

Soininen, Niko, and Platjouw, Froukje Maria (2019). Resilience and Adaptive Capacity of Aquatic Environmental Law in the EU – An evaluation and comparison of the WFD, MSFD, and MSPD. In Langlet, David and Rayfuse, Rosemary (eds.). *Ecosystem Approach in Ocean Governance and Planning*, pp. 17-79. Brill Nijhof.

Soininen, N, Turunen, J-P, Kettunen, A. (2024). The impact of MSPs in Finland. Merialuesuunnitelman vaikuttavuus ja sen kehittäminen Suomessa. Tapausesimerkinä talousvyöhykkeellä sijaitseva merituulivoima (Effectiveness of marine spatial plans in Finland. Offshore windpower as a case study). Report commissioned by the Ministry of the Environment of Finland.

van Kempen, Jasper (2012). Countering the Obscurity of Obligations in European Environmental Law: An Analysis of Article 4 of the European Water Framework Directive. *Journal of Environmental Law* 24(3), pp. 499–533. <https://doi.org/10.1093/jel/eqs020>

Vogeler, Colette S. (2021). The integration of environmental objectives in the common agricultural policy—partisan politics in the European Parliament. *Zeitschrift für Vergleichende Politikwissenschaft* vol. 15, pp. 551-569.

Westholm, Aron (2021). *Scaling Marine and Water Management*. Juridiska institutionens skriftserie.

Wiering, M., Liefferink, D., Boezeman, D., Kaufmann, M., Crabbé, A., Kurstjens, N (2020). The Wicked Problem the Water Framework Directive Cannot Solve. The Governance Approach in Dealing with Pollution of Nutrients in Surface Water in the Netherlands, Flanders, Lower Saxony, Denmark and Ireland. *Water* 2020, 12(5), 1240. <https://doi.org/10.3390/w12051240>

Annex I – Interview protocol and semi-structured questions

Group 1: Agriculture and pollution

Group 1 Background document 1 – Coherence analysis of the EU agricultural and pollutions policies cluster (the Common Agricultural Policy and the Water Framework Directive)

The Common Agriculture Policy (CAP) is one of the oldest and most expensive EU policies with roots in the early 1960s and representing 31 % of the EU total budget. At its core, it has existed to support agricultural production, ensure food security, and promote rural development. At the same time, agricultural production has been one of the main pressures on both our water quality and quantity. While the CAP includes an objective to foster sustainable development and efficient management of natural resources such as water, the main policy for water quality is the Water Framework Directive (WFD). Tackling diffuse pollution from agriculture remains a key challenge for governments seeking to implement the WFD. To legally operationalise the European Green Deal objectives of zero pollution from the agricultural production to the marine environment, a high level of coherence between the CAP and the WFD is essential.

Implementation of the WFD has been significantly delayed due to insufficient integration of environmental objectives in sectoral policies. This is no different for the agricultural sector. While there are environmental objectives in the new CAP, these are added as an outer logic of the already existing policy. This has led to the introduction of legal instruments to address nutrient pollution within the CAP framework. However, the objectives are to a large extent contradictory as objectives on agricultural productivity and environmental production do not relate to each other. The CAP and the WFD risk ending up working against each other rather than in a harmonized way.

Agricultural pollution has not been reduced significantly at the European scale. Legally operationalising the Green Deal's objectives on agricultural pollution continues to be a challenge due to the continued lack of effectiveness and capacity to steer Member States in acting to reduce nutrient pollution from agriculture. This is partly due to the lack of legal bindingness and inability to adequately address agricultural sources of pollution in the river basin management plans. The CAP includes measures to promote sustainable agriculture, such as agri-environmental schemes, but their effectiveness in reducing nutrient pollution may vary across Member States. The success of nutrient mitigation becomes heavily reliant on efficient national implementation rather than a guarantee stemming from EU policies. The lack of integration means that agricultural production continues to contribute to nutrient pollution in an unsustainable way despite efforts to improve water quality.

The most important legal instrument of the CAP is the two funds, one for income support and the other for rural development. While there are funds for fostering sustainable development and efficient management of water, the largest share of the CAP budget goes to direct payments. Analysis of the fund allocation has found that CAP funds are more likely to promote greater rather than more efficient water use, resulting in a financial instrument that risk resulting in taking one step forward and two steps back.

Group 1 Background document 2 – Coherence analysis of the EU zero pollution policy cluster on agricultural nutrient pollution (the Nitrates Directive, Water Framework Directive, Marine Strategy Framework Directive)

The WFD, the MSFD and the ND form a multifaceted legal cluster addressing agricultural nutrient pollution and its eutrophication effects in the aquatic environment. The objectives of the policies target different geographical scale and have slightly different focus – the WFD and the MSFD assessing functioning of the ecosystems and the ND on the amount and impact of nitrates inputs – but they are coherent in their substance regarding the main problem. The same goes for the instruments in the policies, as the WFD and the MSFD provide more general management frameworks for agricultural nutrient inputs, focusing on the design on national policy responses, while the ND provides more concrete and specific requirements for measures to be taken by the Member States in addressing and controlling inputs of nitrates in the waters. Furthermore, the assessment shows that the directives provide opportunities for the Member States to actively seek a synergetic approach to their implementation, including deliberating and establishing the ND's nitrates vulnerable zones and areas of application of the action programs based on the geographical scopes of the WFD or the MSFD or any needs for regional differentiation detected under the implementation of river basin management planning or marine strategies.

In sum, the conclusion of the coherence assessment thus is that there are no major problems of incoherence or fragmentation within the cluster. There are only minor coherence issues, such as the ND's lack of objectives and regulation on phosphorus and the lack of deadline for achieving its objectives. By taking a synergetic and coherence-seeking approach to interpretation, the objectives and instruments can form a coherent and mutually reinforcing regime providing various instruments for tackling the problem of agriculture induced nutrient pollution and eutrophication.

However, the major challenge for this combined regime in legally operationalising the Green Deal's objectives on agricultural pollution is the continued lack of effectiveness and capacity to steer Member States in taking action to actually reduce nutrient pollution from agriculture.¹ All instruments in the cluster have continuously suffered from insufficient rigor in implementation by the Member States, with the effect that their objectives are far from being realised and agricultural pollution has not been reduced significantly at the European scale.² With regards to the WFD and the MSFD, while their objectives entail legal obligations for Member States to deliver improvements in the environmental conditions, the flexibilities in the form of obligations (the MSFD's best effort obligations) and exemptions (the WFD's flexible exemptions allowing exclusion of measures on economic and technical grounds) have provided wide margin of discretion to not address agricultural pollution effectively. With regard to the ND, the Directive has set clear requirements on the designation of vulnerable zones, drawing up action plans and adopting measures (Annex III) to reduce nitrates runoff, but has suffered from failures of Member States to set strict enough requirements to tackle the problem and over-reliance on voluntary-based measures. However, new interpretations of the ND's objectives and obligations championed particularly in the German nitrates -case by the CJEU may reinforce the directive on these aspects, or even force the Member States to act on agricultural nitrates pollution in the event that the failures to reach the objectives of the WFD and the MSFD are under exemption.

Group 1 Interviewees and questions

Interview questions for group one: Agriculture vs Zero pollution
<p>1. Introduction: Could you mention your experiences with EU policies focused on agricultural nutrient pollution, specifically with the Nitrates Directive (ND), Water Framework Directive (WFD), and Marine Strategy Framework Directive (MSFD)?</p>
<p>2. Intro question: From your perspective, what is your impression on how well EU policies meet (or will meet) the aims and objectives of the European Green Deal when it comes zero pollution in the marine environment?</p>
<p>3. Coherence challenges: Do you agree with our assessment that there are coherence challenges between agricultural productivity and pollution control? Is anything you would change in our assessment?</p>
<p>4. Explanatory variables:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">a) Governmental organizational structures set the framework within which policies are formulated and implemented. How well do you believe the current EU organisational structure is suited for the mix of policies and support the achievement of the overarching policy goals?b) Science-policy society interfaces are the social processes that describe the role of knowledge production, transfer, and use in decision-making processes. How well do think the SPSI is suited to address this policy mix and how is it used in your experience?c) Stakeholder involvement refer to the manner in which stakeholders influence policy design and implementation through participatory processes and other avenues and how this affects coherence across policies. How well do you think stakeholder engagement influence the policy mix and what impact does this have on the coherence of pollutions policies?
<p>5. Improving coherence: What specific actions or policy adjustments would you recommend to enhance coherence across agricultural policies and those aimed at achieving zero pollution?</p>
<p>6. Closing question: Do you think we missed anything? Or is anything you would like to share with us that could contribute to our research based on the information discussed?</p>

Group 2: Fisheries and biodiversity

Group 2 Background document 1 – Coherence analysis of the EU fisheries and biodiversity policy cluster (the Common Fisheries Policy, the Habitats Directive, Marine Strategy Framework Directive)

The European Environment Agency reported in 2020 that fishing activities were responsible for some of the main pressures on ecosystems in Europe’s seas, and the Intergovernmental

Science Policy Platform on Biodiversity and Ecosystems Services reported in 2019 that fishing had the largest impact on marine ecosystems. To protect marine biodiversity in accordance with the objectives of the European Green Deal, a high level of coherence between legal instruments that regulate the pressures and protect the marine environment is necessary.

- 1. The policies fall under different competences and are different types of legal instruments with CFP being a regulation and MSFD and HD directives, dividing the responsibilities between the two and limiting Member States ability to apply proper measures on one of the largest pressures.*

Member States have only limited competence in adopting national measures regarding the fishing sector, even when they are acting upon obligations deriving from other EU statutes such as the HD or MSFD. As fishing is one of the largest pressures on marine biodiversity, this limits the Member States ability to enact proper measures in accordance with these directives and creates issues with the coordination of these legal instruments.

- 2. The jurisdictional issues limit the Member States' possibilities to enact protective measures.*

The Member States have limited capacity for their EEZ cannot impose restrictions on fishing activities beyond territorial waters without engaging in multilateral discussions. This complicates protection of the marine environment. Regional cooperation on conservations measures were adopted as a tool for this, but there are no legal obligations for the Member States to engage in such regional cooperation nor is there an obligation for the Commission to enact such measures. The regional influence could as such be seen as weak.

- 3. The objectives of the policies are inherently different as one concerns the protection of an industry, and the others concern protection of the environment.*

The CFP covers resource management and market measures, mainly to support the industry and boost the market. While resource management has clear overlaps with environmental protection, there are also differences in protection mainly for further exploitation and the protection of a natural environment. Further, the policy has historically focused on creating a stable industry and market, while the more restrictive measures have been added more recently. This division increases the need for policy transcending compromises and harmonising mechanisms to avoid coherence issues.

- 4. Article 11 provides a tool for Member States to apply conservation measures but has been deemed as complicated and ineffective.*

Article 11 of the CFP is intended to provide a tool for the Member States to enact conservation measures. The substantive scope is limited though as it only applies conservation measures that are deemed necessary for the effectiveness of MPAs. Further, Member States have not sought to use the tool as it is complicated, lengthy, and often deemed to lead to weak restrictions. This has further led to the ineffectiveness of MPAs in practice.

- 5. Other legal measures within CFP are insufficient to protect the marine biodiversity.*

Other key measures in the CFP have also not been able to protect biodiversity. For example, the catch limits have not been able to prevent overfishing in a satisfying way, both due to the lack of reliable data and legal bindingness of MSY. Further, the funding from the policy has only in a limited extent been used to limit impact of fishing on the marine environment and more often funded activities that risk creating additional pressures on fish stocks and vulnerable marine habitats.

Group 2 Background document 2 – Coherence analysis of the EU marine biodiversity policy cluster (the Habitats Directive, Birds Directive, Water Framework Directive, Marine Strategy Framework Directive, Nature Restoration Law)

The objectives and instruments of the Nature Directives, the MSFD, the WFD and the NRL form a complex policy cluster for marine biodiversity protection towards the Green Deals biodiversity goals. While both the objectives and the instruments are by their general nature quite coherent and aim to direct towards improving the state of marine biodiversity, there is several fragmentations of legal requirements within the cluster. Fragmentation exists with regard to the substance of the objectives, the timeframes for their achievement, the legal impacts of the objectives in relation to Member States obligation and the instruments, particularly rules on authorising new projects as well as the exemptions.

1. *The objectives of the policies are fragmented with a result that no policy addresses all relevant aspects of marine biodiversity with legally forceful conservation obligations.*

The Nature Directives focus on the achievement of favourable conservation status (FCS) for the habitats and species deemed in need of special protection; thus, they do not aim to cover the different components of marine ecosystems or protect biodiversity as a whole. These directives are substantiated by the WFD and MSFD that aim to achieve aquatic and marine ecosystems of good ecological quality, which supports the protection of many species and habitats. Of the two, the WFD's objectives pertain considerably legal forcefulness yet they do not specifically address biodiversity. The MSFD's objective of good marine environmental status is the most comprehensive related to biodiversity. However, the problem with the MSFD is the vague and uncertain legal status of its objectives. The NRL includes a wide array of marine nature in the scope of its restoration objectives, but the focus of its obligations is placed on putting in place restoration measures that address only parts of the area of habitats by 2030, 2040 and 2050 creates uncertainty about the level of coherence with the objectives of other instruments.

2. *Each instruments contains different deadlines for the objectives, and the timeframes are not aligned.*

In the Nature Directives, there is no deadline attached to the objectives, the MSFD's 2020 objective for marine Good Environmental Status (GES) appears to be more of a instructive deadline than a legally binding one, while the WFD's 2027 deadline is potentially a binding one, while rather vast possibilities exist to lower the ambition level of the objectives even beyond this deadline. Furthermore, the NRL introduces its own deadlines of 2030, 2040 and 2050 that significantly exceed those of the MSFD and the WFD.

3. *The legal obligations on Member States and the various exemptions from them are inconsistent with no clear linkages to one another to improve coherence.*

The different legal impetus attached to the achievement of the policy objectives risk creating fragmentation and confusion on planning the measures. Furthermore, especially the WFD and the MSFD include a complex system of exemptions from the objectives where it is not quite clear, what exempting from the objectives of one policy means in terms of the legal requirements related to the objectives in other policies.

4. *While the policy instruments can be interpreted in a rather consistent manner, the complexity creates a risk of distortion and the instruments' design leaves a lot to be desired for in terms of them being able to steer towards the Green Deal objectives.*

The area-based and species conservation regimes in the Nature Directives form the backbone of marine biodiversity protection. Nevertheless, due to the nature of the aquatic environments and the insufficiency of the compilation of marine habitats and species included particularly under the HD's regimes, they alone are not enough to meet the Biodiversity Strategy's objectives or ensure effective protection of marine nature. The MSFD's and the WFD's instruments can however supplement the traditional conservation instruments. First, the integrated marine strategies and river basin management plans and their programmes of measures can respond to pressures, impacts and threats that are not addressed with area-based conservation. Second, the MSFD contains a supplementary system of marine protected areas that can be utilised to extend the area-based protection to cover a wider range of habitats than those of the HD. In response, the area-based protection and species protection regimes of the HD and BD form important, harmonised, and specific instruments for especially the MSFD's objectives.

However, the implementation of the protection regimes, especially the MPAs, has not been very effective in practise, and the EU minimum requirements need to be supported by national conservation regulation and restrictions on key pressures, such as fishing activities. The NRL adds another layer of strategic planning to this mix and while it contains some potential in supplementing and reinforcing some aspects of the instrument mix, it also pertains significant flexibility on the Member States; thus, national implementation is in a key role in ensuring coherence. In addition, a specific coherence challenge in the instrumentalization of these policies are the different sets of rules on authorising new projects and particularly the somewhat different scopes of application of the derogations and their conditions. Depending on where exactly in the marine area a project is located, it may be assessed under 2-4 different sets of permitting rules and derogation regimes.

More specifically in relation to the GD's objectives for marine biodiversity, the policies display variable degree of potential to deliver these objectives. For instance, while the 30 % goals for the protection area coverage can be legally operationalised through the complementary application of different instruments (mainly the nature Directives and the MSFD), the EU legislation does not provide strict legal protection for the 10 % of habitats mentioned in the GD's objectives. Similarly, the vagueness in the HD's obligations on the management of Natura 2000 -sites and the MSFD's ambiguity in the legal bindingness of its objectives undermine the realisation of the GD target that protected areas are effectively managed. In relation to the GD's objectives for restoring habitats and ecosystems, the NRL provides an important contribution to the policy mix; yet the NRL does not fully live up to these objectives, as it only prohibits

deterioration of habitats and ecosystems after good condition is reached and restoration objectives only cover maximum of 90 % of ecosystems by 2050.

Group 2 Interviewees and questions

Interview questions for group two: Fisheries vs biodiversity
<ol style="list-style-type: none">1. Introduction: Can you describe your role and your work in relation to fisheries and biodiversity policies, especially considering the recent focus on sustainability within the Common Fisheries Policy (CFP)?2. Intro question: what is your impression on how well EU policies meet (or will meet) the aims and objectives of the European Green Deal when it comes to fisheries and biodiversity?3. Coherence challenges: Based on your experience, do you share the view that there are significant coherence challenges between fisheries related policies and those focused on improving marine biodiversity? Is anything you would change in our assessment?4. Explanatory variables:<ol style="list-style-type: none">a) Governmental organizational structures set the framework within which policies are formulated and implemented. How well do you believe the current EU organisational structure is suited for the mix of policies and support the achievement of the overarching policy goals?b) Science-policy society interfaces are the social processes that describe the role of knowledge production, transfer, and use in decision-making processes. How well do think the SPSI is suited to address this policy mix and how is it used in your experience?c) Stakeholder involvement refer to the manner in which stakeholders influence policy design and implementation through participatory processes and other avenues and how this affects coherence across policies. How well do you think stakeholder engagement influence the policy mix and what impact does this have on the coherence of fisheries and biodiversity policies?5. Recommendations for enhancing coherence: Given the identified aspects of incoherence and their impacts, what specific actions or policy adjustments would you recommend to enhance coherence across the EU fisheries and biodiversity policy cluster and better align with the Green Deal’s biodiversity goals?6. Closing question: Do you think we missed anything? Or is anything you would like to share with us that could contribute to our research based on the information discussed?

Group 3: Offshore wind and biodiversity

Group 3 Background document 1 – Coherence analysis of the EU offshore wind power policy cluster (the EU Climate Law and the Renewables Directive III versus the biodiversity cluster)

The EU climate mitigation policies and the related legislation are heavily pushing for an increase in renewable energy generation, including offshore wind power generation. This aspiration is visible both in the overall goals of EU climate law (2021/1119) as well as the specific targets of the EU Renewable Energy Directive (RED III, 2023/2413). Developments in maritime spatial planning further emphasize these developments.

The EU climate law sets a legally binding climate neutrality goal for the member states by 2050 (arts. 1–2), with significant reductions in GHG emissions by 2030 (art. 4). These obligations are further operationalized by the EU Renewable energy directive, which requires member states to collectively ensure that at least 42,5 % of all gross energy consumed in the EU comes from renewable sources by 2030, with aspiration to hit 45 %. According to the directive, renewable energy means energy from renewable, non-fossil sources, including wind power on land and in marine areas (RED III, art. 2). Many EU member states, Finland included, are expecting considerable increase in offshore wind power development in the coming decade. To this end, the RED III establishes several measures, such as promoting state incentives for renewables (e.g., grid integration), alleviated Environmental Impact Assessment (art. 16b(2)), national contact points for renewable permitting (art. 16(3)), time limits on permit processes to speed them up (art. 16(2); art. 16a(1); art. 16b(1)) as well as mapping (art. 15b) and specification of renewable acceleration areas (art. 15c). Most importantly, and despite the directive establishing a general obligation not to locate renewable energy projects in Natura 2000 areas or areas otherwise protected by the Habitats (92/43/EC) and Birds (2009/147/EC) Directives, RED III states that renewable energy projects automatically fulfill the overriding public interest requirement that is one of the key criteria for granting exemptions from biodiversity protection (RED III art. 16f). In tandem with these developments, the EU Maritime Spatial Planning Directive (2014/89/EU) requires member states to establish maritime spatial plans by 2021, the purpose of which is to facilitate co-location of several marine activities, including offshore wind power generation, shipping, fishing, aquaculture, and nature conservation (art. 4 and 5). One of the explicit aims of the directive is to promote economic growth in the maritime sector, such as offshore wind (art. 5).

The heavy promotion of renewable energy, including offshore wind power generation, cannot be realized without tradeoffs to the biodiversity of the marine environment. Currently, the most widely used offshore wind power technologies need to be anchored to the sea floor with concrete structures. Moreover, the wingspan of the wind turbines can be several hundred meters with wind power parks encompassing typically dozens or even hundreds of installations. This translates into considerable need for space for the installations. This may conflict with the Sea Floor Integrity requirement of the Marine Strategy Framework Directive (2008/56/EC) as part and parcel of the Good Environmental Status of marine areas. This challenge is made worse by the lack of scientific knowledge concerning the status of marine waters and seafloor integrity. Moreover, in many cases the most economically feasible areas for operation are in shallow banks, which are typically also rich in biodiversity and may enjoy the protection of the Habitats and Birds Directives (either as part of Natura 2000 networks, or as containing species and their

spawning areas protected by the nature directives). Even though the RED III establishes a general rule for not locating offshore wind power operations in legally protected areas, exemptions are increasingly easy to obtain due to the overriding public interest easement. All in all, despite efforts to integrate climate change mitigation and biodiversity goals in EU legislation, there is considerable incoherence between legal frameworks in the context of offshore wind power.

Group 3 Background document 2 – Coherence analysis of the EU marine biodiversity policy cluster (the Habitats Directive, Birds Directive, Water Framework Directive, Marine Strategy Framework Directive, Nature Restoration Law)

The objectives and instruments of the Nature Directives, the MSFD, the WFD and the NRL form a complex policy cluster for marine biodiversity protection towards the Green Deals biodiversity goals. While both the objectives and the instruments are by their general nature quite coherent and aim to direct towards improving the state of marine biodiversity, there is several fragmentations of legal requirements within the cluster. Fragmentation exists with regard to the substance of the objectives, the timeframes for their achievement, the legal impacts of the objectives in relation to Member States obligation and the instruments, particularly rules on authorising new projects as well as the exemptions.

1. *The objectives of the policies are fragmented with a result that no policy addresses all relevant aspects of marine biodiversity with legally forceful conservation obligations.*

The Nature Directives focus on the achievement of favourable conservation status (FCS) for the habitats and species deemed in need of special protection; thus, they do not aim to cover the different components of marine ecosystems or protect biodiversity as a whole. These directives are substantiated by the WFD and MSFD that aim to achieve aquatic and marine ecosystems of good ecological quality, which supports the protection of many species and habitats. Of the two, the WFD's objectives pertain considerably legal forcefulness yet they do not specifically address biodiversity. The MSFD's objective of good marine environmental status is the most comprehensive related to biodiversity. However, the problem with the MSFD is the vague and uncertain legal status of its objectives. The NRL includes a wide array of marine nature in the scope of its restoration objectives, but the focus of its obligations is placed on putting in place restoration measures that address only parts of the area of habitats by 2030, 2040 and 2050 creates uncertainty about the level of coherence with the objectives of other instruments.

2. *Each instruments contains different deadlines for the objectives, and the timeframes are not aligned.*

In the Nature Directives, there is no deadline attached to the objectives, the MSFD's 2020 objective for marine Good Environmental Status (GES) appears to be more of a instructive deadline than a legally binding one, while the WFD's 2027 deadline is potentially a binding one, while rather vast possibilities exist to lower the ambition level of the objectives even beyond this deadline. Furthermore, the NRL introduces its own deadlines of 2030, 2040 and 2050 that significantly exceed those of the MSFD and the WFD.

3. *The legal obligations on Member States and the various exemptions from them are inconsistent with no clear linkages to one another to improve coherence.*

The different legal impetus attached to the achievement of the policy objectives risk creating fragmentation and confusion on planning the measures. Furthermore, especially the WFD and the MSFD include a complex system of exemptions from the objectives where it is not quite clear, what exempting from the objectives of one policy means in terms of the legal requirements related to the objectives in other policies.

4. *While the policy instruments can be interpreted in a rather consistent manner, the complexity creates a risk of distortion and the instruments' design leaves a lot to be desired for in terms of them being able to steer towards the Green Deal objectives.*

The area-based and species conservation regimes in the Nature Directives form the backbone of marine biodiversity protection. Nevertheless, due to the nature of the aquatic environments and the insufficiency of the compilation of marine habitats and species included particularly under the HD's regimes, they alone are not enough to meet the Biodiversity Strategy's objectives or ensure effective protection of marine nature. The MSFD's and the WFD's instruments can however supplement the traditional conservation instruments. First, the integrated marine strategies and river basin management plans and their programmes of measures can respond to pressures, impacts and threats that are not addressed with area-based conservation. Second, the MSFD contains a supplementary system of marine protected areas that can be utilised to extend the area-based protection to cover a wider range of habitats than those of the HD. In response, the area-based protection and species protection regimes of the HD and BD form important, harmonised, and specific instruments for especially the MSFD's objectives.

However, the implementation of the protection regimes, especially the MPAs, has not been very effective in practise, and the EU minimum requirements need to be supported by national conservation regulation and restrictions on key pressures, such as fishing activities. The NRL adds another layer of strategic planning to this mix and while it contains some potential in supplementing and reinforcing some aspects of the instrument mix, it also pertains significant flexibility on the Member States; thus, national implementation is in a key role in ensuring coherence. In addition, a specific coherence challenge in the instrumentalization of these policies are the different sets of rules on authorising new projects and particularly the somewhat different scopes of application of the derogations and their conditions. Depending on where exactly in the marine area a project is located, it may be assessed under 2-4 different sets of permitting rules and derogation regimes.

More specifically in relation to the GD's objectives for marine biodiversity, the policies display variable degree of potential to deliver these objectives. For instance, while the 30 % goals for the protection area coverage can be legally operationalised through the complementary application of different instruments (mainly the nature Directives and the MSFD), the EU legislation does not provide strict legal protection for the 10 % of habitats mentioned in the GD's objectives. Similarly, the vagueness in the HD's obligations on the management of Natura 2000 -sites and the MSFD's ambiguity in the legal bindingness of its objectives undermine the realisation of the GD target that protected areas are effectively managed. In relation to the GD's objectives for restoring habitats and ecosystems, the NRL provides an important contribution to the policy mix; yet the NRL does not fully live up to these objectives, as it only prohibits

deterioration of habitats and ecosystems after good condition is reached and restoration objectives only cover maximum of 90 % of ecosystems by 2050.

Group 3 Interviewees and questions

Interview questions for group three: Offshore wind power vs Biodiversity

1. **Intro question:** can you briefly describe your role and experience with EU policies related to offshore wind energy and/or biodiversity?
2. **Intro question:** what is your impression on how well EU policies meet (or will meet) the aims and objectives of the European Green Deal when it comes to offshore renewable energy production and marine biodiversity? What do you consider the main strengths and weaknesses in the current EU policy mix relevant to achieve these ambitions?
3. **Coherence challenges:** Based on your experience, do you recognise any coherence issues between the goals of offshore wind energy expansion and marine biodiversity conservation in EU policy? Is anything you would change in our assessment?
4. Explanatory variables:
 - a) Governmental organizational structures set the framework within which policies are formulated and implemented. How well do you believe the current EU organisational structure is suited for the mix of policies and support the achievement of the overarching policy goals?
 - b) Science-policy society interfaces are the social processes that describe the role of knowledge production, transfer, and use in decision-making processes. How well do think the SPSI is suited to address this policy mix and how is it used in your experience?
 - c) Stakeholder involvement refer to the manner in which stakeholders influence policy design and implementation through participatory processes and other avenues and how this affects coherence across policies. How well do you think stakeholder engagement influence the policy mix and what impact does this have on the coherence of this policy cluster?
5. **Recommendations for enhancing coherence:** Given the identified aspects of incoherence and their impacts, what specific actions or policy adjustments would you recommend to enhance coherence across the EU marine biodiversity policy cluster and better align with the Green Deal's biodiversity goals?
6. **Closing question:** Do you think we missed anything? Or is anything you would like to share with us that could contribute to our research based on the information discussed?

Annex II – Summaries of the preliminary findings for each cluster used for interviews

Background document – Coherence analysis of the EU marine biodiversity policy cluster (the Habitats Directive, Birds Directive, Water Framework Directive, Marine Strategy Framework Directive, Nature Restoration Law)

The objectives and instruments of the Nature Directives, the MSFD, the WFD and the NRL form a complex policy cluster for marine biodiversity protection towards the Green Deals biodiversity goals. While both the objectives and the instruments are by their general nature quite coherent and aim to direct towards improving the state of marine biodiversity, there is several fragmentations of legal requirements within the cluster. Fragmentation exists with regard to the substance of the objectives, the timeframes for their achievement, the legal impacts of the objectives in relation to Member States obligation and the instruments, particularly rules on authorising new projects as well as the exemptions.

- 1) The objectives of the policies are fragmented with a result that no policy addresses all relevant aspects of marine biodiversity with legally forceful conservation obligations.*

The Nature Directives focus on the achievement of FCS for the habitats and species deemed in need of special protection; thus, they do not aim to cover the different components of marine ecosystems or protect biodiversity as a whole. These directives are substantiated by the WFD and MSFD that aim to achieve aquatic and marine ecosystems of good ecological quality, which supports the protection of many species and habitats. Of the two, the WFD's objectives pertain considerably legal forcefulness yet they do not specifically address biodiversity. The MSFD's objective of good marine environmental status is the most comprehensive related to biodiversity. However, the problem with the MSFD is the vague and uncertain legal status of its objectives. The NRL includes a wide array of marine nature in the scope of its restoration objectives, but the focus of its obligations is placed on putting in place restoration measures that address only parts of the area of habitats by 2030, 2040 and 2050 creates uncertainty about the level of coherence with the objectives of other instruments.

- 2) Each instruments contains different deadlines for the objectives, and the timeframes are not aligned.*

In the Nature Directives, there is no deadline attached to the objectives, the MSFD's 2020 objective for MGES appears to be more of a instructive deadline than a legally binding one, while the WFD's 2027 deadline is potentially a binding one, while rather vast possibilities exist to lower the ambition level of the objectives even beyond this deadline. Furthermore, the NRL introduces its own deadlines of 2030, 2040 and 2050 that significantly exceed those of the MSFD and the WFD.

- 3) The legal obligations on Member States and the various exemptions from them are inconsistent with no clear linkages to one another to improve coherence.*

The different legal impetus attached to the achievement of the policy objectives risk creating fragmentation and confusion on planning the measures. Furthermore, especially the WFD and the MSFD include a complex system of exemptions from the objectives where it is not quite clear, what exempting from the objectives of one policy means in terms of the legal requirements related to the objectives in other policies.

- 4) *While the policy instruments can be interpreted in a rather consistent manner, the complexity creates a risk of distortion and the instruments' design leaves a lot to be desired for in terms of them being able to steer towards the Green Deal objectives.*

The area-based and species conservation regimes in the Nature Directives form the backbone of marine biodiversity protection. Nevertheless, due to the nature of the aquatic environments and the insufficiency of the compilation of marine habitats and species included particularly under the HD's regimes, they alone are not enough to meet the Biodiversity Strategy's objectives or ensure effective protection of marine nature. The MSFD's and the WFD's instruments can however supplement the traditional conservation instruments. First, the integrated marine strategies and river basin management plans and their programmes of measures can respond to pressures, impacts and threats that are not addressed with area-based conservation. Second, the MSFD contains a supplementary system of marine protected areas that can be utilised to extend the area-based protection to cover a wider range of habitats than those of the HD. In response, the area-based protection and species protection regimes of the HD and BD form important, harmonised, and specific instruments for especially the MSFD's objectives.

However, the implementation of the protection regimes, especially the MPAs, has not been very effective in practice, and the EU minimum requirements need to be supported by national conservation regulation and restrictions on key pressures, such as fishing activities. The NRL adds another layer of strategic planning to this mix and while it contains some potential in supplementing and reinforcing some aspects of the instrument mix, it also pertains significant flexibility on the Member States; thus, national implementation is in a key role in ensuring coherence. In addition, a specific coherence challenge in the instrumentalization of these policies are the different sets of rules on authorising new projects and particularly the somewhat different scopes of application of the derogations and their conditions. Depending on where exactly in the marine area a project is located, it may be assessed under 2-4 different sets of permitting rules and derogation regimes.

More specifically in relation to the GD's objectives for marine biodiversity, the policies display variable degree of potential to deliver these objectives. For instance, while the 30 % goals for the protection area coverage can be legally operationalised through the complementary application of different instruments (mainly the nature Directives and the MSFD), the EU legislation does not provide strict legal protection for the 10 % of habitats mentioned in the GD's objectives. Similarly, the vagueness in the HD's obligations on the management of Natura 2000 -sites and the MSFD's ambiguity in the legal bindingness of its objectives undermine the realisation of the GD target that protected areas are effectively managed. In relation to the GD's objectives for restoring habitats and ecosystems, the NRL provides an important contribution to the policy mix; yet the NRL does not fully live up to these objectives, as it only prohibits deterioration of habitats and ecosystems after good condition is reached and restoration objectives only cover maximum of 90 % of ecosystems by 2050.

Background document – Coherence analysis of the EU zero pollution policy cluster on agricultural nutrient pollution (the Nitrates Directive, Water Framework Directive, Marine Strategy Framework Directive)

The WFD, the MSFD and the ND form a multifaceted legal cluster addressing agricultural nutrient pollution and its eutrophication effects in the aquatic environment. The objectives of the policies target different geographical scale and have slightly different focus – the WFD and the MSFD assessing functioning of the ecosystems and the ND on the amount and impact of nitrates inputs – but they are coherent in their substance regarding the main problem. The same goes for the instruments in the policies, as the WFD and the MSFD provide more general management frameworks for agricultural nutrient inputs, focusing on the design on national policy responses, while the ND provides more concrete and specific requirements for measures to be taken by the Member States in addressing and controlling inputs of nitrates in the waters. Furthermore, the assessment shows that the directives provide opportunities for the Member States to actively seek synergetic approach to their implementation, including deliberating and establishing the ND's nitrates vulnerable zones and areas of application of the action programs based on the geographical scopes of the WFD or the MSFD or any needs for regional differentiation detected under the implementation of river basin management planning or marine strategies.

In sum, the conclusion of the coherence assessment thus is that there are no major problems of incoherence or fragmentation within the cluster. There are only minor coherence issues, such as the ND's lack of objectives and regulation on phosphorus and the lack of deadline for achieving its objectives. By taking a synergetic and coherence-seeking approach to interpretation, the objectives and instruments can form a coherent and mutually reinforcing regime providing various instruments for tackling the problem of agriculture induced nutrient pollution and eutrophication.

However, the major challenge for this combined regime in legally operationalising the Green Deal's objectives on agricultural pollution is the continued lack of effectiveness and capacity to steer Member States in taking action to actually reduce nutrient pollution from agriculture.³⁵ All instruments in the cluster have continuously suffered from insufficient rigor in implementation by the Member States, with the effect that their objectives are far from being realised and agricultural pollution has not been reduced significantly at the European scale.³⁶ With regards to the WFD and the MSFD, while their objectives entail legal obligations for Member States to deliver improvements in the environmental conditions, the flexibilities in the form of obligations (the MSFD's best effort obligations) and exemptions (the WFD's flexible exemptions allowing exclusion of measures on economic and technical grounds) have provided wide margin of discretion to not address agricultural pollution effectively. With regard to the ND, the Directive has set clear requirements on the designation of vulnerable zones, drawing up action plans and adopting measures (Annex III) to reduce nitrates runoff, but has suffered from failures of Member States to set strict enough requirements to tackle the problem and over-reliance on voluntary-based measures. However, new interpretations of the ND's objectives and obligations championed particularly in the German nitrates -case by the CJEU may reinforce the directive on these aspects, or even force the Member States to act on

³⁵ Court of Auditors 2016.

³⁶ Court of Auditors 2016, p. 48.

agricultural nitrates pollution in the event that the failures to reach the objectives of the WFD and the MSFD are under exemption.

Background document – Coherence analysis of the EU fisheries and biodiversity policy cluster (the Common Fisheries Policy, the Habitats Directive, Marine Strategy Framework Directive)

The European Environment Agency reported in 2020 that fishing activities were responsible for some of the main pressures on ecosystems in Europe's seas, and the Intergovernmental Science Policy Platform on Biodiversity and Ecosystems Services reported in 2019 that fishing had the largest impact on marine ecosystems. To protect marine biodiversity in accordance with the objectives of the European Green Deal, a high level of coherence between legal instruments that regulate the pressures and protect the marine environment is necessary.

- 1) The policies fall under different competences and are different types of legal instruments with CFP being a regulation and MSFD and HD directives, dividing the responsibilities between the two and limiting Member States ability to apply proper measures on one of the largest pressures.*

Member States have only limited competence in adopting national measures regarding the fishing sector, even when they are acting upon obligations deriving from other EU statutes such as the HD or MSFD. As fishing is one of the largest pressures on marine biodiversity, this limits the Member States ability to enact proper measures in accordance with these directives and creates issues with the coordination of these legal instruments.

- 2) The jurisdictional issues limit the Member States' possibilities to enact protective measures.*

The Member States have limited capacity for their EEZ cannot impose restrictions on fishing activities beyond territorial waters without engaging in multilateral discussions. This complicates protection of the marine environment. Regional cooperation on conservations measures were adopted as a tool for this, but there are no legal obligations for the Member States to engage in such regional cooperation nor is there an obligation for the Commission to enact such measures. The regional influence could as such be seen as weak.

- 3) The objectives of the policies are inherently different as one concerns the protection of an industry, and the others concern protection of the environment.*

The CFP covers resource management and market measures, mainly to support the industry and boost the market. While resource management has clear overlaps with environmental protection, there are also differences in protection mainly for further exploitation and the protection of a natural environment. Further, the policy has historically focused on creating a stable industry and market, while the more restrictive measures have been added more recently. This division increases the need for policy transcending compromises and harmonising mechanisms to avoid coherence issues.

- 4) Article 11 provides a tool for Member States to apply conservation measures but has been deemed as complicated and ineffective.*

Article 11 of the CFP is intended to provide a tool for the Member States to enact conservation measures. The substantive scope is limited though as it only applies conservation measures that are deemed necessary for the effectiveness of MPAs. Further, Member States have not sought to use the tool as it is complicated, lengthy, and often deemed to lead to weak restrictions. This has further led to the ineffectiveness of MPAs in practice.

5) Other legal measures within CFP are insufficient to protect the marine biodiversity.

Other key measures in the CFP have also not been able to protect biodiversity. For example, the catch limits have not been able to prevent overfishing in a satisfying way, both due to the lack of reliable data and legal bindingness of MSY. Further, the funding from the policy has only in a limited extent been used to limit impact of fishing on the marine environment and more often funded activities that risk creating additional pressures on fish stocks and vulnerable marine habitats.

Background document – Coherence analysis of the EU agricultural and pollutions policies cluster (the Common Agricultural Policy and the Water Framework Directive)

The Common Agriculture Policy (CAP) is one of the oldest and most expensive EU policies with roots in the early 1960s and representing 31 % of the EU total budget. At its core, it has existed to support agricultural production, ensure food security, and promote rural development. At the same time, agricultural production has been one of the main pressures on both our water quality and quantity. While the CAP includes an objective to foster sustainable development and efficient management of natural resources such as water, the main policy for water quality is the Water Framework Directive (WFD). Tackling diffuse pollution from agriculture remains a key challenge for governments seeking to implement the WFD. To legally operationalise the European Green Deal objectives of zero pollution from the agricultural production to the marine environment, a high level of coherence between the CAP and the WFD is essential.

Implementation of the WFD has been significantly delayed due to insufficient integration of environmental objectives in sectoral policies. This is no different for the agricultural sector. While there are environmental objectives in the new CAP, these are added as an outer logic of the already existing policy. This has led to the introduction of legal instruments to address nutrient pollution within the CAP framework. However, the objectives are to a large extent contradictory as objectives on agricultural productivity and environmental production do not relate to each other. The CAP and the WFD risk ending up working against each other rather than in a harmonized way.

Agricultural pollution has not been reduced significantly at the European scale. Legally operationalising the Green Deal's objectives on agricultural pollution continues to be a challenge due to the continued lack of effectiveness and capacity to steer Member States in acting to reduce nutrient pollution from agriculture. This is partly due to the lack of legal bindingness and inability to adequately address agricultural sources of pollution in the river basin management plans. The CAP includes measures to promote sustainable agriculture, such as agri-environmental schemes, but their effectiveness in reducing nutrient pollution may vary across Member States. The success of nutrient mitigation becomes heavily reliant on efficient national implementation rather than a guarantee stemming from EU policies. The lack of integration means that agricultural production continues to contribute to nutrient pollution in an unsustainable way despite efforts to improve water quality.

The most important legal instrument of the CAP is the two funds, one for income support and the other for rural development. While there are funds for fostering sustainable development and efficient management of water, the largest share of the CAP budget goes to direct payments. Analysis of the fund allocation has found that CAP funds are more likely to promote greater rather than more efficient water use, resulting in a financial instrument that risk resulting in taking one step forward and two steps back.

Background document – Coherence analysis of the EU offshore wind power policy cluster (the EU Climate Law and the Renewables Directive III versus the biodiversity cluster)

The EU climate mitigation policies and the related legislation are heavily pushing for an increase in renewable energy generation, including offshore wind power generation. This aspiration is visible both in the overall goals of EU climate law (2021/1119) as well as the specific targets of the EU Renewable Energy Directive (RED III, 2023/2413). Developments in maritime spatial planning further emphasize these developments.

The EU climate law sets a legally binding climate neutrality goal for the member states by 2050 (arts. 1–2), with significant reductions in GHG emissions by 2030 (art. 4). These obligations are further operationalized by the EU Renewable energy directive, which requires member states to collectively ensure that at least 42,5 % of all gross energy consumed in the EU comes from renewable sources by 2030, with aspiration to hit 45 %. According to the directive, renewable energy means energy from renewable, non-fossil sources, including wind power on land and in marine areas (RED III, art. 2). Many EU member states, Finland included, are expecting considerable increase in offshore wind power development in the coming decade. To this end, the RED III establishes several measures, such as promoting state incentives for renewables (e.g., grid integration), alleviated Environmental Impact Assessment (art. 16b(2)), national contact points for renewable permitting (art. 16(3)), time limits on permit processes to speed them up (art. 16(2); art. 16a(1); art. 16b(1)) as well as mapping (art. 15b) and specification of renewable acceleration areas (art. 15c). Most importantly, and despite the directive establishing a general obligation not to locate renewable energy projects in Natura 2000 areas or areas otherwise protected by the Habitats (92/43/EC) and Birds (2009/147/EC) Directives, RED III states that renewable energy projects automatically fulfill the overriding public interest requirement that is one of the key criteria for granting exemptions from biodiversity protection (RED III art. 16f). In tandem with these developments, the EU Maritime Spatial Planning Directive (2014/89/EU) requires member states to establish maritime spatial plans by 2021, the purpose of which is to facilitate co-location of several marine activities, including offshore wind power generation, shipping, fishing, aquaculture, and nature conservation (art. 4 and 5). One of the explicit aims of the directive is to promote economic growth in the maritime sector, such as offshore wind (art. 5).

The heavy promotion of renewable energy, including offshore wind power generation, cannot be realized without tradeoffs to the biodiversity of the marine environment. Currently, the most widely used offshore wind power technologies need to be anchored to the sea floor with concrete structures. Moreover, the wingspan of the wind turbines can be several hundred meters with wind power parks encompassing typically dozens or even hundreds of installations. This translates into considerable

Annex II – Summaries of the preliminary findings for each cluster used for interviews

need for space for the installations. This may conflict with the Sea Floor Integrity requirement of the Marine Strategy Framework Directive (2008/56/EC) as part and parcel of the Good Environmental Status of marine areas. This challenge is made worse by the lack of scientific knowledge concerning the status of marine waters and seafloor integrity. Moreover, in many cases the most economically feasible areas for operation are in shallow banks, which are typically also rich in biodiversity and may enjoy the protection of the Habitats and Birds Directives (either as part of Natura 2000 networks, or as containing species and their spawning areas protected by the nature directives). Even though the RED III establishes a general rule for not locating offshore wind power operations in legally protected areas, exemptions are increasingly easy to obtain due to the overriding public interest easement. All in all, despite efforts to integrate climate change mitigation and biodiversity goals in EU legislation, there is considerable incoherence between legal frameworks in the context of offshore wind power.